

**ERÚSHÍÚ–YORÙBÁ ENDOGLOSSIC BILINGUALISM
AND LANGUAGE ALTERNATION IN AKOKO,
SOUTHWESTERN NIGERIA**

By

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DEDICATION

To

GOD ALMIGHTY

For HIS Tender Mercies Over Me

CERTIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

Language contact between Erúshú and Yorùbá has resulted in massive shift from Erúshú, thus, the language now faces a precarious problem of extinction in the near future. This study therefore examines Erúshú-Yorùbá endoglossic bilingualism in Akoko, Ondo State. It specifically explores respondents' abilities in Erúshú and Yorùbá, their language use, language attitude and language alternation pattern. This will enable us to fully understand the sociolinguistic concomitants of societal bilingualism in this community.

The study adopts survey and non-participant observation methods. Subjects for the study comprised 300 respondents. The purposive sampling technique has been employed in that only subjects who are bilingual in Erúshú and Yorùbá were used for the study. The major instrument used in data collection is the questionnaire. The seven null hypotheses postulated are tested using the T-test, chi-square, the analysis of variance and simple percentages.

The basic finding of this study is the dominance of Yorùbá in all domains over Erúshú. For instance, while 71 percent of our respondents know Yorùbá excellently, only 45.7 per cent attain this level of proficiency for Erúshú. The results reveal that at 0.05 level of significance, there is a significant difference in the level of subjects' mastery of Erúshú with respect to age and context as well as their mastery of Yorùbá with respect to education. The study discovers that older respondents possess better mastery of Erúshú than the younger ones. For the former group virtually every respondent (96.9%) speaks Erúshú very well whereas 65.0 per cent of

the latter group speaks Erúshú very well. Again, the well-educated ones display greater facility in Yorùbá than the less educated ones although this appears a typical. However, findings reveal that other variables: sex (with the t-test results of 0.593 for Erúshú and 0.211 for Yorùbá), occupation (the F calculated which is 0.885 is less than the table value of 2.60) and place of acquisition (the F calculated, 1.522, is less than the table value 2.60) are not statistically significant. Language use pattern in Erúshú community reveals a case of language shift in that children are gradually giving up the mastery of Erúshú in preference for Yorùbá and English. Thus, Erúshú can be said to be endangered by this preference. In terms of language attitude, subjects demonstrate a positive attitude towards Erúshú although this does not reflect in their language use. At the structural level, Erúshú borrows heavily from Yorùbá. However, Erúshú interferes with Yorùbá at the phonetic level as evident in their Akoko-accented Yorùbá.

The study re-affirms the reality of language endangerment in Nìgeria. Language as a resource encapsulates the wealth of man's intellectual endowment, hence, efforts must be made to ensure inter-generational continuity of every language. In this regard, the work underscores the need for a more concerted effort between the users of the language, the linguists and language policy makers to forge a symbiotic relationship in ensuring the continued existence of minor languages as language is a veritable resource.

Keywords: Endoglossic Bilingualism, Language Alternation, Language Shift, Language Endangerment, Erúshú-Akoko

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CHAPTER ONE

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

1.0 Introductory Remarks

The present study is an attempt at understanding the linguistic forces behind the co-existence of two indigenous languages in a Nigerian community. The study examines societal bilingualism in Erúshú¹ community, a village in Àkókó North-West Local Government of Ondo State. The Erúshú language, the native tongue of Erúshú community, has co-existed with the Yorùbá language in this community for about a century now without being sumsumed. It is needless to say that certain sociolinguistic factors must have been responsible for the maintenance of this mother tongue, and this we hope to lay bare in the study.

The multilingual nature of most Nigerian communities makes them a ready choice for sociolinguistic investigation since change is inevitable when languages are in contact. According to Egbokhare (2004:511) "the linguistic ecology of any multilingual setting is always in a state of change, even if insignificantly." The Erúshú community typifies a truly multilingual setting. We believe that certain sociolinguistic concomitants of the language contact situation such as bilingualism, language choice, language attitude, etc would be evident in this place, hence our decision to investigate such phenomena in concrete terms.

1.1 Area of Study

1.1.1 The Àkókó Community

The old Ondo State was split into the present Ondo and Ekiti States in October 1996 by the Military government in power then. The old Ondo State was a state within the nineteen-state structure of the Federal Republic of Nigeria created in February 1976. Again, the new Ondo State is also a state within the thirty-six state structure of the Federal Republic of Nigeria as at today.

Akoko Community used to be just two local governments in the old Ondo State viz: Akoko North Local Government and Akoko South Local Government. Erúshú community, the very focus of study, belonged then to Akoko North Local Government Area. At present, Akoko Community is made up of four local governments as follows: Akoko North-East Local Government with the headquarters at Ikare; Akoko North-West Local Government with the headquarters at Oke-Agbe; Akoko South-East Local Government with the headquarters at Isua; and Akoko South-West Local Government with the headquarters at Oka. Akokoland, according to Aminu and Kolawole (2001:1), is within longitude 5° E and 6° E and latitudes 7° N and $7^{\circ} 45$ N. To the North and North-East, it is bounded by Kabba and Yagba areas of Kogi State. To the North-West, South and West, it shares common boundaries with Ekiti East, Owo and Ekiti South Local Government respectively. In the East, Akoko-Edo Local Government bounds it. The foregoing probably accounts for its multilingual nature. On the contrary, ecological disasters or natural barriers like hills, mountains, rivers, jungles which have now given way due to time might have been responsible for the multilingual nature of this community.

With the present local government division in Akoko, Erúshú is located within the Akoko North-West Local Government Area of Ondo State. Other relevant information about Erúshú will be given in the next section. Suffice to say for now that Ondo State is of a fact ethnolinguistically heterogeneous. The different groups within Ondo State include: the Akoko, the Akure, the Ondo, the Ilaje and the Ijaw, all of who belonged to the Yoruba ethnic group except the Ijaw – Arogbo and the Ijaw–Apoi who are not of Yorùbá origin (Personal Communication with Dr. Shoki).

1.1.1.1 Languages

Two major indigenous languages are recognized officially² within Ondo State (see 1991 census). The two languages are Yorùbá and Ijaw. Yorùbá is a lingua franca within the state. Moreover, the little fraction that speak Ijaw–Apoi have been assimilated by the Yorùbá. The Ijaws had to fight for recognition within Ondo State since there is no cultural similarity between this ethnic group and the Yoruba group. Really, the situation of the Akoko group is comparable to that of the Ijaws. Virtually

every language spoken in Akoko land is not mutually intelligible with Yoruba. Such languages, according to Abiodun (2000:3), include Akpes, Owon (i. e. Erúshù, Iye, Afa)³, Epira, Okpamheri and Edo languages.

Abiodun (2000:317) reports further that Ukaan, Akpes and Owon are the major languages within the Northern Akoko cluster (NAC)⁴. In these subsequent studies, two of the languages, Akpes and Ukaan are grouped together to form a major unit within the Benue-Congo phylum, while Owon comes under Akokoid, a group of Defoid (Capo 1989). Capo asserts that the term Owon⁵ is a prefix for dialects of a language with an unknown name. Since these dialects are mutually intelligible we talk of Owon - Erúshù, Owon-Iye, Owon-Afa. Indeed, 'Owon' means language in these dialects. Thus, it is like saying the Erúshù language, Iye language, etc. The necessity of the Owon prefix is that with it, we can easily isolate the dialects of the same language among the various dialects and languages in Akokoland.

Moreover, the contemporary socio-political situation of Nigeria reveals the fact that Akokoland was part of the old Western Region, which lasted between 1947 and 1963. This has linguistic implication in that Yoruba in addition to English became the second official language in most parts of the Region (cf. Oyetade, 2003; Egbokhare, 2004). Thus, Yoruba was able to spread beyond its geographical location to this border areas where their primary languages are not Yoruba.

Indeed, Akokoland has the highest number of languages and dialects among the various regions/districts in Ondo State. While Ekiti State (recently carved out of Ondo State) is homogeneous in terms of language, Ondo is not. Meanwhile, Akoko together with the Ilaje people are the outstanding cases of the heterogeneity within Ondo State in terms of language. The Àkókó can be described as a race that is monocultural but multilingual in that they have many languages but yet of one race. Indeed, this contrast with some multilingual communities (cf. Dorian 1981; Oyetade 1990; Pye 1992, Fakuade 1995, 2003; David, et al 2003) which are at the same time multiracial and multiethnic.

The assumption in history is that the present settlers of the Akoko Land today could not have been the original settlers of this land. The belief is that they (the present settlers) must have migrated from places like Ile-Ife, Benin and Kabba

province. (Beeley (1934:13), Akintoye (1971), Abiodun (2000:2), Oyetade (2003:6))

1.1.2 The Erúshú Community

Erúshú is a village with a pattern of linear settlement along Ikare-Kabba road in Akoko North-West Local Government Area of Ondo State of Nigeria. This Local Government happens to share a common boundary with three states in Nigeria viz. Kogi, Edo and Ekiti. This, therefore, explains the heterogeneous nature of the community. Going by the 1991 population census in Nigeria, Akoko North West has a population of 119,278 with the Erúshú community amounting to 5,326 out of this figure. The projected population for 1996 is 5,996 people. In terms of the landed area, Erúshú is about 8 sq. kilometres.

The Erúshú language is the native tongue of the people of Erúshú. However, the lingua franca of these people is Yoruba and they also regard themselves as Yorùbá by tribe. The written accounts before the 20th century of this settlement are very scanty. However, we were able to gather good information through interview from Chief Osunla, the Oba of the village and Mr. Olugboja (the Balogun of Erúshú, a retired principal) that the people actually came from Ife.

Erúshú is made up of four quarters, which are: Aga, Okesan, Okega and Amo. These four quarters are administered by one Oba, the Osunla of Erúshú, whose palace is at Okega, the third quarters in the town.

In terms of tradition and oral literature, Erúshú shares everything like food, dressing, marriage, etc. with the Yoruba. However, this will not be the central concern of this study.

1.1.2.1 Social Amenities

Erúshú has pipe-borne water with a waterworks situated in the village. According to Osunla, the Oba of Erúshú, the waterworks was constructed in 1955. It also enjoys electricity supplied by PHCN (formerly NEPA). The village also has tarred road, a Postal Agency and one central modern market at Okega where the palace of the Oba is situated. A comprehensive health centre is also available in this

community. The comprehensive health centre actually started as a maternity ward and a dispensary centre in the 50's.

1.1.2.2 Education

The village has three primary schools. That is, each quarter (with the exception of Okesan, the smallest quarter) has its own. Again, there are two secondary schools in this village. The first one named Commercial Secondary School, Erúshù is at Aga; the second, Erúshù Comprehensive High School is at Amo, the last quarters when leaving the town for Ikaramu. That is, the two are located at two extremes. Of recent, however, due to the dwindling number of pupils in the secondary school, located at Aga, the students there have been merged with the ones at Amo.

1.1.2.3 Economic Activities

The main economic preoccupations of Erúshù people are agriculture, pottery and trading. The men engage themselves in farming while women are engaged in pot making and trading. As already mentioned, a central market is at Okega, the quarters where the king lives. Other quarters and even neighbouring towns and villages do bring wares to this market once in five days for sale. This community extends her trading activities to neighbouring towns like Ikare, Arigidi, Ikaramu and Ajowa. People come from neighbouring towns to buy pots, cassava flour (láfún) and some other farm produce while they go out to buy kolanut, melon, rice, beans, salt, clothes, etc, from other places.

1.1.2.4 Religion

Different types of religious beliefs are practised in this community. Indeed, the village has a number of different churches. On the one hand, the list of orthodox churches includes The Baptist Church, The C. M. S and The African Church. On the other hand, the list of Pentecostal churches includes The C. A. C and the Deeper Life Bible Church. It is needless to say that a few muslims as well as the adherents of African Traditional Religion also form part of this community.

Thus, all religions practised in the country are represented in the area.

1.1.2.5 The Sociolinguistic Profile of Erúshú Community

Two indigenous languages, Erúshú and Yorùbá are predominantly spoken in Erúshú town. English, the official language in Nigeria is also used as a medium of expression in schools.

Other languages found in this community which however are of minor use here are: Epira, Hausa and Igbo. It is needless to say that the domains of the routine use of these languages differ considerably. Indeed, the kind of bilingualism found in this community is to be determined in this work. From mere observation, we discovered that there is no indigene, young or old, in this community that cannot speak the two major languages in use here. The domain of language use in this community shall be part of our analysis in this work.

1.2 Choice of Study Area

Erúshú town has been chosen for this study because of many reasons. Akokoland itself is an interesting sociolinguistic terrain for any linguist of our time. Meanwhile, Erúshú happens to be one of the many small communities in this geographical location where the researcher spent his youthful days. The researcher's knowledge of this part of the country is also an indispensable tool in gathering sociolinguistic data like the present one.

Furthermore, since Akokoland is like the biblical Tower of Babel, this site is just suitable for anyone interested in bilingualism and its features. Incidentally too, Akoko North West Local Government where Erúshú is located is a border local government in Ondo State with Ekiti State to its west, Kogi State to its north, and Edo State to its east. The implication of this is a cross-current of linguistic activities within this local government.

In the past, Erúshú was blessed with a commercial bank (National Bank of Nigeria now defund), a postal agency, two secondary schools, and three primary schools. Still in the list are a native court, a good service market and many churches already mentioned. In spite of the reduction in these infrastructures, the fact remains that bilingualism still thrives in this community.

Moreover, the absence of earlier, in-depth linguistic or sociolinguistic work of any kind on Erúshú language makes work of the present kind very desirable.

1.3 Erúshú Language and Its Speakers

Erúshú language is one of the minority languages in Nigeria with speakers spread over five villages. Indeed, Erúshú is a dialect of Arigidi clusters. In fact, not much is available on Erúshú language by way of literature. Up till today very little or no scholarly work has so far been done on Erúshú language. The available ones are undergraduate essays and Masters project works dealing with one aspect or the other of the language. Available published materials on Erúshú language include Greenberg (1963), Williamson (1973a), Hoffmann (1974), Akinkugbe (1980), Capo (1987), Williamson (1989) and Adeniyi and Ojo (2005). The present work has benefited to some extent from the few works mentioned above.

The name 'Owon' has been used in the literature by scholars including Agoyi (1997:10) to refer to the different speech forms spoken in Arigidi, Erúshú, Iye, and parts of Oke-Agbe, and Igassi, all in Akoko North West Local Government Area of Ondo State. There is mutual intelligibility in the speech pattern of these more or less five different communities. It should be noted, however, that the people of each of these towns call their town and language by the same name. We make haste to add that the term 'owon' is inappropriate for this group of dialects since it is just a prefix meaning 'language'. As noted earlier on in this work, Capo (1989) opines that 'owon' is just a prefix for dialects of a language with an unknown name⁶

According to the 1991 national census, Erúshú language has about 23,655 speakers spread over three communities viz Erúshú, Arigidi and Iye in particular. Invariably that means for the three communities today, the number of speakers cannot be less than 35,000 people. In Erúshú community today, the number of speakers is estimated at about 8,000.

Native speakers are also found in different parts of two other towns in Akoko North West Local Government Area of Ondo State namely, Oke-Agbe, and Igaasi.

These communities are, geographically speaking, situated on Yoruba soil, thereby making the Erúshú language to co-exist side by side with the Yoruba language.

1.3.1 The History of Erúshú speakers

Very little is known of the history of Erúshú language speakers. Documented historical sources, which are very scanty, claim that the people are descendants of Oduduwa. Our research through oral sources also confirmed this assertion. A section of the Akoko people (Erúshú inclusive) migrated from Ile-Ife to the Old-Benin Kingdom only to move from there, under pressure of constant wars, to their present settlement in Akoko (Beeley 1934:13, Akintoye 1971, Abiodun 2000:2, Oyetade 2003:6).

1.3.2 Genetic Classification of Erúshú

Erúshú language is a member of a group of languages referred to as the Northern Akoko cluster (Williamson 1973a). Hoffmann (1974), following Williamson's suggestion has classified this group of languages as sub-group 'b' of the Yoruba group while Yoruba, Itsekiri and Igala constitute the sub-group 'a'. (Akinkugbe 1980). Subsequent studies, however, caused the claim to be revised. Capo (1987) and Williamson (1989:267) argued that the relationship between the languages is not close enough to justify calling them a cluster. Thus, Northern Akoko cluster has been dropped.

Two of the three major languages in Akoko North, Akpes and Ukaan have been grouped to form a major unit within the Benue-Congo phylum, while Owon comes under Akokoid, a group of Defoid languages (Capo 1987). Below is the sub-classification of Benue-Congo as presented in Williamson (1989:261) and Abiodun (2004:15).

Table 1:

Benue-Congo

Source: Abiodun (2000:317, 2004:15)

1.3.3 A Comparative Analysis of the Structure of Erúshú and Yorùbá

In this section, we present a brief comparative analysis of the structures of both Erúshú and Yoruba languages. This will enable us to understand how the two languages merge structurally since we intend to discuss code-mixing in this work. In what follows, we attempt to provide a brief comparative analysis of the structures (phonology and syntax) of both Erúshú and Yoruba languages. The sound inventories in both Erúshú and Yoruba are displayed below as tables 2 and 3 respectively.

Table 2: Erúshú Vowel chart (phonemic)

Source: Dada (1987: 12)

Table 3: Yoruba Vowel Chart

Source: Owolabi (1989 : 84-85)

A comparison of the two vowel charts shows that there is no difference between the vowel systems of the two languages.

Table 4: Consonants

		Erùshú	Yorùbá
Plosive	Bilabial	b	b
	Alveolar	t d	t d
	Velar	k g	k g
	Labio-velar	kp gb	kp gb
Nasal	Bilabial	m	m
	Alveolar	[n]	[n]
Affricate	Palato-alveolar	dʒ	dʒ
Fricative	Labio-dental	f v	f
	Alveolar	s	s
	Palato-alveolar	ʃ	ʃ
	Glottal	h	h
Lateral	Alveolar	l	l
Trill	Alveolar	r	r
Approximant	Palatal	J	j
	Labio-velar	w	w

Source Dada (1987:6) and Owolabi (1989:50)

Once again, in the consonant systems of the two languages there is no significant difference which could result into pronunciation error on the part of Erùshú speakers of Yoruba.

1.3.3.1 Syllable Structure

In both Erúshú and Yoruba, the possible syllable structures are V or CV. Moreover, the /n/ sound in both languages is syllabic, hence it conforms to the v pattern by carrying a tone just like a vowel.

Erúshú examples:

V		CV		V-CV	
/à/	'he, she, it'	/dè/	'steal'	/ń -da/	'nine'
/ò/	'us'	/va/	'come'	/o-to/	'ear'
/ì/	'his'	/hò/	'old'	/ε-ʃ ε/	'pepper'

Since the two languages have similar syllabic pattern, Erúshú speakers of Yoruba experience no difficulty in this area too.

1.3.3.2 Syntax

First, both languages operate the SVO constituent order in their sentences. Consider the following parallel structures which have identical meanings.

1. Èlé ó wu uwà (Erúshú)
Íyá wa lọ oko (Yoruba)
'Our mother has gone to farm'.
2. Máà se òwòn mé (Erúshú)
Èmi ko gbó èdè yín (Yorùbá)
'I don't understand your language'

Thus in the Erúshú/Yoruba CS, we should expect the syntactic frame of all sentences to be in the SVO order. Where there are changes in a structure, it may be stylistic rather than syntactic.

Again, another area of convergence is that both languages lack conjugations and declensions that are characteristic of languages like Latin, Japanese and Swahili. Thus, both are genetically related.

Moreover, both are synthetic in that some of their grammatical relationships can be expressed by adding affixes to root morphemes. Consider the following examples:

	Erúshú		Yorùbá
3a.	á ri vè 'He/she/ it goes/		Ó n lọ 'He/she/ it goes/ is going
b.	á si vè 'He will go'		Ó maa lọ 'He will go'
c.	á vè 'He she/it went'		Ó lọ 'He went'
d.	/iriʃɔ/ 'fish owner'		Eleja 'fish owner'
e.	iriʃu 'yam owner'		'onisu' 'yam owner'

As evident in the examples above, the verbs *vè* and *lọ* in the two languages are not inflected for person or tense. Thus, the two languages have a number of words that do not vary in structure while some others have morpheme components, thereby, confirming that both Erúshú and Yoruba languages are synthetic.

1.4 Statement of the Problem

Based on the few available records on Akokoland, the co-existence of Erúshù and Yoruba dates as far back as the beginning of the 20th Century. Yet very little is known about the Erúshù language while the Yoruba language has witnessed a lot of developments.

Moreover, from all indications - political, economic, social, educational and cultural - Erúshù language is no threat to Yoruba language with respect to the latter's status as a national⁸ language with more than a hundred years of extensive and recorded literary output.

Today, Yoruba is a lingua franca⁹ in six states (Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Oşun Ondo and Ekiti) of the Federation with a combined total population of about 25,000,000 people (Igboanusi and Peter 2005). Yorùbá is also used as a first language in parts of Kwara, Kogi, Edo and Delta states. In addition, Yoruba is a potent language for countless thousands of Nigerians whose mother tongues differ from this language. These 'aliens' learn Yoruba in addition to their mother tongues because they are resident in the community.

The number of individuals who speak Yoruba language as their first language¹⁰ all over Nigeria today is probably close to 40,000,000 while that of Erúshù language across five villages is just about 35,000 going by the 1991 population census. The foregoing reveals the fact that the political status of Yorùbá is incomparable with that of Erúshù. Yet, both of them have been co-existing now for over a century (Banjo 1979:8). Thus we ask: will standard Yoruba wipe out Erúshù language? If not, why not? This is the main thrust of this study.

With this background, Erúshù language ought to have been phased out of existence completely given the many years of its co-existence with Yoruba, but for some sociolinguistic factors which this work sets out to examine.

1.5 Aims and Objectives

We shall examine the use of language (or the dynamics of language contact and bi-multilingualism¹¹) in this bilingual community. Again, we shall try to discover those changes that are taking place in the structures of Erúshù and Yoruba

as a result of the contact situation. As we know, when languages come in contact they exert certain influences on each other at two major levels, namely, social and structural. This work intends to explore the two dimensions of the contact situation between Erúshú and Yoruba.

The specific objectives of the present study are:

- 1) to determine the abilities (degree of proficiency) of our respondents in Erúshú and Yorùbá languages with a view to establishing their dominant language.
- 2) to lay bare the type of societal bilingualism (stable or unstable) found in this community. This we consider to be a natural corollary to (1).
- 3) to examine language use in specific domains. In doing this, the different domains of use of the different languages in Erúshú community will be examined. The data again will serve as another opportunity at re-examining the concept of diglossia as it operates in an African environment. In addition, the study shall establish why Erúshú language could resist for so long the daily on-slaught it receives from Yoruba.
- 4) to examine the linguistic as well as the sociolinguistic implications of the co-existence of Erúshú and Yorùbá languages with a view to speculating the future implications. Thus, the structure of these two languages in contact will be examined for effects such as, interference and code-switching so as to determine the extent of interference between the two languages.

1.6 Research Questions, Hypotheses and Assumptions

This section highlights the research questions, the hypotheses formulated as well as the assumptions underlying them.

1.6.1 Research Questions

The highlights of the research questions are as follows:

- (1) To what extent has this category of bilinguals mastered their two languages, that is, in terms of production and comprehension?
- (2) Do the subjects' degrees of bilingualism determine their language choice?
- (3) What are the specific situations of use for each of the languages under investigation?
- (4) Do the subjects' degrees of bilingualism vary with regard to demographic, socio-economic and socio-cultural variables?
- (5) What noticeable pattern or tendency exists in usage among this category of bilinguals? Specifically, is the direction of use of these two languages leading the community towards maintenance of or shift from either of their two languages?
- (6) How do the subjects view their two languages in terms of importance? That is, what is their attitude to the two languages in question?
- (7) What are the social functions of code-switching/code-mixing in this community?
- (8) To what extent could code-switching be regarded as a function of the relative dominance of one of the two languages under investigation?
- (9) Is code-switching, in fact, a question of who speaks what language to whom and when (Fishman, 1965)?

1.6.2 Hypotheses and Motivating Assumptions

The hypotheses have been formulated in consonance with the practice in sociological research. Thus, they are negatively stated. That is, they are null hypotheses. The research hypothesis is proved if the null hypothesis is rejected. However, if the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, then the research hypothesis is not valid.

Ho¹: There is no significant difference between the proficiency of our subjects in the two languages, Erúshú and Yoruba.

Converse: There is a significant difference in the level of proficiency in Erúshú and Yoruba among our subjects.

Motivation: The privileged position of Yoruba in the formal school system, coupled with the fact that it is a major language in Nigeria, has made it to be more dominant than Erúshú. It is therefore assumed that our subjects are more likely to learn Yoruba at the expense of Erúshú.

Ho²: There is no significant difference in the degree of proficiency of subjects in the two languages in different contexts. That is, there is no significant difference in bilingual proficiency as compared with bilingual usage.

Motivation: Languages in contact perform complementary roles. But then, the popular view is that the degree of bilingual proficiency is proportional to bilingual usage.

After all, certain subjects are better discussed in some languages than in some others.

Ho³: Male and female subjects do not differ significantly in their proficiency in the two languages.

Motivation: To determine if this societal bilingualism is sex-determined. Research findings on this issue is inconclusive. Some works on societal bilingualism

have proved that linguistic ability in L2 is sex-determined and that the result could be in favour of the men or the women depending on the community. Examples like Lieberson (1981) and O' Barr (1971) cited in Oyetade (1990), Adeniran (1982), and David and Naji (2000) presented men as more bilingual than the women.

However, other examples like Garai and Scheifield (1968), Wilkinson (1975) and Aitchison (1976), Obanya (1976) and Ginet (1992) are of the view that women have better fluency and greater facility with L2 than men. Thus, the foregoing attests to the fact that the result could be either way in Erúshú community (cf. Wodak and Benke (1997).

H0⁴: There is no significant difference between subjects belonging to different age groups in their proficiency in the two languages.

Motivation: Psycholinguists believe that language learning is maturational, hence, the necessity of examining the influence of age on language use in this community. Previous works of this nature say that youths are more proficient in their L2 than adults (O' Barr 1971; Doriar 1981, Oyetade 1995, 2004; David et al 2003) and that adults are more proficient with regard to L1 than youths.

This study stands to either refute or assert this position.

H0⁵: Subjects will not differ in their proficiency in the second language as a result of their levels of education (Scotton 1972).

Motivation: Previous research work (Hoffman 1994, David et al 2003) in this area revealed that education exerts an influence on the L₂ such that the educated group exhibited a superior knowledge of L₂ in relation to the uneducated group once the L₂ is the language or one of the languages used in education.

Our findings here will either affirm or debunk the general theoretical postulations on the role of education in bilingual acquisition.

H0⁶: Subjects will not differ in their proficiency in the two languages as a result of their occupation.

Motivation: Occupation or economic factor has also played a significant role (Scotton (1972), Harrison and Pieter's (1980) in Cheng (2003), Lewis (1982), Wardhaugh (1987) and Fakuade (1998)) in second language acquisition. Thus, occupation could be a probable variable in language variation within the community of study. Our findings on this will reveal the actual situation.

H0⁷: There is no significant difference between subjects in their proficiency in the two languages with regard to different places of their acquisition.

Motivation: To discover the influence of a demographic factor on bilingual proficiency, since different contexts of language use present varying opportunities for language acquisition. It is thus assumed that a language used in the neighbourhood, home and in school will enjoy a better mastery than the one acquired only at home.

1.7 The Significance of the Study

An empirical sociolinguistic investigation like the present work on two indigenous Nigerian languages holds forth both theoretical and pragmatic benefits. Beardsmore (1982) asserts that the scope of such investigation can be very wide and can be of use to language policy makers and language planners, educational strategists, social engineers and communication specialists.

This study is an in-depth work with respect to endoglossic bilingualism in Erúshú. The work contributes to our understanding of some sociolinguistic concomitants of societal bilingualism such as language choice, language attitudes and code-mixing either at the local level or even globally. This can assist language planners and influence language policy decisions within the country. Thus, the present study contributes in a modest way to the existing literature on bi-/multilingualism in general and bi-/multilingual language choice in Nigeria in particular.

The work also contributes to knowledge in the area of language contact and conflict. That is, the study reveals the inevitable change in an African community that is dependent on western ideals and ethics as a result of our colonization. The consequence of this is reflected in the transition in the community of study from endoglossic bilingualism to that of semi-endoglossic. This result is useful in predicting current trends in bilingualism in Nigeria. This changing pattern reveals the need to improve the level of competence of Nigerians in their mother tongues as a means of securing the future of these minor minority languages.

The study presents a more revealing analysis of the influence exerted by a major indigenous language on a minor one when co-existing side by side within a community; that is, as opposed to bilingualism among two contiguous ethnolinguistic groups already investigated in some sociolinguistic works in Nigeria. The study presents in very clear terms the 'gobbling' effect of Yoruba over the minority language in this community of study in particular and over the other minority languages in general in the western region of Nigeria. It has thrown enough light on what the co-existence pattern of two indigenous languages look like in Southwestern Nigeria which can be very useful for language engineering within the country.

Indeed most minor Nigerian languages today, as evident in this study, face extinction not only because children are not taught the languages, but rather because even those that have been taught are not encouraged to speak them. Thus, studies such as this on language shift and language endangerment will no doubt go a long way in generating and sustaining awareness among Nigerians on the necessity of using with pride their mother-tongues, whether a major or a minor language. This is a sure way of preserving these languages as well as the identities they represent.

One of the pragmatic results and values of the present study is the implications it holds for the teaching and learning of Yorùbá in the area of study in particular and for the teaching and learning of second languages in general. The structural examination done here is on two indigenous languages. This could be a useful guide to the educational strategists in designing and evaluating bilingual education programmes especially in multilingual states of Nigeria. Again, the result

of this structural examination reveals that code-mixing is a function of a dominant language over a minor, less prestigious one. An extensive study of code-mixing as presented here has something to contribute to our knowledge in the area of language accommodation and intercultural communication.

For over three decades now, there have been attempts on the part of Nigerian government and some other agencies to promote indigenous languages and grant them 'value' by making them perform some of the functions that the English language has always performed in the national life of the country. However, despite declarations of intent and spirited efforts by some private organizations to introduce these languages into formal domains, very little success has been recorded in this regard. It is in this light therefore, that this study informs on the attitudes of native speakers of Erùshù towards the Yorùbá language. The study can be used by the government to predict the reactions of this group in case the Yorùbá language is granted more functions in this nation's socio-political life.

Still on the language attitudes, the study has implications for the country's socio-political well-being in that mother tongue speakers of minority languages are now apathetic towards the learning of their languages. This situation may eventually lead to the loss of the nation's rich cultural heritage which is that of unity in diversity.

Again, the spread of the Yorùbá language in the study area is of great relevance to communication experts. The result of the present study can help solve language-related problems of professions outside education. For instance, communication difficulties and breakdowns have been studied in the medical services delivery system (Coulmas 1997:10). Thus, the study arms professionals such as doctors, nurses, population census officers, agricultural extension officers, and even youth corpsers, etc in the nation with the knowledge of the language necessary for operation in this part of the country. By this analysis, a professional wishing to work in this area now knows that the Language of Wider Communication (LWC) in this area is Yorùbá. Hence, a knowledge of the two indigenous languages in this community may not be necessary to be a successful professional worker in this area.

The dominance of Yorùbá in virtually all domains over the mother tongue in the area of study and the resultant language shift should be of particular interest to the social engineer. The work reveals the need for interdisciplinary approach to language study in the country all with a view to ensuring inter-generational continuity of every language. This particular result should challenge all stakeholders with respect to mother tongue maintenance to now think of how best to salvage those lesser known languages from extinction. The die is cast. To do nothing is to invite shame and 'death'. To act boldly now is to recognize right as well as reality even in matters of language use.

Finally, the study which intends to study societal bilingualism in all its ramifications presents the government with insights on better ways of ensuring the survival of the minority languages in Nigeria in particular and in the world at large.

As evident thus far, this chapter presents the background to the study. Thus the chapter contains the history of the community of study, the structure of the two indigenous languages in contact in this community, the problem investigated in the study as well as the significance and limitations of this study. All these constitute the background information upon which the whole research work is hinged. The next chapter will focus on a review of the related literature on language use, and language alternation.

1.8 Limitations of this Study

As the saying goes, every study has some limitations. These limitations are factors that the researcher was aware of but could do nothing about, because of the nature of the subject. Even then, the normal practice in behavioural research is to indicate these limitations so that future researchers may be aware of them and take adequate steps to ensure validity.

Inherent in a sociolinguistic research work of this nature is the methodological problem of devising adequate technique for obtaining reliable information about language proficiency and attitudes towards languages and their owners. The problem is further compounded by our efforts at trying to use Western

Social Science survey technique to elicit sociolinguistic data among traditional peoples.

The nature of the problem being reported here is succinctly captured in the words of Akere (1982:344) as follows:

In many indigenous, African communities, the low level of literacy coupled with the general lack of enthusiasm on the part of the inhabitants to trust the good intentions of researchers, render the use of sophisticated techniques for measuring language competence and language attitudes impracticable. This makes it necessary for the researcher to have recourse to informants' opinions and self-reports.

History has repeated itself in that, the present work met with the constraints stated above. Thus, the work meant with the constraints of having to rely primarily on informants' self-reports on their language use as well as their opinions about the speech communities that use them. The researcher had to adopt the transaction count (non-participant observation method) as a way of ensuring the validity of the results obtained here.

The self-report type of instrument itself has limitations in that it is usually very difficult to determine the accuracy of the statements made by the subjects in self-reported data. Indeed, this researcher had to go back to the field several times to be able to get enough accurate information from the respondents. Initially, the participants were very deceptive in their answers because they thought that I was working for the government. Moreover, copies of the questionnaire were administered to both literates and illiterates. Thus, translating and reading out of the questions to the illiterates might have influenced their responses.

Indeed, the predictive power of the result of this work in respect of the linguistic situation in Nigeria has been limited by the very nature of the study which is a non-governmental one. Since the present study is a personal research effort then its predictive power has been seriously limited to its very source.

The result got from the present study, all things being equal, is in fact applicable to other endoglossic bilingual situations in the country without any fear of

contradiction. However, we can not make such a generalization now since the community of study was not selected out of many others in the country after a consideration of several factors. Moreover, the power to generalize and act lies with the government. That is the more reason we feel that the present result, useful as it is to bilingual education as well as to language engineering within the country, is somehow incapacitated by the very nature (personal and academic) of the study. Thus, until we are able to make our findings known to the government through the appropriate channels, our findings will remain an academic gymnastic.

Furthermore, the reactions of the Nigerian government in the past to education, especially, research efforts like this have not been encouraging. Therefore, even when this result is made public, are we sure the government will take the appropriate steps bearing in mind that attitudes are not inborn or accidental. They are learned and absorbed reactions which could therefore be changed. It only needs than co-operation of the subjects concerned.

Because of the limitations of the present study, there are still viable areas of the study which could be researched into. The study has made an attempt to identify and discuss some problems basic to the issue of language contact or bilingualism. The study features topics such as measurement of bilingualism and bilingual proficiency, language choice/ use; language attitude and language alternation.

NOTES

1. Erúshú can be spelt either as Erúshú or Erúsú, (see Crozier and Blench 1992:16)
2. An official language is the language employed by the government in its day-to-day official activities. Both languages are employed on a daily basis over the state's radio and television. (Bamgbose, (1985); Elugbe, (1985))
3. Brackets mine.
4. The term NAC has been dropped in current literature as far as these Akoko languages are concerned. Reasons being that Capo (1987) is of the view that the term presupposes the presence of a Southern Akoko Cluster (SAC) which has not been proved anyway. Thus, he argued for its rejection. Moreover, Capo (1987) and Williamson (1989) have proved that not all the languages in this region are related enough to be called a cluster. Ukaan to them belongs to a separate division in Benue-Congo because, whereas the dialects of Ukaan are mutually intelligible, Ukaan itself is not mutually intelligible with those languages spoken in Akoko and in neighbouring areas of Edo State.
5. As already observed, for varieties of this language in Akoko land, the prefix Owon (which means 'language') is usually prefixed to the name of each town to name its language. However, the term 'Owon' has been used by some scholars like Agoyi (1997) to refer to these different speech forms spoken in Arigidi, Erúshú, Iye, etc. This study, however, regards Owon as a prefix and not the name of these dialects.
6. The emphasis here is mine.
7. The present classification was proposed in Abiodun (2004:15) since other researchers simply grouped together all the Owon dialects as Akokoid.

8. A national language is usually the one adopted as a common medium of communication (*lingua franca*) by a given society for the expression of its world view and day-to-day activities. It is used purposely to further social and cultural integration at the national level. A national language is used as a symbol of a country's nationality (cf. Fishman, (1968:8); Bamgbose, (1985:94); Elugbe (1985:165)
9. As evident in note 8, a *lingua franca* is a common medium of communication of a given society. (cf. Elugbe, 1985:165)
10. The first language or mother-tongue is the first language a person picks up in his early childhood. It is not learned but acquired. (cf. Oyetade, 2002; Chomsky, 1965)
11. According to Crystal (1987) the inevitable result of languages in contact is *multilingualism*, which is most commonly found in an individual speaker as *bilingualism*.

CHAPTER TWO

2 A REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter is divided into three sections. The first section discusses the different conceptions of the phenomenon called bilingualism. In other words, the manifold definitions and typologies of bilingualism are examined in this section. The second section reviews those problems and issues associated with languages in contact like interference, code-switching, language choice and attitude, language maintenance and shift. An Attempt is made in the third section to examine bi-or multilingualism in Nigeria vis-a-vis multilingualism in other parts of the world. This brings into focus Africa's experience of bi-or multilingualism as compared with the western nation's experience.

2.1 Language Contact and Bilingualism¹

Any time languages come in contact, a number of things actually come in contact like the people who speak these languages as well as their culture. Indeed, the order begins with the people themselves before the languages. Language contact can be described as a phenomenon whereby two or more distinct languages are spoken within a speech community. It has often been described as a situation whereby an individual has access to two or more languages. According to Yusuf (1999) language contact should be seen in the broad sense of contact between two cultures resulting from conquests, wars, migration, colonization, etc. Languages in contact are often languages in competition and there is no language contact without language conflict (Igboanusi & Ohia, 2001:125, Egbokhare 2004:509). However, as evident to this researcher in some other works, there could be language contact without language conflict. That is, languages in competition which however does not imply that the languages are necessarily in conflict. The revolutionary cause of change (language usage) in any speech community is the force encountered between one culture and another which needs not be violent. Indeed, it may well be co-operative. However, whatever brings two speakers of different languages into contact and makes them communicate with each other counts as a force for change.

Languages compete for roles when in contact, whereas language conflict has to do with one language dominating the other in a contact situation. Whenever two languages come in contact within an individual or a community, such an individual or host community inevitably becomes bilingual (Crystal 1987).

Bilingualism has been described as a product of language contact, a consequence of economic, political, and social interdependence existing among different peoples and societies (Oyetade 1995:61). Bilingualism is a world-wide phenomenon with world-wide evidence. Indeed, it is very difficult today to conceive of a human community that is not bilingual in one way or the other. Monolingual countries are the exception rather than the rule, due to failure to assimilate local minorities and large scale labour migrations (Mansour, 1993). Current facts within sociolinguistics have revealed that there is no genuine monolingual country in the world. Thus, any country so described as monolingual merely has a high degree of linguistic homogeneity.

The socio-cultural factors which contribute to the development of bilingualism either in Africa or elsewhere may be analysed as follows (Beardmore, 1986, Appel and Muysken, 1987, Mansour, 1993):

- (1) Tribal wars of conquest which succeeded in joining distant territories together led to bilingualism. In each case the language of the colonial master experienced a period of expansion as the favoured lingua franca throughout their dominions. And even though in many cases the mother tongues of such conquered communities continued to be spoken, the wide spread use of the colonial master's language led to bilingualism in such colonies up till today. Examples abound in African countries such as Nigeria, Cameroon, Ghana, etc.
- (2) Trade or occupational factors which often lead to social, economic and cultural development or stagnation. The belief that no man is an island motivated many communities to engage in long distance trading with one another which, in turn, promotes bilingualism (either at individual or societal level) within these communities. Minority languages are often in conflict

with the major ones in language contact situations because their speakers seem to be aware that their languages do not often function in gaining upward social mobility. Thus, to this set of people bilingualism is a natural way of circumventing a man-made barrier to a life of social and economic well-being. In other words, speakers of the minority languages all over the world (especially the youths) often learn the prestigious language accessible to them which may in turn spell economic and social up-liftment. To this set of people, all the factors influencing social development also shape languages and the roles they may play. Thus, they do opt for a second language which gives them the opportunity to develop economically, socially and culturally.

- (3) The last factor to be examined here is the environment. According to Mansour (1993) certain types of environment favour certain types of socio-historical process, which, in their turn foster either monolingualism or multilingualism. Mansour states further that monolingualism at the level of the nation can only flourish in a contiguous geographic space or in a centralised state which deliberately fosters linguistic unity through the imposition of a standard language and by achieving a high degree of literacy (p. 21). The causal link between the environment and linguistic development has been recognised by a number of scholars. Alexandre (1967) for instance, points out that in Africa the languages with the widest spread are found in the Savannah Zones, whereas the greatest linguistic fragmentation is found in mountainous and forest regions, to which one might add the coastal region of West Africa. Oyetade (1990:28) says that there is a cross-current of contact between the languages spoken in Nigeria and that we can isolate bilingualism in major Nigerian languages like Hausa and Yoruba. Similarly, there are bilingual individuals and societal bilingualism is wide-spread in the country. In other words, wide open spaces of land without any physical barriers like rivers and mountains provide an ideal corridor for human contact, which invariably has implications for language contact or bilingualism. Related to the environmental factor is the issue of whether or not the linguistic borders of community neatly coincide with politico-

geographic borders. Political policies affect, according to Egbokhare (2004) even if indirectly, the balance of language usage pattern, especially where uneven population distribution is the result.

Although, a lot of research work had been carried out on the different aspects of bilingualism (see Ferguson 1966, Kloss 1967, Berry 1971, Lieberman 1972, 1980, Obanya 1973, Johnson 1973, Adeniran 1977, Lamy 1979, Bchheit 1988, Sridhar 1988, Oyetade 1990, 1992, 2004, Ruiz 1995, Fakuade 1995, 1999, Yuka 2002, David et al 2003, Mati 2003, Govindasamy and Nambir 2003, Cheng 2003, Attia and Mutaka 2004, among others), even then our knowledge of this phenomenon is still very scanty.

In the last 25-30 years many sociolinguistic studies all over the world document the fact that members of a speech community may have different varieties in their linguistic repertoire. For instance, Sotton (1972) shows in a study carried out in Kampala, Uganda, how the languages an individual knows are associated with level of education, occupation, age, and ethnic group. Similarly, Parkin (1974), who studied language repertoires in Nairobi, Kenya, reported that ethnic group made the difference in a person's claimed ability in Swahili as well as Kenyan languages.

Again, studies of social dialects conducted in Western societies in particular present how dialectal differences are associated with demographic variables like socio-economic class, age, and sex (e. g. Labov 1966, Trudgill 1974), Trudgill for instance who studied speech in Norwich, England, reported that in the casual speech of middle class subjects the nonstandard variant of the final consonant in words ending in *ing* (/n/ rather than the standard variant /ŋ/) occurred 28 percent of the time. Whereas amidst lower working class subjects the nonstandard variants occurred 100% of the time in their casual speech (1974:94)

Numerous studies of multilingual communities reveal that the different varieties in a community's linguistic repertoire are used for different functions. Once again, Barton, (1980: 187) who studied language use in a part of Dar es Salaam, Tanzania, reported that only discussion with grandparents marked the only situation where other (mother tongues) languages were used more than Swahili, the national and official language of the state. Gal (1979) also details the different interactions for which residents of an Austrian

village near the Hungarian border use Hungarian and German. The extreme case of allocation of functions is classic diglossia, as discussed by Ferguson (1959).

Attitudinal studies have equally shown that people speaking different dialects or languages, are assessed differently along a number of scales. A classic example is Lambert's "matched guise" study in Canada (1967) where it was discovered that if subjects were tested unknown to them, with the same person speaking English and then speaking French, subjects judged the English "version" more favourably in relation to a number of factors like education, competence and intelligence. Similar studies conducted elsewhere confirmed that evaluations are significantly influenced by speech markers. A corroborative study is that of Ryan and Carranza (1975) which proved that speakers of Spanish- accented English are downgraded relative to standard speakers.

As evident from the foregoing, different aspects of the phenomenon have been empirically studied. However, in spite of the fact that the past seems inundated with works on bi/multilingualism, it is unfortunate that we can hardly lay our hands on any cohesive theory with respect to its definition and measurement.. This lack of a cohesive theory has implications for any new work on bilingualism.

Moreover, it makes each new study of this phenomenon an uphill task. It is for these reasons that the study of languages in contact will continue to interest researchers of varied background for as long as the phenomenon lasts. After all, just as Appel and Muysken (1987) have rightly observed, sociolinguistics is not like Chemistry, and when you put two languages together the same thing does not always happen.

Suffice it to say for now that certain works (cf. Mansour 1993, Appel and Muysken 1987) on language contact have gone a long way to de-mystify the phenomenon called bilingualism or multilingualism and to search for its roots. Thus, the interest it has generated among scholars in recent times is indeed a welcome development. The diverse research with examples from many different situations may eventually lead to a clear overview of this lively area of language study.

2. 2 Bilingualism: Concepts and Definitions²

The phenomenon of bilingualism has experienced a sharp rise in its investigation during the last twenty /thirty years (Ferguson 1966, Scotton 1972, Trudgill 1974, Parkin 1974, Ure 1979, Gambhir 1983, Fasold 1984, Beatens Beardsmore 1986, Oyetade 1990, 1992, 2003, 2004, Fakuade 1995, Blench 1998, Nercissians 2001, Yuka 2002, David et al 2003, Govindasmy and Nambiar 2003), but it is unfortunate that despite this surge of interest, the term is still easier to describe or classify than to define.

Over the years, various definitions that have been given for bilingualism have met with criticisms. This derives from the relative nature of the phenomenon and the different biases brought into its studies by scholars. However, the progress so far made in the study of bilingualism stems from the fact of its realization as a relative phenomenon.

In what follows in this section, we present some notable definitions of the phenomenon as discussed in the literature. Bilingualism has been narrowly and broadly defined by different scholars. We shall present the two extremes here starting with the narrow definitions with the highest demands.

Bloomfield (1933:56) has narrowly defined bilingualism as "the native-like control of two languages". Haugen (1953:7) also considers bilingualism as beginning from the point where a person can produce complete meaningful utterances and pass for a native speaker in more than one linguistic environment. In a similar vein Theyry (1978) defined a true bilingual as "someone who is taken to be one of themselves by the members of two linguistic communities at roughly the same social and cultural levels" (cited in Grosjean 1982:146). Still in the spirit of equal mastery of two languages Christopherson (1973:63) while defining bilingualism also stressed the habitual use of two languages to produce meaningful utterances with a range of proficiency by speakers to achieve their communicative need. Still in the spirit a narrow definition of bilingualism, Skutnabb-kangas (1984:91) came up with the following criteria as presented in table 5 below:

Table 5

Criterion	Is the language the mother tongue	A speaker is bilingual who
Origin	First learned (the speaker has established her first lasting linguistic contact in)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Has learnt two languages in the family from native speakers from the beginning. b. Has used two languages in parallel as means of communication from beginning.
Competence (level of proficiency)	Best known	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Complete mastery of two languages. b. Native-like control of two languages. c. Equal mastery of two languages. d. Can produce complete meaningful utterances in the other language. e. Has at least some knowledge and control of the grammatical structure of the other language.
Function	Most used	Uses (or can use) two languages (in most situations) in accordance with her own wishes and the demands of the community.
Attitudes: identity and identification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Identified with by self (internal identification). b. Identified by others as a native speaker of (extended identification). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Identifies herself as a bilingual with two languages and/or two cultures (or part of them). b. Identified by others as a bilingual/ as a native speaker of two languages.

Skutnabb-Kanga's attempt at defining bilingualism made her to combine four criteria (origin, competence level, function and attitude) to define the concept.

Other definitions to be discussed presently can be said to be broad definitions of bilingualism. Weinreich (1953:5), one of the founding fathers of bilingual studies and a bilingual himself, for instance defined bilingualism as the "practice of alternatively using two languages and the persons involved bilingual". Following Weinreich, scholars like Mackey (1968), Muller et al (1981), and Appel and Muysken (1987) defined bilingualism as the alternate use of two or more languages by the same individual. Hamers and Blanc (1989) defined it as "the state of individual or a community characterized by the simultaneous presence of two languages. In the opinion of Halliday et al (1964) "bilingualism is recognized wherever a native speaker of one language makes use of a second language"

Again, Grosjean (1982:1) accepted this loose definition when he referred to it as the regular use of two languages. Macnamara (1969) and Baker on their part said that somebody should be called a bilingual if he has some second language skills in one of the four modalities (speaking, listening, writing, reading), in addition to his first language skills. To Malherbe (1969) bilingualism is "the co-existence in the same individual or community of two distinct sets of linguistic symbols of communication (i. e. two languages)". And Diebold (1961:111) is of the view that bilingualism should be extended to include a "passive knowledge of written language or any contact with possible models in a second language and the ability to use these in the environment of the native language. " Thus, we have a flux of confusing definitions of bilingualism. We now examine their apparent inadequacies in the next section.

2. 2.1 A Critique of the Definitions

It will be necessary at this point to re-examine each of these definitions. Suffices it to say for now that earlier scholars had already noted the inadequacies inherent in these definitions.

The loophole in a psychological definition like Bloomfield's or Theiry's is two fold: (1) Problems of measurement seems insurmountable, (2) finding a general norm or standard for proficiency is impossible.

Other scholars who have pointed out the inadequacies of these ambilingualism type of definition include Obanya (1973), and Adeniran (1977), Beardsmore (1982), Grosjean (1982) and Oyetade (1990) who contend that it is impossible to objectivize "native-like control" because native speakers of a language do not have the same degree of proficiency in their languages. In his own reaction to Bloomfield's definition, Obanya wants to know how best to describe a person who knows a standard as well as the non-standard variety of the language. A situation Ferguson (1972) describes as diglossia.

The reaction of the two specialists in this branch of linguistics quoted above succinctly reveals the inadequacies inherent in any definition of bilingualism couched in absolute terms.

Again, at the other extreme where bilingualism is loosely defined, inadequacies also abound. For instance, Weinreich (1953) and Mackey (1968) in their own definitions rather than emphasize fluency have emphasized usage. To Oyetade (1990:43), the problem with these definitions is that they do not state how well the two or more languages should be known and how much use is made or is to be made of the languages.

Thus, whichever perspective one looks at it, that is, whether we define bilingualism (1) biologically, as the language which the mother speaks, and passes on to the child; (2) attitudinally, as the one the speaker identifies with, or (3) sociolinguistically, as the language a person uses most (Skutnabb-kangas 1984), bilingualism is difficult to define satisfactorily. Added to all these problems already reviewed is the measurement standards which are not even universally the same (cf. Oyetade 2004) nor completely foolproof (cf. Webb 1992, Adegbija 1994, Fakuade 1996) for any objective results to be possible. Hence, the research result as regards a respondent's knowledge of two languages may not necessarily tally with the respondent's personal assessment of himself. Put in another way, the research's result or conclusion may not necessarily capture the real situation as far as bilingualism is concerned. Just as the respondent's self-report may not reflect the real situation.

In the words of Baker (1988), the initial issue is that of dimensions. To be called a bilingual, is it necessary to show literacy as well as oracy in two languages? Mackey (1962) suggests four basic language skills: listening, reading, speaking and writing. These skills can be further subdivided. For example, in speaking two languages, people may differ in terms of extent of vocabulary, correctness of grammar and pronunciation. As defined by Mackey (1962), there are at least twenty dimensions of language skill in each language. People have varying skills in listening, speaking, reading and writing a language. Within those four skills there are sub-skills in vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, meanings and style (Baker, 1988).

Baker went further to say that if we add to the many dimensions of language skills the context or domain of language usage, defining who is or not bilingual becomes even more difficult. While some may have ability in two languages, one language may be restricted to the home. Each language may be used in narrow or broad range of contexts. The context or domain of language usage defines when each language is spoken, to whom, where and why (Fishman, 1965).

The intractable nature of bilingualism as evident in the foregoing made it to be considered as a relative ability by scholars. According to Oyetade (2004:484) "this awareness of bilingualism as a relative phenomenon has been the frame of reference for research". With this consideration granted, one is now in a position to measure it either at the level of the individual or the society.

Meanwhile, bilingualism shall be taken here to mean a fair or reasonable mastery of more than one language to the extent that such an individual is able to relate (i.e. communicate) well with members of two different ethnic groups. Hence, in line with earlier works Mackey (1956), Crystal (1987), Oyetade, (1990, 2004), Nsawir (1999), we shall consider bilingual ability as a continuum with bilinguals existing at different points along this continuum. Thus, at one extreme are monolinguals and at the other the theoretical ideal of a perfect, balanced bilinguals.

Notice that bilingualism has been defined here from the individual's point of view. This is necessarily so since its problem of definition is with the individual and not the bilingual society.

2.2.2 Measurement of Bilingualism

Several methods exist in literature for measuring bilingualism. According to Wardhaugh (1992) sociolinguistics data base is drawn from a wide variety of sources such as: censuses, documents, surveys, and interviews. He states further (p.18) that some data require the investigator to observe naturally occurring linguistic events, e.g. conversations; others require the uses of various elicitation techniques to gain access to the data we require and different varieties of experimental manipulation e.g. the 'matched-guise' experiments.

Indeed, a number of approaches that constitute indirect measures of bilingualism such as word-naming, word-frequency estimation and word association tests have been reviewed extensively in Oyetade (1990). After that, several other approaches in use in literature include: Sentence Repetition Testing (SRT) and Second-language Oral Proficiency Evaluation (SLOPE).

Broadly speaking, sociolinguistic survey of societal bilingualism adopts two perceptives, the sociological perceptive and the ethnographic approach. The first uses questionnaire and interview techniques to ascertain the level of bilingualism of respondents while the second method uses direct observation and inference. Thus, the present review will examine two common ones: questionnaire and interview; as well as the matched-guise experiments, and sentence repetition testing.

Questionnaire

Language use and language attitudes have been studied extensively through the use of questionnaire to elicit information on the language behaviour of subjects. It has been widely used because of a number of its advantages. Questionnaires, are relatively easy to distribute and collect back. Thus one can get a greater number of people surveyed than is practical to observe or interview. Indeed direct sociolinguistic observation according to Pride (1980:294) "very frequently forces the question of how to look into private as well as public verbal behaviour." Again depending on the design of the questionnaire, its results can be more easily analysed and compared across informant than in general discussions.

However, questionnaires have some drawbacks. In the first place, this approach is limited by what is put into it. Hence, for it to be a useful instrument of obtaining the right kind of information one must be very careful to ask the right questions in the questionnaire

The commonly used procedure for the assessment of language attitude is that of the psychologist, Likert Scale (1932). This procedure comprises a number of statements and each of which subjects must indicate whether they:

- A: strongly agree
- B: agree
- C: undecided
- D: disagree
- E: strongly disagree.

This scale gives respondents more choices to make than the "Yes" or "no" options. Another common procedure used for the assessment of the degrees of bilingual proficiency through the questionnaire is the rating scales. The rating scale involves the use of the Language Background Questionnaire (LBQ). In this method, respondents are asked to estimate the extent to which they use their two languages across various domains and locales. They may be required to rate their ability in their two languages. A rating scale may require information on the respondent's language use that of his family members and the general language use in that environment. The aggregate score of the subject in all these questions thereby represents a single rating for the subject.

For instance, **David et al (2003)** in their study of the Punjabi Sikh community in Petaling, Malaysia, asked the respondents to assess their abilities in different skills in their ethnic language (Punjabi), English and Malay on a continuum ranging from "very poor" to "very good"

Some problems associated with the use of questionnaire in the study of bilingualism include the following:

- i. Not all aspects of language can be assessed with the instrument.
- ii. Data gathered here could be unreliable and misleading since respondents are left on their own.
- iii. The questionnaire method is equally problematic in an African setting which is predominantly that of illiterates.

Interview Techniques

Interview methods can be either unstructured or structured. It is unstructured when subjects are simply asked to express themselves as well as their attitudes toward a particular language and its speakers. It is structured when a predetermined set of questions is asked from each subject-this is more or less a verbal questionnaire. The purpose of using pre-set questionnaire method is to gather information across a large number of cases and its potential for guaranteeing the reliability of the comparison between different sets of data collected from different respondents.

Indeed, the structured interview may be understood as an alternative to the use of questionnaire in that the reliability of the responses elucidated from the interviewees is still ensured apart from the scope it provides for the elucidation of responses. This method has the advantage that useful data can still be collected even if respondents have problems with expressing themselves in written form. This flexibility allows the interviewers the opportunity to frame and reframe the questions so that they can be more certain that all the respondents understand them in the same way.

A questionnaire is a complete tool, which is an instrument capable of cueing all the necessary information required all by itself. On the other hand, an interview is a face-to-face oral procedure. Moreover, the result of interview is the sum total of what was originally designed and the ideas accruing from the interactions of the interviewer and interviewee.

In a study of London school children by Bernstein in Robinson (1968) he succeeded in generating stylistic variation by exposing children to different communication tasks as part of a half-hour structured interview session. This

procedure requests the child to bring a painting or a model to the interview room and talk about it. Next, a model room with furniture and family figures to be supplied by the interviewer will be constructed by the child. The child will also answer several questions on these.

However, a major disadvantage of the interview method is the problem of interviewing a large number of people. Also, people may be biased for one reason or the other against the interviewer and this will affect the results. Gumperz illustrates this point by sharing his field work experience in a discussion session with a group of black teenagers in a ghetto neighbourhood. Gumperz and his assistance were the only whites there and I quote "I felt myself repeatedly the target of remarks such as the following: 'you are racists'. A series of these and similar remarks made me feel increasingly under attack". (Gumperz 1982:221). As a result of the problems inherent in indirect measurement of bilingualism, Oyetade (2004) suggests that the two basic skills (comprehension and speaking) that can be determined by one or more measures should be assessed in any study that attempts to measure bilingualism, since these skills take care of both the literate and the illiterate populations equally well.

To measure speaking proficiency, Oyetade suggests the use of the interview method which will allow the subjects to express themselves in a sustained discourse. The researcher will then note subject's performance before rating him/her against some predetermined rating scales like: poor, fair, good, very good and excellent against these sub-skills: the semantic, the grammatical, the phonetic, the lexical and the stylistic. He cites Rubin (1972) as using this method in less detail in her study of Spanish-Guarani bilingualism in Paraguay through a tripartite scale (none, so/so, good) to measure each informant's ability in speaking, understanding and reading.

He suggests listening comprehension tests as opposed to reading comprehension for the other language skill so as to take care of both the literate and illiterate populations equally. A conscious attempt should be made to ensure that passages are equivalent in terms of complexity but not in content. This method will truly give a picture of bilingualism of an individual or of a particular community. He opines that the result they eventually come up with will be reliable

and much more valid than word-naming, word-frequency estimation and census figures that constitute indirect measures of bilingualism. These alternative measures of bilingualism recommended by Oyetatde are in line with the Summer Institute of Linguistics test for measuring societal bilingualism called Second Language Oral Proficiency Evaluation (SLOPE).

SLOPE is an adaptation of oral interview technique originally developed by the Foreign Service Institute (FSI) for diplomatic trainees. According to Radloff (1991:4) the method concentrates on a subject's second-language performance during an interview conducted by a trained interviewer. The subject's performance is evaluated according to the six FSI proficiency level descriptions.

She states further that this oral interview technique has been found to be most helpful in obtaining an in-depth analysis of an individual's strengths and weaknesses in the second language, especially for more educated or sophisticated people who can function under the constraints of an interview of this type. Thus, one of the limitations of this technique is its inapplicability in rural settings in developing countries.

The Matched-Guise Experiments

This is an experimental manipulation, which was first used by a psychologist, Lambert (1960) to measure language attitude. The Matched-guise technique involves the reactions of listeners (or judges) to the taped recordings of a number of perfectly bilingual speakers reading a two-minute passage in both languages. Subjects (or judges) whose language attitudes are being studied listen to these recordings under the impression that the two readings by each of several bilinguals are actually from two different speakers.

The subjects (or judges) evaluate and rate the personality characteristic of the unfamiliar speakers mostly on semantic differential scale. These scales have opposite extremes of certain traits at either end and a number of blank spaces in between the points of the scale e.g intelligent/dull, unfriendly/friendly, etc. Since the subjects have not recognized the two fragments as being by the same speaker, any difference in reactions to the two fragments will reveal underlying attitudes.

Improving on Language use and Attitude Scales

Based on the methods above, Baker (1992:25) emphasizes the need for attitude scales to meet three criteria. These are:-

Internal consistency: consistency of response and of using many items.

Validity: This means that the attitude scale should actually measure attitude and nothing else. This can be attained through a thorough checking of items (content validity), the relation of the scale to present variable (criteria-related validity) and future variables (predictive validity).

Dimensionality: A test of whether one or more entities have been measured. Multidimensionality can be measured if a large initial pool of attitude items is subjected to an explanatory confirmatory factor analysis.

Similarly, Gross (1999:517) also presents some hints on designing attitude tests.

- (a) Since subjects normally give answers, which they think are expected or 'proper' rather than honest answers, the test designer should incorporate a 'lie' scale that can help detect this tendency,
- (b) Subjects should be reassured that their answers will remain anonymous and stressing the importance of giving honest answers.
- (c) Introducing irrelevant items 'red herrings' help to make the true purpose of the scale less obvious and so less susceptible to distorted responses.

Finally, Baker (1992:25) recommends a combination of approaches to be used in attitude measurement because of its dicey nature.

Sentence Repetition Testing (SRT)

Another elicitation method in sociolinguistic survey is SRT. Sentence Repetition Testing is the result of the work of a team of experts involved in the South Asia Sociolinguistic Survey project. SRT developed by Radloff (1991) and her

associates is a screening test for evaluating an individual's proficiency in a second language.

An SRT consists of series of tape-recorded sentences in the second language. The subject being tested listens to each sentence one by one and repeats same immediately after hearing it. The subject must repeat each sentence verbatim to earn maximum credit, however some credit is awarded if a repetition included only one or two mistakes. Assessment here has to do with a person's ability to use a second language automatically without pondering.

Elicited imitation or a sentence repetition task is deemed to have substantial promise as methods of assessing language proficiency in third-world countries of low-to-nil-literacy. Another merit of the SRT over other approaches like oral interview is in its wide applicability in different cultural and social settings.

2.2.1 Typologies of Bilingualism

It is gratifying to note that what definitions could not do, typological classification has taken care of it. From the preceding section it is patently clear that definitions do not make bilingualism easy to conceptualize. Indeed, it is evident in the literature on bilingualism that deciding exactly who is or is not bilingual is problematic (Mackey, 1962; Skutnabb-kanga, 1981, Baker 1985). Scholars have noted that the advantage of typology is that it enables us to work within a clear frame of reference in a large field. It also reduces the danger of overgeneralization.

Usually, the typology of bilingualism is discussed in bipolar terms which are descriptive of features of bilingualism in an individual or in a community. Bilingualism is found in two main forms either in the individual or in a society. Thus, the first and primary distinction to be made as the basis of any discussion in this field is that between societal and individual bilingualism (Fishman, 1966). Of these two, individual bilingualism is the more basic due to the fact that it is the aggregate of individuals that forms a society. On the other hand, societal bilingualism feeds and sustains individual bilingualism. In this regard, Beardsmore (1982:126) says that the very fact that a person is a bilingual is usually determined

by the society in which he lives, originating in such things as migration, exogamy, social mobility, job requirements and so forth, and often the individual bilingual has had little choice in deciding his status.

The foregoing has actually established the primacy of individual bilingualism. In what follows, we shall examine societal bilingualism versus individual bilingualism

2. 2.3.1 Societal Bilingualism Versus Individual Bilingualism

This primary distinction is very crucial to the present study. Societal bilingualism refers to a society using two or more languages for the purposes of communication. Individual bilingualism on the other hand refers to an individual who speaks two or more languages for the purposes of communication.

Again the basic distinction of this phenomenon into societal versus individual bilingualism is evident in the various definitions given earlier on in this chapter. Researchers like Halliday, et al (1964), Mackey (1957) etc, defined bilingualism from the point of view of the individual while Malherbe (1969), Weinreich (1953) etc defined it from the point of view of the society.

Fishman sees societal bilingualism as a sociolinguistic phenomenon, in that, conceivably, there could be a society in which two languages are used but where relatively few individuals are actually bilingual. He calls individual bilingualism a psycholinguistic phenomenon in that it is the existence in the mind of an individual of two (native) languages.

As evident from the foregoing, bilingualism has been sub-categorized in various ways by various scholars and from the well-established dichotomy between societal and individual bilingualism (Fishman, 1966), through the little-known typologies of Pohl (1965) viz horizontal, vertical and diagonal bilingualism to the functional specialization based dichotomy of primary/natural and secondary bilingualism (Houston 1972).

Thus, these differences have placed the onus on the investigator to state the indices with which his own typologies have been established. For the purposes of the present study we shall employ the major distinction (societal vs individual

bilingualism) already reviewed as the basis of our typological framework. This is so since the frame of reference for the present research work on bilingualism examines the four aspects of this phenomenon as discussed by Macnamara (1969).

These four aspects are: its degree, its function, alternation and interference. In this work, our examination of degree and function, the first two aspects, will be community based, while the last two, alternation and interference can only be individualized. It is only after this stage that our findings can be generalized to explain the community's type of bilingualism.

The next section examines the typologies of societal bilingualism, the burden of the present research. The other side of this, individual bilingualism³ shall be discussed briefly in the endnote.

2.3 Societal Bilingualism

Under this heading, we shall examine the following: stable versus unstable bilingualism, elitist versus mass bilingualism, vehicular versus cultural bilingualism, horizontal versus vertical bilingualism, oral versus literate bilingualism, and additive versus subtractive bilingualism, endoglossic versus exoglossic bilingualism and symmetrical versus asymmetrical bi/multilingualism.

2.3.1 Stable versus Unstable Bilingualism

The distinction between stable and unstable bilingualism is used to describe a stage in the development of bilingualism in a community.

In an unstable bilingualism the second language is just making its contact with the first language of the host community. That is, the second language has not been entrenched into this new community due to some factors such as socio-economic factors, cultural and political factors. Bilingualism becomes stable in a community by the time the aforementioned forces act in favour of the second language to the extent that the community now adopts it as their second language.

In a society characterized by unstable bilingualism, functional differentiation of language usage by speakers is lacking whereas in stable bilingualism speakers functionally differentiate their language usage. An important characteristic of

language contact situations is their fluidity. It is rare to find a setting where the languages are stable and balanced and where social controversy over government policy is not a major issue Crystal (1987:360).

Crystal's observation is however true of many African communities characterised by unstable bilingualism. The present research work is a case in point. Our findings will however validate or disprove Crystal's observation. Oberwart (Gal, 1978, 1979 cited in Fasold, 1984: 21 – 22) in Austria provides one of the best examples of stable bilingualism in language contact settings (Hungarian and German).

2.3.2.1 Elitist versus Mass Bilingualism

This distinction is used to describe exoglossic and endoglossic bilingualism. That is, the co-existence of foreign and indigenous languages. We have elitist bilingualism when a few speakers are trained in a foreign language in addition to their mother tongue in order for this set of people to be used in the service of their nation. Lewis (1972) cited in Oyetade (1990) reported that this was the case in Russia in the past where French was the second language of the elite. This was also the case in Nigeria in the past, that is, during the colonial regime when few Nigerians were trained in the colonial master's language so that they may function as civil servants.

Mass bilingualism is used to refer to a larger set of people who are illiterates but are able to speak two indigenous languages. Oyetade (1990) opines that mass bilingualism of this nature is largely unplanned and that it may be rare except in frontiers of two language areas.

This term, mass bilingualism, aptly describes our study location which is engulfed with the use of two indigenous languages irrespective of the speakers level of education. It is also interesting to note that Erúshú falls within a local government that is in a border area of Ondo State. It has boundaries with Edo, Ekiti and Kogi States. Thus, the local government is a frontier one.

2.3.3 Vehicular versus Cultural Bilingualism

A third distinction within societal bilingualism introduced by Lewis (1972) is that between vehicular and cultural bilingualism. This distinction as presented in Oyetade (1990:53-54) is as follows. Vehicular bilingualism refers to a limited knowledge of a second language. It arises in a situation of contact, where one of the languages is used only for very limited purposes or for minimal transactions.

This kind of bilingualism does not make any demands on the bilingual with respect to his cultural affiliations. Cultural bilingualism, in contrast, is comprehensive bilingualism. In this case the second language is acquired as a means of entry into the total culture related to the language. Therefore, the language is well mastered such that the bilingual can pass for a monolingual speaker of the language.

These types of bilingualism can be noted among immigrants. In some cases the vehicular type is typical of the older generations of immigrants, while their offsprings may exhibit cultural bilingualism. Oyetade (1990) remarks that whichever type characterises a society is dependent on a composite of factors: linguistic, socio-cultural and socio-political.

2.3.4 Horizontal versus Vertical Bilingualism

Horizontal and Vertical bilingualism formulated by Pohl (1965) cover the two major distinctions (i. e. societal and individual bilingualism) adopted as our frame of reference for typological distinctions here.

Horizontal bilingualism according to Pohl is used to describe a situation where two distinct languages share the same official, cultural and social status in a community. An example of this is in Canada where only two languages (English and French) are officially recognized. On the other hand, vertical bilingualism occurs when a speaker can use a standard language together with a distinct but related dialect (Pohl 1965 cited in Beardsmore 1982).

2.3.5 Oral versus Literate Bilingualism

The measurement here is done through the mode of acquisition of the two languages involved. Thus, oral bilingualism means the bilingual speaks his two languages but has no literacy skill in one or both of them. The literate bilingual, on the other hand, does not only speak both languages but also reads and writes in them.

Oral bilingualism aptly describes the type of bilingualism found in our area of study since Erúshú is not a written language. Yoruba, however, has its written form learnt within the four walls of the classroom.

2.3.6 Additive versus Subtractive Bilingualism

Additive and subtractive types of bilingualism which also cover the two major distinctions (i.e. societal and individual bilingualism) here were first defined by Lambert (1975). Additive bilingualism occurs when conditions favour the development and maintenance of the maternal language while permitting the learning and use of a second language (Fakuade et al. 2003). Thus, by additive bilingualism (Hamers and Blanc 1989, Hakuta 1992, Kachru 1992) a majority group has learnt the minority language, whereas in subtractive bilingualism a second language has eventually replaced a first language. Yuka (2002) observes that when a child learns a second language in addition to his mother tongue, reference is made to *additive bilingualism*; but when a child learns a second language at the cost of his L₁, subtractive bilingualism bestows upon the preferred L₂ the status of a *Killer Language* (a term attributed to Ann Pakir).

2.3.7 Endoglossic versus Exoglossic Bilingualism

The bipolar division of endoglossic bilingualism and exoglossic bilingualism has been discussed in Kloss (1967) Bamgbose (1978), Hamers and Blanc (1989), Oyetade (1990, 1992, 2004). According to Kloss (1967) we have endoglossic bilingualism as opposed to exoglossic bilingualism. The former refers to bilingualism involving two indigenous languages while the latter refers to bilingualism involving two foreign languages. The position was modified in Oyetade

(1990, 1992) as endoglossic bilingualism and semi-exoglossic bilingualism as far as Nigeria is concerned. To Oyetade (1990) semi exoglossic bilingualism involves English and indigenous languages. Cobarrubias (1983) in Ruiz (1995) who worked on America Indian languages distinguishes three types of societal bilingualism viz: endoglossic, exoglossic, and mixed. He defines endoglossic and exoglossic just as Kloss defines them. Cobarrubias' mixed type is what Oyetade has also identified as semi-exoglossic in that it accommodates both indigenous and foreign languages in a country.

2.3.8 Symmetrical versus Asymmetrical Bi-/multilingualism

In symmetrical bi-/multilingualism, all the languages have equal status. On the other hand, in asymmetrical bi-/multilingualism, at least one of the languages in question has more status than the others. For instance, in Switzerland, with three national languages (French, German, and Italian) each of these is equal despite substantial differences in the number of speakers. According to Clyne (1997: 306), 73.5 percent of Swiss citizens have German as their first language, 20.1 percent have French, 4.5 percent Italian, and 0.9 percent the regional official language, Rheto-Romansh. However, the same equality of status does not apply to national four official or national languages of Singapore. According to Clyne (1997:307) Malay is the national language but its special functions are limited to the national anthem and the national motto. Mandarin, he says, has been propagated in the majority Chinese community, and Tamil as the official language undergoing the greatest language shift, but in most respects the four languages – English, Mandarin, Malay and Tamil – are officially equal. English, which serves as the lingua franca between the ethnic groups as well as the international code, is often employed on its own, whereas the other three – Mandarin, Malay and Tamil represent the three major ethnic groups, the Chinese, Malay and Indians.

Canada and Cameroon, for instance, operate symmetrical bilingualism, in that, both English and French have official and institutional backing in these countries.

2.4 Key Issues in Language Contact Situation

The study of languages in contact has always been approached along two dimensions viz. (1) linguistic (i. e. structure), (2) sociolinguistic (i.e. social functions). This section examines relevant topics within these two dimensions such as the social, psychological and linguistic aspects of contact situation. The social aspects concern issues like language choice, language and ethnicity; the psychological aspect also deals with language attitude; while the focus of linguistic aspects are code-switching, interference, etc as its by-products.

Each aspect is an area of investigation by itself. That is, they represent different orientations and research agendas. Thus, a full-blown discussion of these will not be engaged in here. In what follows, we examine similar works, which can provide a theoretical orientation for our investigation.

2.4.1 Social Aspects of Language Contact

2.4.1.1 Language use or Language Choice

Language use is intricately tied to situations and reflects general features that underline behavioural norms (Johnson, 1978). Oyetade (2001) says "use" as it relates to language is used synonymously with function, significance or role (Ferguson, 1966, Stewart 1968; Nida and Wonderly 1971; Heine 1970, etc). Languages differ in their functions or use. Again, the degree of use or function allocated to different languages varies from scholar to scholar. Works of scholars mentioned above can be reviewed as follows.

Ferguson (1966) recognizes seven functions in a country, viz group function, official, language of wider communication (LWC), educational, religious, international and school subject. Stewart (1968) provided another three, which are provincial, capital and literacy. Thus, we have an addition of ten functions altogether. To Nida and Wonderly (1971) the three functions of language in consonance with the three levels at which communication is required in a nation are in-group, out-group and specialised information.

In his comments, Oyetade (2001:15) observes that the proliferation in these terms gives rise to considerable overlap, e.g. the group function of Ferguson (1966) means much the same as in-group function of Nida and Wunderly (1971).

According to Fasold (1984) the sociolinguistic aspects of language choice have been studied by sociologists, social psychologists and anthropologists. Thus, following Fishman (1964, 1965, 1968e) language choice in this work is considered along certain institutional contexts, called *domains*, in which one language variety is more likely to be appropriate than another. Domains of language use make an attempt at describing the major clusters of transaction that are prevalent in multilingual settings (Fishman 1971). Domains are taken to be constellations of factors such as location, topic, and participants. A typical domain, for example, would be the family domain (Fasold 1984:183).

The sociological approach to language choice which is that of domain analysis have appeared in important works like Greenfield (1972); Parasher (1980); Dirvin (1991); Elthereda (1999); Oyetade; (1990, 1995, 2001, 2002, 2004); Nercissians (2001); Yuka (2002); Fakuade et al. (2003); David et al. (2003); Govindasamy and Nambiar (2003). Thus, the reality of the different domains in the minds of subjects has been tested before now. For instance, Parasher (1980) used the approach among 350 educated people in two cities in India. Parasher like Greenfield used self-reported questionnaire data and attempted to determine people's language use in domains.

Parasher examined language use in seven domains: (1) family, (2) friendship, (3) neighbourhood, (4) transactions, (5) education, (6) government and (7) employment. The subjects who responded to Parasher's questionnaire were asked to state which language out of five languages they would use in each situation. For each language, they were asked to mark a five-point scale to show that they would use that language in that situation always, usually, often, sometimes, or never (Fasold 1984). Elthereda (1999) explores some domains of language use in Bamenda, Cameroon. Elthereda employed self reported questionnaire administered to 250 respondents in multilingual Bamenda. To justify the claim that fewer Cameroonians are employing indigenous languages in their daily interactions

judging from the comparative proficiency in reading, speaking, and understanding English and/or French as against indigenous languages, she presented a five point scale (excellent, very good, good, fair, poor) for English and /or French and indigenous languages in the community.

Dirvin (1991), on his part, distinguished between primary and secondary domains, where primary domain accords with the soft sectors of life involving family, kinship, friendship networks, local markets, cultural life and the like. The secondary domains, on the other hand, correspond with advanced areas of life where issues like education, science and technology, Government administration, judiciary, etc. are given prominence. Domains vary from one scholar to the other and it is doubtful if their number can be exhausted (Schmidt-Rohr 1963 and Mackey 1962 in Oyetade 2001).

The dichotomy between English and Nigerian language becomes very obvious when one examines domains of language use in Nigeria. According to Oyetade (2001) English language is intricately bound to high domains while indigenous languages are tied to the low (or primary) domains of life such that the two types of languages are mutually exclusive in the Nigerian experience.

English is the major foreign language in use in Erúshú just as it is in Nigeria. Moreover, the last paragraph above succinctly captures the Erúshú linguistic situation. Thus, domains of language use is one of our major tasks in this study.

2.4.2 Psychological Aspects of Language Contact

Three areas usually investigated from the psychological dimensions are bilingualism and education, bilingualism and language attitudes, and bilingualism and second language learning. For the purpose of the present study, only bilingualism and language attitude will be discussed here since it is the only aspect having a direct bearing with the aims of the present investigation. Indeed topics such as bilingual education and language planning belong to applied sociolinguistics.

2.4.2.1 Bilingualism and Language Attitude

Language attitudes happen to be one of the three interrelated areas usually explored in works on societal bilingualism. In any multilingual community, language choice and language attitudes toward the respective codes in the repertoire of this speech community is inevitable. Thus, the importance of attitudes in bilingualism as an individual or societal phenomenon is yet to be fully explored. Language attitude is helpful in determining or understanding why a second language is learnt and used. Typical language attitudes include language loyalty, pride and awareness of the norm (Garvin 1954a). To Haugen (1956) language attitude can be positive or negative in respect of the languages involved. Fishman (1974) observed that attitudes toward language vary: it can be about the language itself whereby languages are imbued with human attributes as: beautiful, rich, poor, etc. or the different kinds of behaviours resulting from certain beliefs. Appel and Muysken (1987:16) say "attitudes can be considered as an internal, mental state, which may give rise to certain forms of behaviour".

Trudgil (1983: 44) opines that language attitudes are the 'attitudes which people have towards different languages, dialects, accents and their speakers'. He states further that these attitudes may range from very favourable to very unfavourable, and may be manifested in subjective judgements about the correctness, worth and aesthetic qualities of varieties as well as about the personal qualities of their speakers. Fasold (1984:147) says it can be described as 'an intervening variable between a stimulus affecting a person and that person's response'. According to Fasold two theoretical approaches are distinguished in the study of language attitudes, which are the *behaviourist* point of view and the *mentalist* point of view. In the *behaviourist* view attitudes must be studied by observing the responses to certain languages, i. e. to their use in actual interactions. The *mentalist* view considers attitudes as an internal, mental state, which may give rise to certain forms of behaviour. Baker (1992: 10) is of the view that 'an attitude to something is not like height, weight, or attending church'. In other words, height, weight, and church attendance can be directly and accurately measured. But in contrast, attitudes cannot be directly observed. Thus, the problem with this psychological view point is

that internal, mental states cannot be directly observed, but must be inferred from behaviour or from self-reported data which are often of questionable validity. Indeed, when two languages are in contact, the dominant language is usually considered more prestigious than the low-status language. This is as a result of the function and/or the status of the owners of this prestigious language. (cf. Ferguson, 1959; Hesbacher and Fishman, 1965; Rubin, 1968; Gal, 1979; Oyetade, 1990, 1995 and Yuka 2002).

Dominant languages evoke a positive attitude from their speakers. Ferguson says attitudes such as this are often exaggerated such that the prestige language is considered more 'beautiful', more 'expressive' more logical and better able to express abstract thoughts whereas the other language is seen to be ungrammatical, 'concrete', or 'coarse'. And this is the negative way the dominant group regards the minority languages in bilingual communities.

Attitudes have influence on language use and language learning. Lambert, Just and Segalowitz (1970) noted that for a second-language learner to avoid experiencing anomie⁴ his attitude plays a crucial role. Appel and Muysken (1987:63) report that negative social attitudes towards minority languages are often adopted by the minority groups themselves.

Many parents, according to Appel and Muysken, (1987) are opposed to minority language teaching because of their negative attitudes towards the minority language. Thus, according to them, the parents mainly reinforce the general prejudice against them: the minority language, being the language of a stigmatized group, cannot be the right medium of instruction in school or a valuable school subject. Research has shown that this kind of situation more often than not leads to semilingualism⁵.

The importance of language attitudes cannot be over emphasized. Attitude provides an indicator of community thoughts and beliefs, preferences and desires, and the chances of success in policy implementation. The attitude to English and the indigenous languages in Nigeria might reveal the possibilities and problems of national language within the country. For instance, Lewis (1981:262) observed that any policy for language, especially in the system of education, has to take account of

the attitude of those likely to be affected. In the long run, no policy will succeed which does not do one of those three things: conform to the expressed attitudes of those involved; persuade those who express negative attitudes about the rightness of the policy; or seek to remove the causes of the disagreement. He stated further that in any case knowledge about attitudes is fundamental to the formulation of a policy as well as to success in its implementation.

Two components of language attitudes have been identified by research (Gardner, 1985), (1) an instrumental orientation and (2) an integrative orientation. Instrumental attitude to a language is mostly self-oriented and individualistic and would seem to have conceptual overlap with the need for achievement (McClelland, 1958, 1961). An integrative attitude to language on the other hand, is mostly social and interpersonal in orientation. According to Baker (1976) such an attitude has conceptual links with the need for affiliation. It has also been defined according to Gardner and Lambert (1972:14) as 'a desire to be like representative members of the other language community'.

As evident from the foregoing, language attitude is not limited to only attitudes towards the language of a group but it is also related to attitude towards a social or ethnic group. Finally, language attitudes underpin planning strategies (cf. Oyetade 1990). Thus, one of our tasks in this work is a description of language attitudes in Erúshú community. We hope to ascertain the attitudes of this community towards each of these two languages under investigation. Language attitude plays a crucial role in bilingual settings in that it is one of those factors that determine the languages that are learned, used and preferred by bilinguals. Following his assertion this issue is of particular relevance to a country like Nigeria which is still grappling with the issue of language policy and national language. We hope to come up with ideas that will be useful in language engineering in the country.

2.4.3 Linguistic Aspects of Language Contact

When two languages are in permanent contact a number of linguistic phenomena which are social and psychological (already reviewed) are expected. In

this section we review the linguistic aspects of languages in contact. Indeed, the general impression of many non-linguists is that a person who is permanently in contact with two tongues does not speak either of them correctly. It is unfortunate that some of these bilinguals⁶ themselves hold on to this assumption.

Although, some linguistic problems inevitably crop up when two languages are in contact, we are not of the view that such problems are insurmountable. A bicultural-bilingual will definitely be free from certain interference problems facing many bilingual individuals.

The influence of bilingualism on language skills are evident in the following sociolinguistic processes: code switching, interference, borrowing and linguistic change among other factors. The idea that bilingualism has a detrimental effect on linguistic skills was formulated as the balance hypothesis⁷ (Mcnamara 1966). The linguistic processes discussed in this section are not to be viewed as features of linguistic deficiency but rather as the by-product of bilingualism. These features at least in part distinguish the speech of a bilingual from that of a monoglot. These are linguistic phenomena that demand empirical examination as opposed to naïve interpretations borne out of linguistic purism.

In what follows, we review just three of these features viz: (i) code-switching/code-mixing, (ii) interference, and (iii) language maintenance, shift and death.

2.4.3.1 Code-Switching and Code-mixing

Code-switching or code-mixing owes its development to the coming in contact of two or more languages. Code-switching and code-mixing had been researched by linguists, socio-linguists and psycholinguists as well as educators. It has become a topical and important field of research today, because of its communicative import. Although previous studies on it have emphasized its sociolinguistic aspect see Blom and Gumperz (1972), Scotton and Ury (1977), Scotton (1977), Kachru (1978), Gumperz (1982), Singh (1983), Auer (1984), more recent studies have shown that code-switched languages are rule-governed see Pfaff (1979), Poplack (1980,1981), Sridhar and Sridhar (1980) Bentahila and Davies

(1983), Joshi (1985), Gardner – Chloros (1987), Nishimura (1989), Savic (1995), Essien (1995), Banjo (1996), Myers – Scotton and Jake (2000), Lamidi (2003), among others. As to the major claims of these studies, it is argued that while grammatical processes designate permissible forms of code – switching, social processes regulate selection among the range of permissible forms. However, social factors have their most important contribution in the fact that because they impinge upon choice from a set of structural options, they can become central in language change. Socially motivated choices may suppress other options over time (Myers – Scotton 1993).

It needs be stated that in spite of the new focus (i.e. morpho- syntactically – based code – switching research), the social and discourse motivations for code – switching continue to attract many researchers in the 1990s (cf. Myers – Scotton 1993b, 1995, 2004, Foley 1998, Fakuade 2003, David et al. 2003). Indeed, some papers do explore at once both the social and structural motivations for code-switching (e.g. Myers – Scotton 1993,2002).

In the sociolinguistic literature, 'code-switching is distinguished from code-mixing. Code-switching involves switches of large structures (usually sentences) while code-mixing entails switches of smaller structures within the same sentence or stretch of speech (see Banjo 1983, Wardhaugh 1992). Indeed, the two concepts are essentially the same except that some researchers regard intrasentential code alternation as code-mixing, while an intersentential code alternation is regarded as code-switching. For instance, a discussion can be started in Yoruba and concluded in English. Thus, intersentential (Yoruba – English) language-mixing (i.e. code-switching) will be considered with this example by Fatokun (2000:145) on doctor/patient's linguistic interaction.

Doctor: You didn't come last week

Patient: I came ...

Doctor: You came to clinic last week? They didn't record it that you came. *fun anfaani yin naa l'ase n se clinic yii.* (It is for your benefit that the clinic is being run).

Another example:

Yemisi kọ lẹta sí mí,

she sent her greetings to you.

(Yemisi wrote to me, she sent her greetings to you)

An example of intrasentential language-mixing, that is, within a sentence at major constituent boundaries such as noun phrases or verb phrases, is:

Sẹ lady yẹn ti better.

(Hope that, that lady has now improved)

Mummy àti Daddy

(Mummy and Daddy)

A ti wọ quarter kejì-ọdún

(We are now in the second quarter of the year)

Agbára òlá wá ní mí nkan tí a ò pè ní (There is mighty power in the blood of Jesus)
ẹjẹ Jésù

Ohun tí mo mọ ní wípe the

(What I know is that the power of God is
unshakeable).

Since the distinction is sometimes made in literature, between code-switching and code-mixing, we make the domain of code-switching here as that of a complex sentence or the discourse, whereas that of code-mixing is the simple sentence.

However, there is no syntactic basis of the distinction between the two forms since they are both governed by the same rules for purposes of grammaticality and acceptability. (Lamidi 2001:1)

The study of code-switching and code-mixing in Erúshú community is one of our engagements in this work. With empirical data we hope to provide insight into this phenomenon with respect to Erúshú community.

2.4.3.2 Definitions of Code-switching

Code-switching, the alternate use of two or more languages within conversation has been variously defined in the literature. To Appel and Muysken (1987:120) code-switching is the use of several languages in the same discourse. And to Crystal (1987:362) 'language mixing', 'language switching', or simply

'code-switching' involves changes from one language to another in the course of the conversation.

Auer (1981:1) defines code-switching as the 'alternate use of two or more "codes" within one conversational episode. Lamidi (2001:1) defines code-switching as the product of an agglutination of two or more languages in a particular syntactic structure without respect to the volume of words incorporated from the contributing languages. According to Myers – Scotton (1993: 480) CS is the selection by bilinguals/multilinguals of forms from two or more linguistic varieties in the same conversation. She states further that stretches of CS material may be intersentential (switches from one language to the other between sentences) or intrasentential (within the same sentence, from the single morpheme level to higher levels).

Ahukanna (1990:175) sees code-switching and code-mixing as intra-sentential switching in language, which characterizes the speech behaviour of bilinguals. Since code switching is a common experience among bilinguals the world over, the Erúshú /Yoruba data present yet another opportunity to test for this basic assumption about the speech of a bilingual.

All the various definitions above point to the fact that code-switching/code-mixing is an intra-sentential language switching which characterizes the speech behaviour of bilinguals.

2.4.4 Basic Considerations

In the past code-switching used to be taken as evidence for "internal mental confusion, the inability to separate two languages sufficiently to warrant the designation of true bilingualism" (Lipski 1982:191). Recent socio-and psycholinguistic research has revealed that code-switching far from being a manifestation of mental confusion, is rule-governed and depends on factors such as topic, the code in use, situation and participants.

Ahukanna (1990:175) says code-mixing is governed by a complicated and as yet not fully delimited set of constraints indicating a complex and structured interaction between the two languages in the internal cognitive apparatus of the bilingual (Kolers, 1966, Macnamara, 1969; McCormack, 1977; Albert and Obier,

1978, Garnham, 1985, Lamidi 2003) coupled with various external factors (Hymes, 1962, Weinreich, 1953).

Beardsmore (1982) asserts that for such switches of stretches of utterances to take place the minimal bilingual community must exist, by which is meant that at least two interlocutors must share the same pair of languages. Should only one of the interlocutors be bilingual then a switch becomes almost impossible since this would imply a breakdown in communication. Lipski (1978) while commenting on the rule-governed behaviour of the bilingual as regards code-switching says:

... It is clear that, despite superficial appearances of random and unprincipled behaviour, bilingual code-switching does seem to obey a rather stringent set of sentential constraints. These constraints are of two fundamental types, intralinguistic constraints and interlinguistic constraints. (P. 274)

Lipski states further that the interlinguistic constraints are difficult to isolate since there is no clear picture of the quantity of code shifts that may be accommodated in a stretch of discourse nor how many words or syllables must intervene between switches.

The psychologists (Javier and Marcos 1989 and Wontersen et al. 1995) use the independent and interdependent hypothesis to explain the phenomenon of code-mixing. That is, a bilingual is supposed to have a single mixed or shared linguistic store for his two languages. For the sociolinguists, code-mixing could be explained in terms of the interaction between certain linguistic and non-linguistic variables (Fishman, 1965; Scotton and Ury, 1977). To these could be added the socio-psychological variables of attitude and motivation (Smith, 1980; Ellul, 1978).

2.4.4.1 Functions of Code-Switching

Why people switch between languages in the course of a single conversation has been extensively discussed in the sociolinguistic literature. Such works include: Gumperz, 1976; Gumperz and Hernandez-Chavez, 1975; Scotton (1979), Poplack (1980), Myers – Scotton (1993, 1998, 2004).

Research (cf. Gumperz 1973, Myers – Scotton 2000) has shown that bilinguals alternate between two languages for much the same reason that monolinguals select among styles of a single language. For instance, the social pressures which would make a monolingual change from colloquial to formal or technical styles may lead a bilingual to shift from one language to another. The following points can be adduced as reasons behind code-switching:

- (1) Linguistic incompetence or lack of facility in that language on a certain subject. Since a given subject is better discussed in one language rather than the other, the introduction of such a subject can lead to switch. Third World countries employ the same pattern in discourse about technical subjects in their languages. Below is an Igbo-English bilingual example: Governor Imo state ga-ekuru okwu na radio na television taa. (The Governor of Imo state will broadcast on radio and television today). (Ahukanna 1990: 184)
- (2) To exclude an intruder in the course of a discourse. An example of this is when immigrant parents (say an Ibo couple in a place like Ibadan) use their language with their children in the presence of a stranger from the host community.
- (3) To accommodate (i. e. the opposite of point 2) someone who has just joined in a conversation by using his language. Myers – Scotton (2000) cited many instances, while in western Kenya for field work, in which her interlocutors would shift from Swahili to English immediately they wanted to attend to her.
- (4) Speakers code-switch to express a mixed identity. Appel and Muysken (1990) cited fluent Spanish-English bilingual Puerto Ricans in New York as an example of people whose conversation full of code-switching is a mode of speech by itself. Thus, individual switches no longer have a discourse function.

- (5) Another type called *metaphorical switching* by Gumperz and Hernandez – Chavez (1975) is used to indicate a change in tone of the conversation. Example is given by Sebba and Wotton (1984) on London Jamaican and London English. That is, a stretch of basically Jamaican discourse is interrupted by an English ‘meta-comment’. Metaphorical code-switching is like dialect-shift or style-shift noticeable in monoglot.
- (6) Code-switching may take place as a show of knowledge. That is, speakers may switch between different codes to impress the other participants with a show of linguistic skills (Scotton, 1979, in Appel and Muysken, 1990). Examples are found in the public domain: performers, market salespeople. For example, while writing on switching between English and Ibibio in Nigeria, Essien (1995) points out how code switching can serve a social function in this community in that there is a class of successful and rich business people who usually have little or no Western education – the so – called *nouveaux riches* – but who, through association with the so – called high society people and participation in business ventures have acquired some English. For such people he states further code – mixing is a wonderful opportunity to camouflage

2.4.4.2 Summary and Comments on Code-Switching

We state that theories apart, empirical research has established that code-switching is a characteristic of language use in bilingual communities when all the participants in a speech situation share a bilingual background. In spite of this, it is by no means certain that code-switching has the same functions within each community (Appel and Muysken 1990). Thus, it behoves us in the present study to establish the various reasons behind code-switching in Erúshú – Yoruba bilingualism.

It suffices to say for now that code-switching is a universal linguistic phenomenon. It has been observed in the language behaviour of Filipino- English bilinguals of Philippines (Lande et al 1979), of Malteso – English bilinguals in

Maire (Schweda, 1980), also of Spanish – English bilinguals of the United States of America (Lipski, 1982) and again of the Punjabi Sikh community, Malaysia, who are using a mixed code that consists of three languages (David et al. 2003). Code – switching is evident in the speech of the various speech communities in Nigeria. For instance, Nwadike (1981), Brann (1978), Ahukanna (1990) among others, all observed this phenomenon in the language behaviour of Igbo-English bilinguals while Banjo (1996) and Lamidi (2003) among others work on code-switching in the speech behaviour of Yoruba – English bilinguals. Oyetade (2004) reported a mixed code (Auga/Yoruba) among the Auga people of Ondo State. Fakuade et al. (2003) also reported instances of Fulfulde/ MT code switching among the Girei, Song and Gombi Local Government Areas of Adamawa State, Nigeria. Again, Myers – Scotton (2004) presented a number of CS examples from Kenya and South – Africa. Consider these examples: Swahili-English (1) THEY WILL STAY mapaka shereke zote zitakapomalizika. 'They will stay until all the celebrations are over'. (2) THE CLIMAX WILL BE ON TWELFTH DECEMBER Wakati Mtukufu WILL ADDRESS THE NATION...tume kuwa na michezo mbali mbali PERFORMED By wananchi FROM ALL OVER KENYA.

'The climax will be in December 12th when his excellency (the president) will address the nation...we will have different kinds of shows performed by people from all over Kenya' (Myers – Scotton 1993: 157)

2.4.4.3 The Interference or Transfer Theory

The phenomenon of interference just like code-switching has been a subject of research for years by linguists as well as educationists.

Transfer is a term used by the psychologists in their account of the way present learning is affected by past learning. That is, is there any carry over from the work in task A to task B? If there is, then the word transfer becomes relevant. Once speakers have acquired the habits of their Mother Tongue, there is the tendency for the speech habits of their first language to interfere with the second language in their efforts at learning and using such a second language.

For Weinreich there are two types of transfer. One, when the first language and the second language are similar we expect positive transfer. This is called *facilitation*. Two, however, if the languages are different there is negative transfer this type is *interference* (cf. Smith 1979). According to Smith (1979) 'negative transfer' arises from the difficulties experienced in using the target language as a result of mother tongue interference whereas 'positive transfer' implies the ease or facilitation in learning the L₂ due largely to the similarities between the L₁ and the L₂.

Some past studies of language transfer (Tiffen, (1969), Odlin, (1989), Adeniran, (1990), and Igboanusi, (2000), among others) have established the facts that transfer or interference can occur at both formal and informal contexts and in all linguistic subsystems. And that typological factors as well as non-structural factors can influence the likelihood of transfer.

2.4.4.4 Interference: Concepts & Definitions

Weinreich (1953:1) says 'those instances of deviation from the norms of either language which occur in the speech of bilinguals as a result of their familiarity with more than one language, i.e. as a result of language contact, will be referred to as *interference phenomena*'. That is, it is a situation whereby two different languages overlap. The linguistic systems of the first language has been transferred (wrongly of course) to that of the second language. For instance, a Yoruba – English bilingual speaking English may from time to time transfer a system of the Yoruba language into that of English.

Beardsmore (1982:40) defines interference as the use of formal elements of one code within the context of another, i. e. any phonological, morphological, lexical or syntactic element in a given language that could be explained by the effect of contact with another language. Thus, interference is purely a linguistic enquiry into the structure of two languages in contact. In line with the foregoing, Merio (1978:27) defines interference as the influence exerted by the grammatical systems of the first language on that of the secondary language in violation of the latter's normative grammar.

The concept of interference carries with it a negative connotation, which is that of impaired communication. Indeed, linguistic interference according to Fakuade (1999: 79) usually manifests itself in (a) borrowing – the natural taking of words from one language and using them in another so that they become part and parcel of that other language, and (b) code switching or interlading – where pieces of one language (words, phrases and larger units) are used where a speaker is basically using another language. Indeed, the notion of code-switching cannot be successfully discussed without making recourse to that of interference. It is as if the two notions are intertwined. A major problem associated with the concept of interference is that of delimitation. That is, how do we decide when the use of elements of one language within the context of another ceases to be interference but represent a switch in language or code-switching. The distinction between code-switching and interference will be discussed in the next section.

2.4.4.5 Code-Switching versus Interference

Code-switching is seen by many people as the result of serious interference between two languages in contact within a speaker.

Appraising the difference between code-switching and interference, Beardsmore (1982) has this to say:

Interference used to be considered as any feature in a bilingual's L₂, which differed from features found in unilingual speech, and was attributable to the linguistic structure of L₁. Bilingual code-switching is very similar in that it consists of using elements of a second language in contexts where a monoglot speaker would not do so. Since bilingual code-switching may range minimally from the introduction of a single sound not normally present in monoglot speech to a complete change of language over large chunks of discourse, it is not always evident where the difference lies. (p. 110).

The foregoing attests to the fact that the distinction usually made between interference and code-switching is not as clear-cut as was originally assumed – in earlier works on bilingualism. To the sociolinguist, code-switching is an advanced stage in language use which requires attention beyond the purely formal linguistic elements to include other features of linguistic behaviour which can possibly distinguish a bilingual from a monoglot.

Thus, while interference is purely a linguistic issue, code-switching is a sociolinguistic issue. Again, in line with Chomsky's distinction between competence and performance, while interference has implications relevant to the notion of linguistic competence, code-switching on the other hand has implications relevant to the notion of communicative competence on the part of the speaker cum hearer.

In other words, this linguistic behaviour, code-switching, has psychological dimensions in terms of "who speaks what language to whom and when" (Fishman 1965).

To Beardsmore (1982) the social implications of language choice available to the bilingual may so operate that the same speaker will behave differently depending on the type of interlocutor involved and the make-up of the linguistic community (cf. Essien 1995). Thus, the notion of code-switching cannot be viewed negatively all the time the way we are bound to view interference.

Evident in the above discussion is the fact that a bilingual discussing with another bilingual of the same linguistic background sees and feels nothing called interference even when switching codes. Indeed, to this set of people code-switching is the norm, since comprehension is unimpaired in conversation; rather it enhances it. And what is more, it is useful particularly for registering familiarity, solidarity, etc.

Finally, the only means of clarifying the distinction between code-switching and interference is the observable behaviour of the bilingual. In discourse interference operates at the subconscious level, hence, intrusive in that the speaker is not aware that he is producing features alien to monoglot norms. Code-switching on the other hand operates nearer the surface of consciousness in that it tends to manifest itself only in situations where it is meaningful to the interlocutor (cf. Beardsmore 1982). Thus, code-switching rather than being an error is a linguistic

strategy. Nevertheless, this (CS) does not manifest in our data. The data here belongs naturally to code-mixing.

2.4.4.6 Language Maintenance, Shift and Death

When languages come in contact a number of things which are however impossible to generalise actually happen. Languages, like people, may succumb to onslaught from one another. Thus, the need to examine the issues of language maintenance, shift and death in the present research work.

2.4.4.7 Language Maintenance & Language Shift

In sociolinguistic circles, a distinction is usually made between language maintenance and language shift. When two languages come in contact and somehow, the two manage to survive the contact, we talk of language maintenance, in that, the minor language has survived the influence of the major one.

Fakuade (1996,1997) examined the language contact situation between two (the Bachama and the Mbula) contiguous communities in Numan and Demsa Local Government Areas of Adamawa State of Nigeria and discovered that language maintenance is the major feature of this language situation. Simply because Mbula informants are of the view that their mother tongue is the principal carrier of their culture and identity: they rely upon it as a symbol of ethnic identity and a defining value which acts as a prerequisite for authentic group membership among the Mbula. The Polish, the Baltic and the Greek peoples can be regarded as other examples of such groups in Europe, as can the French in Quebec (McRae 1989:9). With regard to this language centered culture, according to McRae, language is more than the medium of communication and self-expression. Thus their survival in a viable form is deemed by the group members to depend on the preservation of their mother tongue.

However, when a language yields to the consuming influence of another language thereby making its speakers to assimilate to this dominant language, we have a case of language shift.

While writing on the factors responsible for language shifts in communities, Cañule (1998:105) cited in Lamidi (2003:9) has the following to say: *when a*

language is extricated from its natural setting and surrounding or is experiencing a reduction of its domains of use to dominant language, it embarks onto (sic) a process of passivization and change, which ultimately may lead to language shift or loss. Moreover, the shift according to Ilija is from a weak language to the stronger language and is an active process of language displacement.

Brenzinger (1995:282) says that language contact is a prerequisite for language shift. Fakuade (2001) examined instances of language shift in Bauchi, Gombe, Adamawa, and Taraba States of Nigeria. For Ichen language in Donga Local Government Area, Fakuade reported that 36. 2% of Ichen still speak their mother tongue. The remaining 63. 8% of Ichen in Jukun and Donga Local Government Areas now speak Jukun. In a similar study carried out in Bauchi Local Government Area, Samu (1991) showed that all but one Butawa respondent communicate only in Hausa in the home. Thus, the Butawa are most likely to use Hausa in all domains of communication.

The Butawa's experience is similar to the Krenak's in South Eastern Brazil. Only a handful of elders among the 70 or so tribesmen still speak their mother tongue. Originally a tribe of hunter – gatherers, the Krenak were expelled from their land and herded into reserves by government agents intent on making more space for farming. Up until the 1950's, Catholic Missionaries forbade them to perform rituals or speak their own language. The linguistic ban, combined with their tribe's expulsion from its traditional lands devastated the oral transmission of tribal culture (Geary 1997: 40 in Fakuade 2001:17).

2.4.4.8 Language Death

Craig (1995:258) says that language death refers to the complete disappearance of a language. The death of a language, with rare exceptions, cannot be the result of the sudden death of a whole community of speakers. More often, death comes by in a situation of languages in contact and shifting bilingualism. The sociolinguist's interest resides more in studying the causes and circumstances of this death.

Dorian (1981:51; 1986:74) argues that language death may appear to be sudden but may in fact occur as the result of a long period of gestation. It typically involves a case of sudden shift from a minority language to a dominant language after centuries of apparent strong survival. One major cause of language death according to Craig (1995: 259) is the evolution of the patterns of language use in specific families, whereby parents and older siblings speak an ethnic language while younger siblings suddenly do not acquire it.

Research has shown that at times that process of death affects first the lower registers of the language, leaving for last a few pieces of the most formal register. This type of bottom-to-top death has also been referred to as the "Latinate pattern". For instance, Yaqui of Arizona is surviving only in ritual contexts but which crucially marks membership in the ethnic community (Hill, 1983 in Craig, 1995:259).

Speakers of the types of language death patterns mentioned above can be plotted in the continuum of the process of language death, from native fluent speakers to non speakers (Schmidt, 1985; Dorian 1981, 1985, 1989; Campbell and Muntzel, 1989; Dressler, 1991 in Craig, 1995). Schmidt (1985) in his studies distinguished between older fluent and younger fluent speakers. The latter typically were found to speak a somewhat changed form of the language, which is still accepted by the whole community. On the effects of language death on language structure, the first level of linguistic loss correlates with the loss of certain functions of the language. Craig (1995:261) states that the most widespread case is that of the loss of higher functions, such as the use of the language in the public area, including the socio political and religious traditions which necessitate the handling of some formal style of language. For instance, terminal speakers of Breton could only control causal styles (monostylism) for intimate routine interactions (Dressler and Wodack-Leodolter, 1977; Dressler 1991:101 in Craig, 1995). Again, lexical loss, loss in phonology as well as morphology has been reported in the discussion of the different types of language death.

Tandefelt (1992) captures the process of language endangerment in a formula:

$$A > Ab > AB > aB > B$$

In the formula, A represents the minority language (i. e. the language dominated socially, politically or numerically) and B represents the majority language (the dominating language) in a multilingual society. The intervening variables between points A and B are the initial second language learning stage Ab, followed by a period of bilingualism AB, then followed by almost total language shift aB. At point aB the minority language is endangered.

Hale (1993) saw language endangerment as a part of a much larger process of loss of cultural and intellectual diversity in which politically dominant languages and cultures simply overwhelm indigenous local languages and cultures, placing them in a condition which can only be described as embattled. According to him, the process is not unrelated to the simultaneous loss of diversity in the Zoological and Botanical worlds (Fakuade 2001:15).

According to Appel and Muysken (1990:42) when the focus of a language user is another language other than theirs, their language is at risk. It will first experience borrowing. The situation can be further worsened such that large chunks of foreign words are incorporated into the host language, a process called relexification. According to them, if these borrowings are not checked, the society will suffer language disintegration, loss and/ or language death. Appel and Muysken note that children will be eager to learn a productive/ dominant language. Thus, when a dying language is restricted to only one style, language loss and death is inevitable.

The foregoing points to the fact that until the facts about Erùshù –Yoruba bilingualism are laid bare, we cannot predict the course of language events in this community. Thus, by the time this study is completed it is hoped that the process on course in this community, out of those ones discussed above, will become very clear. Meanwhile, we present methods of reversing language shift/loss.

2.4.4.9 Reversing Language Shift or Preventing Language Death

In view of the discussions in the preceding section, linguists all over the world (Hinton, 1997; Adegbija, 1997; Emenanjo and Bleambo 2000; Oyetade, 2003; Fakuade, 2004, among others) have come up with various methods, suggestions and recommendations concerning the preservations and promotion of minority languages.

As evident in this body of literature, native-language preservation can be done and must be through documentation since this is an important part of any programme of language survival. More importantly, however, is the fact that languages survive through actual usage, and through their active transmittal from one generation to another. According to Hinton (1997:177) "a language without speakers is only 'preserved' in the same sense that a dead organism in formaldehyde is preserved." Thus, the efforts and the commitment of the communities themselves in this regard cannot be over emphasized.

A notable programme or method that has been used effectively to save from extinction some of the 50 indigenous languages (Hinton 1994) of California that still have one or more native speakers is the Master-Apprentice Language Learning Programme (MALLP). According to Hinton (1997: 178) MALLP, overseen by the Native California Network and its subsidiary committee, Advocates for Indigenous California Language Survival (AICLS), began its first summer of operation in 1993, with six teams of two people each from six different California languages (Karuk, Hupa, Yurok, Wintu, Yowlumme, and Mojave), each team consisting of a native-speaking elder and a younger tribal member trying to learn the language. Hinton who was also involved in the programme states that each year the programme has grown as much as funding and staffing could allow, with some teams participating for as long as three years. In 1994, for instance, between one and three teams each were funded for nine languages: Chemehuvi, Hupa, Karuk, Mojave, Northern Pomo, Tubatulabal, Washo, Western Mono, and Yowlumme. In 1995, 20 teams and in 1996, 26 teams were funded in respect of this programme of one to one transmission of the native language across generations. He states further that the

continued growth of the programme is assured if funding and staffing can continue to grow

The Master Apprentice Programme is a training programme methodologically designed to teach a common sense, culturally appropriate, oral approach of language learning to teams consisting of a native speaker and an apprentice. The goal is for the apprentice to develop proficiency in his or her language over a period of a few years. From Hinton's (1997) report, MALLP is primarily a summer programme, although the teams are encouraged to continue their work together all the year round if the opportunity exists. The programme also hopes that the association between the team members will be a lifelong one, rather than limited just to the programme. According to this report, teams are selected through application and one of the main criteria for selection is the demonstrated commitment to passing on the language to other generations. Hinton observes that those teams that do the best work often consist of close relatives, because of their geographical proximity and personal commitment to each other.

MALLP as evident from the foregoing is so designed to be common sense and grass-root in nature, so that dedicated people according to the designers can utilize the philosophy and methodology of the programme themselves with a minimum of training and can work on their own. Hinton (1997:180) states that the aim of MALLP is for the teams to create their own mini-immersion situation for language-learning purposes. The techniques are straightforward; teams are instructed to live their daily lives together, doing things as they might normally do them, but communicating always in the language, at least for 10 to 20 hours per week. Game and other language-learning activities may also be used, and traditional activities such as participating in ceremonies are very strongly encouraged.

Hinton (1997:181) states further that teams get a single two-day training workshop to teach them the philosophy and methodology of the programme. For instance, masters are taught techniques of teaching language through context, gesture, and action. The apprentices are taught how to be active learners. The training workshop according to Hinton, gives the teams frequent short practice sessions in monolingual language work and then conducts discussions about the

problems, features and success of each session. It also features the videotapes of previous years' teams at work.

A major advantage of this programme over some other methods being used in many parts of the world to fight language death is that it fits in well with (California Indians') traditional learning style of one-on-one voluntary learning. This contrasts sharply with the typical foreign-language classroom of schools and universities which "runs on the basis of competition and individual assertiveness and of forced learning under threat of punishment (such as poor grades)" Hinton (1997: 179).

Indeed, MALLP's methodology is very suitable for use in an African setting because of its emphasis on oral skills and the traditional one-on-one voluntary learning situation typical of indigenous culture. This method is therefore highly recommended for use in Africa in order to cause a change in the destinies of many indigenous African languages which require only few decades from now to become languages of memory rather than languages of use. Suffice it to say for now that the fate of Erúshú in terms of use is not as bad as these indigenous California languages that were however effectively revived with this programme.

Another distinct method used successfully to revive from death a number of endangered languages in the world happens to be the schools. According to Hinton (1997:179) the Maori, Irish, Welsh, Hawaiian, Navajos, and Mohawks, among others have fought language death effectively through the school. They have been able to establish immersion preschools and elementary schools where the language of instruction is the heritage language. Hinton states further that through these efforts a whole generation of bilingual children whose home language was English are nevertheless growing up with a strong command of their language of heritage.

The major disadvantage of the school system is that the creation and teaching of an entire curriculum in a minority language requires a great many people and resources. Indeed, Nigeria's multilingual situation coupled with the advanced state of language loss in many communities implies that creating Nigerian-language monolingual schools and preschools as in California is beyond the present capacity of most communities – including Erúshú. Getting many Nigerians schooled in their language of heritage may not be feasible now and for many years to come

considering the development level of such languages. This does not however imply that such a project is not desirable for these languages. Indeed, a precedent in this regard already exists in Rivers state.

An ambitious language programme in Nigeria comparable to those described above is the Rivers Readers Project (RRP) that focuses specially on the development of small-population languages. Rivers State has about 33 languages (Adegbija, 1997) and no one of them is understood in all parts of the state. To teach a single language in the primary schools in this state is impossible. According to Williamson (1990:155) "it was in response to the existence in Rivers State of this multilingual situation coupled with a strong local interest in publishing books for primary school use that the Rivers Readers Project was set up shortly after the creation of the Rivers State." Williamson states further that the aim of the Rivers Readers Project is to publish books for primary school use written in all the languages and major dialects of the state, together with supporting materials for teachers. This aim according to her report has resulted in the appearance to date of more than fifty publications in twenty languages/dialects of the state. The efforts of the Rivers Readers project according to Adegbija (1997:11) resulted into: sixteen languages having one reader each; two, Abua and Obolo, have two readers; while one, namely Egbema, has three readers. The remaining 14 languages have no readers in them.

The impression one gets from the foregoing is that Rivers State languages, albeit small-population languages, enjoy a higher language-developmental status than in most other states in Nigeria. The Rivers State Government supports the RRP financially. And by this giant stride of the Government, the language situation in Rivers State today, even though a large number of the languages are still largely undeveloped, is far better than what obtains in Nigerian states of multiple tongues like Plateau, Cross River, and even Ondo State where Erúshú and other Akoko languages are located.

The RRP has succeeded in erasing the impression that it is useless to use any small language in education. It has also destroyed the myth that once an area is multilingual without a single dominant language it is useless developing these small

languages for education purposes because it will be far too expensive to publish books in them.

The remainder of this section highlights some concrete proposals for promoting and ensuring the survival of small languages (see Adebija 1997:17 – 24 for detail).

1. **Positive policies**

Adebija argues that prior to solving all other problems that bedevil the development of small group languages there is the need for a strong, unshakable policy and commitment of the will to the philosophy that all languages, no matter the number of their speakers, qualify for, and should be given, a chance to survive, develop, and grow to their maximum potential without being stifled by government policy actions. In other words, government should absolve itself from all blames by providing constitutionally for the equality of all languages, in principle as well as in practice. It should recognize all these languages as national resources without giving the impression that some are inferior to others, etc. According to him, in Papua New Guinea, with its population of 3.5 million and about 869 languages a policy already exists.

2. **Co-ordination at the National Level**

Again, Adebija argues that there is the need for the establishment of a small, even if informal, language development co-ordinating body for each language in a multilingual context. According to him, Obolo in Rivers State has an active language committee. Some other examples include the Ibiobio language Panel of the Akwa Esop Imaisong (Ibibio Cultural Association); the Ogbako Ikwerre Convention and its Language Committee; the Itsekiri Communal Land Trust and its Language Committee; the Nupe Language Committee and the Kanuri Language Board (cf. Emenanjo 1990:90). The existence of such bodies according to Adebija is the very *raison d'être* that has kept some of these languages alive. He advises that

smaller languages than the ones mentioned here, Erùshù definitely belongs to this category, need and should be encouraged by the government, to emulate them by setting up their own bodies. And that it is very useful if a national governmental body also exists in a multilingual context to co-ordinate and provide support for language-development efforts within the country.

Bleambo's (1990) position in this regard is that government should properly fund and promote Nigerian languages departments in our institutions of learning as well as evolve a National Language Policy. Moreover, bodies such as the National Institute for Nigerian Languages should be properly funded to enable them perform their functions well. Bleambo argues further that the media (largely owned by the government anyway) should play an active role in propagating our various languages by way of news, programmes and jingles.

3. **The Commitment and Effort of the Communities themselves**

According to Williamson, the fact that the Rivers Readers Project is community-based is one of its principal strengths. Thus, "the deep emotional, intellectual, and mental involvement of the small population community whose language is being developed is imperative for achieving the success of the development of small languages" (Adegbija 1997:20). Adegbija opines that a deep involvement of the community concerned ensures total commitment of emotion and resources of the community to the development programme, as is the case in the Rivers Readers Project (RRP). In a similar vein, Bleambo (1990:152) argues that it is the fundamental responsibility of parents and the country to encourage the teaching, learning and use of Nigerian indigenous languages to our children. After all, use is the bedrock of language growth. Thus, efforts should be made to use a language being developed not only in the primary domain (such as the home) but also in the secondary domain like the

media, public radio and television, public notices in the community, etc.

We conclude this section in line with Fishman's (1991) views that without the kinds of concrete implementation efforts proposed above, reversing language shift or preventing language death in most multilingual communities will be almost impossible. What is more? Many speakers of small languages are bound to continue drifting to major languages once it is perceived that they have no need of their heritage languages or any motivation to learn them.

Now we turn to the last aspect of this chapter which is a comparative discourse on multilingualism.

2.5 Bi-or Multilingualism; Local versus Global Considerations

The general impression one gets from a superficial study of the phenomenon at hand, bilingualism, is that bi-or multilingualism is a feature of the Third World countries while monolingualism is of the Advanced nations. Again, while monolingualism used to be seen as the norm for a nation, multilingualism used to be seen as an aberration. Current research has however thrown more light on the phenomenon called multilingualism.

Recent and current research has also proved that monolingualism as far as language use is concerned is varied in form just as multilingualism is. Consider what Mansour (1993:1) says in this regard:

Strictly speaking, monolingualism should refer to only those situations where one language is the only means of communication at all levels of social interaction.

He states further that in analyzing modern sociolinguistic situations, we would either have to admit that monolingual countries are the exception rather than the rule due to the failure to assimilate local minorities and large-scale labour migrations- or accept a looser definition. Because of this latter fact, countries such as Britain, France, Spain and Germany pass off as monolingual, despite the existence of minority languages and considerable dialect variations within them.

To Crystal (1987:360) "the widespread impression that multi-lingualism is uncommon is promoted by government policies: less than a quarter of the world's nations give official recognition to two languages... and only six recognize three or more". He adds further that when we look at what takes place within each country, studying the speakers rather than the national policies, a very different picture emerges. It has been argued that there is no such thing as a totally monolingual country. Even in countries that have a single official language used by the majority of the population (e.g. Britain, U. S. A, France, Germany, and Japan), there exist sizeable groups that use other languages.

The picture that emerges from the foregoing is that monolingualism is easily equated with civilization, and multilingualism, in the words of Mansour (1993), is God's punishment for the wicked. To the sociolinguist, value judgements are beyond his scope. Moreover, monolingualism and multilingualism are alternative patterns of communication which may exist either at the individual's level or at the communal (national) level.

That language contact and multilingualism is not necessarily a feature of African countries alone is contained in the following words of Brenzinger (1995).

In all parts of the world, we observe an increasing tendency among members of ethnolinguistic minorities to bring up their child in a language other than their own mother tongue, thereby abandoning their former ethnic languages. These changes in language use by individuals might ultimately lead to the irreversible disappearance of the minority's original language. The new one, that is, replacing language, is in many cases one of a few fast-spreading languages such as English, Mandarin (Chinese), Russian, Hindi-Urdu, Spanish, Portuguese, Arabic, French, Swahili and Hausa.

From the list of the replacing languages above, we can clearly see that the phenomena of language shift and death is a world wide one, something not limited to Africa alone.

Moreover, the various research works conducted on the different aspects of multilingualism as evident in this review alone is enough to prove its world wide scope. These various works reviewed here further confirm the fact that multilingualism is a universal phenomenon which should really be studied and discussed as such.

2.6 Summary

The foregoing attests to the fact that the study of multilingualism has been a major concern of sociolinguistics all over the world. As evident in this review, some of these past studies have focused on the nature of bilingualism, language choice; language attitudes, language maintenance and shift, code-mixing and code-switching, etc.

With specific reference to Southwestern Nigeria, a number of in-depth studies have been carried out on the existing linguistic heterogeneity of some of the Yoruba communities. However, these sociolinguistic studies have focused on language use with respect to semi-endoglossic bilingualism (i.e English and a Nigerian language) in each community of study. (Obanya 1973, Daramola 1975, Adeniran 1977, Ayodele 1980, Kassal 2000). Indeed, with the exception of a few journal articles (Akere 1982, Salami 1982, Ikotun and Soyoye 2002, Oyetade 2005), endoglossic bilingualism has not received much attention in this part of the country. Besides, these studies were pitched in urban communities such as Ikorodu, Ile-Ife and Idoani.

Some of the linguistic and sociolinguistic aspects that have not received much attention in a sub-urban community such as Erushu include: language use and language alternation, language maintenance and shift. It becomes necessary, therefore, to examine these aspects in concrete terms (i.e. in terms of who speaks what language, to whom and for what purposes) in the study location. This will be useful for language planning and policy formation in the country.

NOTES

1. Bilingualism is a special case of multilingualism. Crystal (1987) says the inevitable result of languages in contact is *multilingualism*, which is most commonly found in an individual speaker as *bilingualism*. Hence, unless otherwise specified, bilingualism is subsumed throughout in this work as a special case of multilingualism, and thus not distinguished from it (cf Goodman 1971).
2. The definitions of bilingualism discussed here are not in any way exhaustive. We have only presented a few along two dimensions.
3. For the interest of our readers, individual bilingualism has at least the following polarity of typologies: simultaneous versus successive bilingualism, primary/natural versus secondary bilingualism, (see Houston, 1972) coordinate versus compound bilingualism, (see Weinreich (1953), Ervin and Osgood (1954), Hamers and Blanc (1989), Hakuta (1992), McArthur (1992) ascendant versus recessive bilingualism (see Beardsmore (1982), additive versus subtractive bilingualism (see Lambert (1977), Hamers and Blanc (1989), Hakuta (1992), receptive versus productive bilingualism (see Beardsmore (1982).
4. Anomie is a feeling of personal disorientation anxiety and social isolation experienced by the adolescent bilingual of the immigrant population. Their bewilderment and frustration is brought about by the conflict of loyalties and aspirations generated between the home language and culture, and the language and culture outside the home (i.e. that of the host community).
5. Semilingualism is a situation whereby competence in both the minority language and the majority language will not fully develop (see child, (1943), Beardsmore (1982)).
6. A case in point is that of my former office mate who happens to have two-second languages (French and English) in addition to his first language,

Yoruba. He had his secondary education in a Franco-phone country. Thus, he speaks French better than English. In fact, he teaches French at the University level presently. However, he feels so uncomfortable with his English that he asks me questions (which are not real anyway) from time to time about his performance in English.

7. To this hypothesis more proficiency in one language implies fewer skills in other ones since we all have limited potential for language learning. In other words, bilingualism has negative effects. However, ambilinguals, albeit they are few, can be regarded as exceptions to this.
8. This addition is mine.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter discusses the method of data collection, the instruments employed as well as the subjects for the study.

3.1 The Research Design

The main objectives of this sociolinguistic study include:

1. A description of the spoken abilities of our respondents in the two major languages (Erushu and Yoruba) in use in Erushu community.
2. An analysis of the functional distribution of Erushu and Yoruba across specific domains.
3. A description of the attitude of the respondents to Erushu and Yoruba, on the one hand and their speakers on the other hand.

In line with the research tradition in this field (cf. Oyetade, 1990, 2004; Akeredolu-Ale 2000; Fakuade et al 2003) we have adopted here the method of elicitation of information through a Language Background Questionnaire. In ascertaining the degree of bilingualism of our respondents in Erushu and Yoruba, we have relied on the self-report of our respondents as well as the researcher's knowledge of the two languages under investigation. A subject's self-report on his proficiency in a language may not actually correspond with his actual proficiency in that language. Thus, we consider transition count which is an aspect of method participant observation indispensable to this study. These methods-the questionnaire/ interview guide and non-participant observations-were all utilized in varying degrees by past researchers in this field. The list include O' Barr, 1971; White, 1971; Lieberson and Mc cabe, 1978; Sridhar, 1988; Oyetade,

1990, 2004; Nsawir, 1999; Kassal 2000; Akeredolu-Ale, 2000; David et al., 2003; Govindasamy and Nambiar, 2003 Fakuade et al, 2003 among others. To improve on these methods as used by past researchers, we actually employed educated native speakers who are competent in the two languages as research assistants. These assistants are properly oriented as to the language skills to be measured.

Oyetade (1990) investigated the pattern of bilingualism among two contiguous ethno-linguistic groups in Saare/ Tsaragi community in order to ascertain the extent of the influence of concomitant demographic, socio-cultural variables on their bilingualism. A multi dimensional interview schedule was used to collect data on language ability and use as well as language attitudes of these respondents to these languages and their speakers.

The research revealed that there were just minor variations between Nupe and Yoruba speakers as far as the use of the mother tongue is concerned. Each group was discovered as having more proficiency in its mother tongue than in the second language. And that the Nupe appeared to be more proficient in Yoruba than were the Yoruba in Nupe. Two, no age group could be said to be superior to the others with regard to bilingual ability. Three, that there is a significant difference between the proficiency of males in the Nupe group and that of their female counterparts whereas the reverse is the case among the Yoruba. Four, couples who shared both Nupe and Yoruba were more proficient in Yoruba than those who did not and so on

Akeredolu-Ale (2000) in his study explored the direct relationship between second language acquisition, social background and academic performance and their effects on the life-chances and social achievements of Nigerian children. Data were collected from 123 subjects through a Language Background Questionnaire (LBQ) proficiency tests and the previous academic reports of the subjects. Two hypotheses were postulated and tested. Her findings revealed that class (or social- stratification) is at the base of variations in language proficiency.

David, et al (2003) studied the process of language shift among the Punjabi Sikh community in Malaysia using an 85-item questionnaire directed at 312 respondents, attempts were made by them to determine language choice and the dominant language of the community in the home and religious domains and with

different interlocutors. The findings revealed that the community was shifting to English and/or using a mixed code that consists of three languages (Punjabi, Malay and English)

In conclusion, having examined the different methods of assessing or measuring bilingualism, we have adopted the language background questionnaire/interview scheduled here based on Macnamara's (1969) suggestion that scholars should decide on the skills they want to determine, depending upon the objective of their investigation and the exigencies of the situation.

Thus, in line with the foregoing, we have therefore isolated those skills (listening and speaking) which can be easily determined by a combined measure of bilingual skills adequate for both literate and illiterate subjects. As stated already, the kind of measures of bilingualism described in Oyetade (2004) is much more valid in Africa than word-naming, word frequency estimation, word association test and census figures which constitute indirect measures of bilingualism. These alternative measures of bilingualism enunciated in Oyetade (2004: 490-493) will form the yardstick of measuring our respondents' bilingual proficiency.

3.2 The Instruments

The study adopted a descriptive survey research method. The Language Background Questionnaire was used to gather data from respondents, supplemented by non-participant observation method (i.e. transaction court). The questionnaire designed to elicit information from respondents had four sections. The first section was designed to reveal demographic facts such as sex, age, educational level, source of knowledge and occupation of the subjects. The other three sections focused respectively on the language ability, language use and language attitude. The research instruments featured closed items while a few of them were however open ended to allow participants to offer free, unassumed, unanticipated but pertinent points.

On our respondents' degrees of proficiency in both languages – Eriṣhó and Yoruba – respondents were required to assess their proficiency in both languages in two basic skills: speaking and comprehension. Only native speakers of Eriṣhó were

considered as samples. Thus, those who were born and bred in Erúshù or elsewhere in the neighbouring villages that speak Erúshù dialect were regarded as fluent speakers of Erúshù.

On language use, participants were tested on various contexts of situation. For instance, they were requested to indicate the languages with which they communicate generally. Again, they were also asked to indicate their choice of codes with respect to different interlocutors (say between husbands and wives, parents and children, etc) in different domains (home, school, church, work, neighbourhood and the market).

The remaining part of the questionnaire, which was on language attitude, sought to know the respondents' feelings or attitude towards their mother tongue, Erúshù and the Yoruba language both at home and in public situations.

A tape recorder was employed to record our data on code-switching/code-mixing and interference which happen to be the other part of the present investigation. The tape recorder was used to collect spontaneous utterances of a number of Erúshù – Yorùbá bilinguals. These recordings were done without the knowledge of the speakers so as to obtain natural results.

3.3 The Sample

According to the 1991 national population census Erúshù speakers number up to 23,665 and they spread over three communities namely: Arigidi, Erúshù and Iye. Today and by projection¹ the number of speakers is about 35,000. It is estimated that Erúshù is just about 8,000 out of this 35,000. This community is one dominated by natives who are indeed bilinguals. Even then, the stratified random sampling technique was adopted for this study. This has the merit of incorporating every sector of the populace. Our survey for potential participants covered the market place, churches and mosque, schools, recreation centres and busy streets in the town. Apart from testing respondents for proficiency in both languages to be qualified for the exercise, certain demographic factors such as ethnic background, age, gender, social status, etc were also given consideration.

In addition to the number of respondents that were got from the above locations, other samples of bilinguals were got from their shops, homes and offices. The sample is a little large due to the nature of the measurement procedures. Thus, the subject for the study comprised three hundred (300) respondents. The important thing, which was taken care of, is to ascertain that the sample is representative of different age groups, educational backgrounds, occupation and so on.

3.4 The Sampling Procedure

For the purpose of the investigation, the four quarters making up the town (Agà, Okesan, Okega and Amo) were visited for a full coverage of the study area. These respondents were randomly selected from each quarter. All the three hundred copies of the questionnaire given to the participants were returned. The questionnaire was the multiple-choice type, thus to fill and return immediately was not too difficult. Those who could not write were assisted by the researcher to complete their copies. Besides, the researcher's intimate knowledge of this village since 1966 was also a contributing factor to the hundred percent return of the copies of the questionnaire.

Although, the respondents were selected based on their accessibility and co-operation, to ensure representativeness, the researcher went round schools, churches, homes, markets and playing grounds to meet with participants. Again, this afforded us the opportunity to observe first hand the language behaviour of these respondents in a natural setting.

The instrument for the study contained a section where respondents were asked to assess their speaking and understanding abilities in Erùshù and Yorùbá along a five point rating scale: Poor, Fair, Good, Very good, and Excellently. While respondents were completing the other parts of the questionnaire, the researcher was also available to clarify respondents confusion and doubt.

Finally, our respondents' output was assessed against the hypotheses postulated for them as presented in chapter one. Thus, the data analysed here is the self-report of our respondents with respect to their language ability, language use, language attitude and language alternation with respect to Erùshù and Yorùbá.

Suffice it to say that the researcher speaks Yorubá as his mother tongue and also possesses a working knowledge of the Eriśhír language. Our findings on this shall be the preoccupation of the next chapter.

3.5 Statistical Analysis

The data generated from the questionnaire was processed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS-Win). Descriptive and inferential statistics were used in the analysis. For the descriptive statistics, simple frequency distributions and percentages were applied and for the inferential statistics we employed, the T-test, the Chi-square (X^2) and the Analysis of Variance depending on the type of hypothesis to be tested.

NOTE

1. This projection was done in 1996 by the Ministry of Information, Youth, Sports and Culture, Ondo State, Nigeria, published in *Prospects and Potentials — A Compendium of facts and Figures on Ondo State (1999)*.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the results of all the analyses carried out in this work. It attempts to answer the research questions and the hypotheses already postulated in chapter three. The analysis is done in accordance with the sections in our questionnaire namely, demographic information, language ability, language use and language attitude. Meanwhile, we present the demographic profile of our respondents.

4.1 Demographic Information

The sample is made up of 300 respondents. The males amount to 55.3%(166), while the females constitute 44.7% (134). That the male respondents outnumbered the female ones can be attributed to two factors: (1) There are more males in our schools than females (especially in the rural areas of the country where many still do not believe in educating the women) (2) There are more males than females outside the house playing ludos, etc, in a rural community like Erúshù. Put in a better form, males are more accessible to strangers/researchers in a village setting like ours than females. However, that we have more male bilinguals in our sample than females does not suggest anything about the bilingual status of the males vis-à-vis their female counterparts until we examine the data. The data should reveal if there is any correlation between gender and bilingual proficiency.

The ages of the respondents range between 10 and 80 years. The pattern of age distribution of our sample is presented below as table 6.

Table 6: Distribution of Respondents by Age Groups.

Age	Frequency	Percentage
10-20	107	35.7
21-30	32	10.7
31-40	47	15.7
41-50	42	14.0
51+	72	24.0
Total	300	100

The adolescents (10-20) constitute the highest percentage in the sample. Next to this group are the adults with 24.0 percent whose ages range between 51-80 years. However, a clean break into two generations, that is, youths versus adults, will give us two age groups of 10-30 and 31-80 which results into 46.3 percent and 53.7 percent respectively for each group.

As stated already, all respondents are bilingual in the two languages under investigation. Thus, we cannot infer anything about the bilingual status of these respondents at this stage. The data analysis will show if there is any correlation between this pattern of age distribution and the respondents actual degree of proficiency in Erúshú and Yoruba.

Table 7: The Educational Profile of our Respondents.

Education	Frequency	Percentage
Nil	73	24.3
Primary	41	13.7
Secondary	170	56.7
Post secondary	16	5.3
Total	300	100.0

The respondents were categorized into four groups on the basis of their level of education. The first group are those without any formal education. The majority of our respondents are secondary school pupils, the reason being that there are three primary schools in this community, while there is just one secondary school and no higher institution. Indeed, the community is opened up to only the primary and secondary education. It is therefore not surprising to find that the number of people with secondary school education is the highest with 56.7 percent, while the people

with primary education have up to 13.7 percent. Besides all this, the few educated indigenes normally leave the town once they attain this level for various reasons such as job opportunities, separation from the extended family, access to science and technology, etc. Suffice it to say that the sample is representative enough to determine if there is any correlation between levels of education and levels of bilingual proficiency of our respondents.

The educational pattern suggests that the community is still very remote. Indeed, it took the assistance of well-informed youths who are indigenes to take me round the village before the old people could co-operate. Actually, these old ones were still very bitter about the increase in the prices of petroleum products about the time of this research work so much so that whenever I turned to them they responded by saying that they would no longer vote in any election. After all, according to them they had benefited nothing from the last one. In other words, the very old people in this community are predominantly illiterates. This has really influenced their level of cooperation. The pattern of distribution in our table by percent is just a true reflection of the educational attainment of the people living in this community.

Occupation is another very important demographic variable in this study. The occupational distribution of the respondents is as presented in table 8.

Table 8: The Occupational Distribution of the Respondents

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Students	185	61.7
Farmers	18	6.0
Traders	32	10.7
Artisans	37	12.3
Civil servants	19	6.3
Others	9	3.0
Total	300	100.0

The largest group, as evident in the table above happens to be students with 61.7 percent. This frequency distribution among various occupations reveals a high concentration of students. Although the research sample was never tilted towards the

students, the situation has turned out to be this. Indeed, the age distribution, as in Table 6, is a clear index to this fact. Moreover, about 18.9 percent of our sample who are young adults and who are engaged in one educational programme or the other such as the National Teachers Institute (NTI) programme and the various sandwich programmes feel it more dignifying to be identified simply as students.

Besides the foregoing, many of the respondents did not believe that a private investigator could ever be interested in their language. To them, I must have been working for the government (this assumption actually became evident to me when I went back to the field after the elections), hence, the need to colour their answers by putting down the best they could claim to be. Moreover, there was no way the number of civil servants could have swollen up here considering the rural environment within which we are operating.

Thus the distribution of the various occupational groups in our sample should not be seen as favourable only to the students. However, while admitting this sampling irregularity, we hasten to add that the data is still representative of every occupational group evident in this community of study. Indeed, students constitute majority of our sample population due to accessibility and their understanding.

On the place of acquisition of Erúshú/Yorúbá, four possible options in respect of this were given in the questionnaire viz: home, school, neighbourhood and elsewhere. The response we got to this question is shown in Table 9 below.

Table 9: Place of Acquisition of Erúshú /Yoruba

Place of Acquisition	Frequency	Percentage
Home	289	96.3
School	5	1.7
Neighbourhood	2	.7
Elsewhere	4	1.3
Total	300	100.0

The home domain with an overwhelming 96.3 percent best facilities the learning of these two codes in Erúshú community. Indeed, it is as if all other domains are of no relevance as far as the two codes are concerned. The place of acquisition would help in determining the attitudes and preferences of the people towards the

languages under study. And this in turn has implications for the process of language shift and language maintenance.

The true position of things will emerge by the time we examine the domains of language use in our data. As patently obvious from the table above, the value of the school as a potent place for the acquisition of Yoruba is almost zero. Table 9 above confirms the viewpoint that our respondents did not learn Yoruba formally at school. Rather, they learnt it informally at home, in their youth, as a result of their exposure to the language without any formal teaching.

In actual fact, this community has been able to trace their origin to Ile-Ife. Hence, they claim to be Yorùbá by tribe. Indeed, this issue shall become clearer by the time we discuss language attitudes of these people towards Erúshú language vis-à-vis Yoruba language and people.

A further implication of the present point (place of acquisition) is that our respondents either young or old should be well grounded in their knowledge of the two languages if they had all acquired the two languages at home as evident in this self-report. This can easily be confirmed as either true or false by our data on their proficiency in the two languages.

4.2 Other Languages in Erúshú Community

It is interesting to note that a good number of our respondents are able to speak other languages apart from Erúshú and Yorùbá. Other languages indicated as spoken by our respondents are: English, Ebíra and Hausa. However, out of the three, only English is worthy of note since it is the only language in which majority of the respondents have an appreciable degree of proficiency due to their formal education. Moreover, English is the nation's official language as well as the dominant educational language from the primary to the University level of the nation's educational system. Consider table 10 below for this presentation.

Table 10: Other languages spoken in Erúshú.

Degree	English		Others	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Nil	28	9.3	227	75.7
Poorly	45	15.0	32	10.7
Fairly	129	43.0	23	7.7
V well	79	26.3	11	3.7
Excellently	19	6.3	7	2.3
Total	300	100.0	300	100.0

As indicated in the above table, only 9.3 percent of our respondents have no facility at all in English language while an intimidating figure of 75.7 percent have no facility at all in other languages like Ebira or Hausa. The possession of Hausa and Ebira languages by a few Erúshú indigenes is not strange since Erúshú has its northern border with the northern part of Nigeria where we have the Hausa and the Ebira.

4.2 Verification of the Hypotheses

This section is on data analysis and verification of the various hypotheses formulated here. Our first null hypothesis, which sought to measure the degree of bilingual proficiency among the respondents, was formulated as follows:

H^0 : There is no significant difference in the abilities of our subjects in their two languages, Erúshú and Yorùbá.

The t-test was used to ascertain the proficiency level of respondents in their two languages, Erúshú and Yorùbá.

Table 11. T-test values showing the differences between subjects' Competence in Erúshú and Yoruba.

Variables	Poor %	Fair %	V.Well %	Excellently %	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	DF	t-cal	t-table	Result
Erushu	(8) 2.7	(32) 10.7	(123) 41.0	(137) 45.7	300	17.27	2.26	276	2.84	1.96	Significant
Yoruba	-	(4)1.3	(83) 27.7	(213)71.0	300	19.03	3.08				

$p < 0.05$

Table 11 shows that the t- calculated (2.84) is greater than the t-table (1.96). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is a significant difference in the subjects' proficiency in their two languages, Erúshú and Yorúbá. This implies that the respondents did not maintain the same degree of proficiency in their mother tongue, Erushu and the second language, Yoruba. The mean score in Yoruba is higher than that of Erushu and the t-value in both measures of bilingualism prove that they are more proficient in Yoruba than in Erushu. Since the t-value is greater than the critical value that means the null hypothesis is rejected using this measure of bilingualism. Statistically speaking, the Erushu know more of Yoruba than the Erushu language. For instance, while 71.0 percent of our respondents know Yoruba excellently only 45.7 percent attains this level for Erúshú. And about 13.4 percent of the respondents have a poor knowledge of Erúshú only 1.3 percent are of this category with respect to Yoruba.

In the questionnaire, we sought to know which code(s) the respondents would use in different contexts such as home, work, school, church and in the market in view of the fact that there is a relationship between language use and proficiency. This forms the basis for our second hypothesis which stated thus:

H⁰². There is no significant difference in the degree of proficiency of subjects in the two languages in different contexts. To test for this, the Chi-square Test and correlation matrix were employed.

Table 12a: Chi-Square Test Analysis: Subjects' Code Choice in Different Domains

Domains	No response	Erushú	Yorùbá	English	Erushú + Yorùbá	Yorùbá + English	Total
Home (Parents with Children)	-	33.9% (44)	26.9% (35)	0.77% (1)	38.5% (50)	-	100% (130)
Home (Children with parents)	-	13.5% (23)	67.1% (114)	2.9% (5)	13.5% (23)	2.9% (5)	100% (170)
Work (with boss)	-	6.0% (9)	56.7% (85)	18.7% (28)	14.0% (21)	4.7% (7)	100% (150)
Schools (with teachers)	-	1.2% (2)	26.7% (46)	65.1% (112)	2.3% (4)	4.7% (8)	100% (172)
Church/Mosque (with Congregations)	1.0% (3)	0.7% (2)	92.0% (277)	1.3% (4)	1.7% (5)	3.0% (9)	100% (300)
Market (buying and selling)	3.0% (9)	2.0% (6)	80.0% (240)	1.7% (5)	10.3% (31)	3.0% (9)	100% (300)

$$X^2C = 909.605$$

$$X^2t = 37.65$$

$$Df = 25$$

$$N = 300$$

$$P < 0.05$$

As evident in table 12a, the Chi-square calculated (909.605) greater than X^2t (37.65), thus the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies there is a highly significant difference in language use in the various domains. This result simply corroborates

corroborates that of percentage analysis in this same Table (12a). For instance, the home language for parents is Erúshá, that is 33.9% + 38.5% = 72.4% whereas the home language for the children is Yoruba with 67.1 percent. The language at work for the workers or adults is mainly Yoruba with 56.7 percent. The language at school for the youths or students happens to be English with 65.1 percent. Again, the church/mosque domain has Yoruba with 92.0 percent and the market also has Yoruba as the main code with 80.0 percent respondents acknowledging its use. Institutional support factors have also supported the use of Yoruba in religion.

For more illumination on language use in various domains we present the Pearson product moment correlation matrix showing the relationship among different contexts as in Table 12b

Table 12b: The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Matrix showing the relationship among different contexts.

	Home (Parents)	Home Children	Work	School	Church/Mosque	Market
Home (Parents)	1.0000					
Home (Children)	.4291**	1.0000				
Work	.7648**	.4553**	1.0000			
School	.4827**	.7570**	.4771**	1.0000		
Church/Mosque	.0011	.1748**	.0827	.2386**	1.0000	
Market	.0188	.0237	.0865	.0579	.2800**	1.0000

N = 300, ** significant at $\alpha = 0.05$ level

The correlation matrix, above shows the degrees of relationships between variables of interest. The table shows that the following pairs have significant relationships: parents' and children's language use at home; language use in work domain and home domain (for both parents and children); School domain and home domain (for both parents and children); in church/mosque domain and home domain (for the children); school domain and work; market domain and church/mosque.

For instance an average (0.4291) relationship exists between the language use of parents at home and children at home. The relationship (0.7648) between the language use at work with that of parents at home is high. There is an average

significant relationship (0.4827) between language use in the school and parents language use at home. There is almost no relationship (0.0011) between parents' relationship (0.0188) between parents' home language and that in the market.

There is a very fair significant relationship (0.4553) between children's language use at home and that of workers. There is a very high significant relationship (0.7570) between children's language use at home and language use in school. There is a very low but significant relationship (0.1748) between home language use of children and language use in the church/mosque. There is a very low but not significant relationship (0.0237) between language use in the market and children's language use at home. There is a very fair significant relationship (0.4771) between language use at school and at home. The relationship between (0.0827) language at church/mosque and at work is very poor and not significant. Also very poor and not significant relationship (0.0865) exist between language use in the market and at work.

There is a very low but significant relationship (0.2386) between school language and that of the church/mosque. Similarly, very poor and no significant relationship (0.0579) exist between market language and school language. Again, a poor but significant relationship (0.2800) exists between market language and that of the church/mosque. Of all these domains of language use, the highest relationship is between language use at work and parent's language use at home as well as school language and children's language use at home.

Thus far, the degree of proficiency of the respondents in Yoruba is superior to that of Erúshú. In what follows, we present analyses of how demographic variables (sex, age, etc) are related to proficiency, language choice and dominant language as well as language attitude among the respondents.

Since societal bilingualism could be sex-determined, we hypothesized as follows:

H_0^3 : Male and female subjects will not differ significantly in their proficiency in Erúshú and Yorùbá.

To verify this hypothesis, the mean scores of female and male respondents using the t-test were statistically compared. The results of our statistical comparison are summarized as Tables 13a and 13b below.

Table 13a: T-test values showing the differences between Male and Female proficiency in the Erushu Language.

Samples	Poor %	Fair %	V.Well %	Excellently %	N	$\bar{x}$	SD	tc	t-table	Result
Male	(4) 2.4	(13) 7.8	(77) 46.4	(72) 43.4	166	2.3795	1.5077	0.593	1.96	Not Significant
Female	(4) 2.99	(19) 14.2	(46) 34.3	(65) 48.5	134	2.2761	1.4938			

$p > 0.05$

Table 13a shows that t-calculated is less than the t-table hence the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is no significant difference between male and female proficiency in Erushu.

Table 13b: T-test values showing the differences between male and female proficiency in the Yoruba Language.

Samples	Poor %	Fair %	V.Well %	Excellently %	N	$\bar{x}$	SD	tc	t-table	Result
Male	-	(2)1.2	(54)32.5	(110)66.3	166	3.5904	0.6137	0.211	1.96	Not Significant
Female	-	(21.5)	(29)21.6	(103)76.7	134	3.5746	0.6759			

$p > 0.05$

Once again, table 13b shows that the t-calculated (0.211) is less than the t-table (1.96), hence the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 level of significance. In other words, there is no significant difference between male and female proficiency in Erushu.

However, since there is a high level of bilingual proficiency in this community, we probed to see if there is any relationship between age and bilingual proficiency of our subjects. The hypothesis is as follows:

H₀* There is no significant difference between subjects' proficiency in the two languages, Erúshù and Yoruba, with regard to age.

The t-test was once again used to test for this. The two languages under study were actually correlated with age. The results are presented as tables (14a) and (14b) below.

Table 14a: T-test values showing the differences in proficiency in Erúshù between the different age groups.

Age	Poor %	Fair %	V. Well %	Excellent %	N	Mean	SD	DF	t-cal	Sig.	Result
10-20	(8) 7.5	(27) 25.2	(62) 57.9	(10) 9.3	107	2.4904	1.3365	128	-2.265	0.025*	Sig.
21-30	-	(1) 3.1	(15) 46.9	(16) 50.0	32	3.1154	0.8628	128	-2.918	0.005*	Sig.
31-40	-	(4) 8.5	(18) 38.3	(25) 53.2	47	2.1860	1.5925	168	0.319	0.750	N'Sig.
41-50	-	-	(15) 35.7	(27) 64.3	42	2.0945	1.6351	168	0.324	0.745	N'Sig.
51+	-	-	(13) 18.1	(59) 81.9	72	3.0930	0.8399	168	-0.977	0.330	N'Sig.
Total	8	32	123	137	300						

* Sig.

In table 14a, there is a significant difference between the age groups as regards proficiency in Erushu. The first two groups, 10 – 20, and 21 – 30, show a lower level of proficiency in Erushu when compared with those who are over 30 years of age.

Thus, the null-hypothesis that our subjects do not differ in their proficiency with regard to age is rejected. This implies that bilingual ability is age-related in Erúshú community.

Table 14b: T-test showing the differences in proficiency in Yoruba between the different age groups.

Age	Poor %	Fair %	V. Well %	Excellent %	N	Mean	S.D	DF	t-cal	Sig.	Result	
10-20	-	(2) 1.9	(38) 35.5	(67) 62.6	107	3.3173	0.8037	128	-1.936	0.055	Not Sig.	
21-30	-	-	(7) 21.9	(25) 50.0	32	3.6538	0.7452	128	-2.029	0.409*	Sig.	
31-40	-	(1) 2.1	(10) 1.3	(36) (76.6)	47	3.5581	0.7336	168	-0.399	0.691	N'Sig	
41-50	-	-	(15) 8.6	(27) 4	71 4	42	3.6142	0.8170	168	-0.420	0.675	N'Sig
51+	-	(1) 1.4	(13) 2.2	(55) 4	76 4	72	3.2677	1.0649	168	-1.098	0.275	N'Sig.
Total	8	4	83	213	300							

*Sg.

From table 14a, we are able to see clearly that the first group, 10-20, (adolescents), is with a lower level of proficiency in Erúshú (32.7 percent for poor/fair and (67.3percent) for Very Well or Excellent) when compared with those over 20 years and above. That is, speech varies with speaker age. Indeed, competence in Erúshú language decreases as the age increases, that is, the older the better in Erúshú language.

However, with respect to Yoruba, age has no significant influence on its mastery as evident in table (14b). Indeed, with the exception of one age group (21 – 30) in this table where the significant value generated 0.049 is lesser than ($p < 0.05$),

all others are not significant. This is an indication that age has nothing to do with proficiency in Yoruba in Erushu community.

For hypothesis 5, the variable of education was examined. We hypothesized thus:

H_0^5 : Subjects will not differ in their proficiency in the second language as a result of their levels of education.

We have limited our investigation here to the second language, Yorùbá, since the first language, Erùshù, is not even near anything developed let alone being learnt in schools. To test this hypothesis, we have applied the analysis of variance statistical test. ANOVA like the chi-square is applied as a test whenever there are more than two variables to be tested. The result of this analysis is presented in table (15a).

Table 15a: One-way Analysis of variance showing the difference between Proficiency in Yorùbá and Level of Education

Source of variation	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F cal.	F table	Sig.
Between groups	197.564	3	65.855	7.350	2.60	0.000
Within groups	2651.983	296	8.959			
Total	2849.547	299				

As evident in table 15a, the F calculated which is 7.350 (i.e. $F_{cal} = 7.350 > F = 2.60$) is greater than the F table value which is 2.60, hence the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference between subjects proficiency in Yoruba and their level of education. In other words, proficiency in Yorùbá is related to the level of education of subjects.

Once an ANOVA test is significant, a Post Hoc analysis as presented directly below the ANOVA table 15b is mandatory to show the pairs that explain the significance.

Table 15b: Tukey HSD: Post Hoc Analysis

	Nil	Primary	Secondary	Post Secondary
Nil			*	
Primary				*
Secondary	*			*
Post Secondary		*	*	

As evident in the Post Hoc analysis there is a significant difference in the Yorùbá proficiency of those with secondary education vis-à-vis those with no formal education at all. Similarly, the Yorùbá proficiency of those with post-secondary education varies from that of the groups with primary education and even secondary education.

That the result of ability in Yoruba vis-à-vis education is significant should not surprise us since Yoruba is a subject on the school curriculum in Nigerian schools. Thus, education is a significant factor in bilingual proficiency in Erúshú community with regard to Yorùbá.

Another demographic variable tested for any influence on bilingual proficiency in Erúshú community is occupation. The hypothesis was formulated thus:

H_0^6 : Subjects will not differ in their proficiency in the two languages, Erúshú and Yoruba as a result of their occupation.

ANOVA was also used to test for this. The result is presented as table 16.

Table 16: One-way Analysis of Variance showing the differences in Language Proficiency of our respondents vis-à-vis their occupational backgrounds.

Source of variation	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F cal.	F table	Sig.
Between groups	42.270	5	8.454	0.885	3.21	0.491
Within groups	2807.277	294	9.559			
Total	2849.547	299				

Here, the F calculated which is 0.885 is less than the F table value which is 3.21 ($F_{cal} = 0.885 < F_{table} = 3.21$), this implies that the hypothesis is accepted. That is, there is no significant difference in subjects' bilingual proficiency as a result of their occupation. It therefore means that occupation does not actually have any significant effect on their language proficiency.

The last hypothesis to be tested here is on the possible correlation existing between the two languages under investigation vis-à-vis their different places of acquisition. The hypothesis was formulated thus:

H_0^7 : There is no significant difference between subjects in their proficiency in the two languages with regard to different places of their acquisition.

To test this, the ANOVA statistical test was applied since there are six occupational groups to be caputed. The result is presented as table 17 below.

Table 17: One-way Analysis of variance showing the difference in the proficiency of the respondents' with respect to place of acquisition.

Source of variation	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	F cal.	F table	Sig.
Between groups	43.295	3	14.432	1.522	2.60	0.209
Within groups	2806.252	296	9.481			
Total	2849.55	299				

Here the F calculated (i.e. $F_{cal} = 1.522 < F_{table} = 2.60$) which is 1.522 is less than the F table value of 2.60. It therefore means that the null hypothesis will be accepted because at 5 percent level, (0.05) the significant value generated (0.209) is greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$). In other words, there is no significant difference in the

proficiency of our subjects in the two languages as far as place of acquisition is concerned. This result is not at variance in any way with the self-report of our respondents who claimed to have acquired the two languages under investigation, *Erúshù* and *Yorùbá*, at home.

The next chapter shall focus on some detailed discussion of these findings. Meanwhile, we shall presently turn our attention to language use in specific domains in order to discover the functional allocation for roles of these two languages.

4.4 Language Use

Domains of language use varies from one community to the other. In the present investigation, five different domains have been recognized, viz: the home, work, school, market and religion. In addition, the context of situation of each domain varies. For instance, the home domain has six possibilities of different interlocutors communicating among themselves. The home domain is a major factor in matters of language use. Moreover, six code possibilities were recognized here since any two of the three codes being examined for domains of use could be alternately used within a discourse. Thus, we recognize in addition to *Erúshù*, Yoruba or English options, a mixture of *Erúshù* and Yoruba, Yoruba and English, *Erúshù* and English.

In the present analysis, subjects were categorized into subgroups. On language use at home, two separate groups (parents and their children) were recognized. The market is another domain meant to examine language use of traders and women.

Religion also constitutes another domain. Since language use in churches and mosques are predictable, it needs no serious investigation here. In what follows, we present the responses of our subjects domain by domain, starting with language use at home.

4.4.1 Language Choice at Home

A hundred and thirty (130) respondents who were parents reported on their language use with their children, wife/husband, relations, neighbours, friends when discussing important family matters at home. Table 18 as well as Figure 1 below both present the self-report of these parent respondents.

Table 18: Parents' Self-reports on Language Use (N=130)

Context	Erùshù	Yoruba	English	Erùshù + Yoruba	Yoruba+ English
Talking to children	34.6	31.5	0.8	33.1	-
Talking to spouse	21.5	51.5	2.3	22.3	2.3
Talking to relations	26.9	33.1	0.8	35.4	3.8
Talking to neighbours	12.3	49.2	0.8	32.3	5.4
Talking with another Erùshù speaker (friend)	11.5	53.8	2.3	27.7	4.6
Discussing family matter	26.9	33.9	0.8	37.7	0.8

Fig. 1: Language use in the home domain (parents' self-report)

The table above presents Yoruba as the major code used in communicating with various interlocutors by the adults at home in this data. 21.5 percent of married subjects agreed to use only Erúshú in talking with their spouses at home, while 51.5 percent claimed the use of only Yoruba. Thus, Yoruba is of a higher use than Erúshú, even in this domain.

In the data analysis, a mixture of Erúshú + English was never reported at all by any of our respondents, and very low percentages were recorded in the column for the mixture of Yoruba and English. This is a pointer to the fact that communication at home between adults and their interlocutors is done principally in this community either in Erúshú or Yoruba or a mixture of the two. This again, has implications for language alternation in this community.

It is however observed that parents' language use at home when talking to their children is Erúshú with 34.6 percent followed by Erúshú + Yoruba with 33.1 percent, while Yoruba only is with 31.5 percent. It is interesting to note that Erúshú still tops the list in this domain inspite of the fact that the children themselves are not

favourably disposed to the use of Erúshù language itself at home. Yoruba is also highly used when this set of respondents (parents) is talking with their neighbours.

The conclusion that can be drawn from the above analysis is that adults in this community communicate mostly even at home in Yoruba, although Erúshù is also highly used here by these adults, which is a reflection of the fact that people in this community are truly bilingual. Moreover, Yoruba seems to be gaining dominance at home among even the adults.

The graph in figure 1 illustrates at a glance parents' language use at home. For instance, the use of Erúshù records the highest percentage (92.0) in this domain when parents are talking to their children, the graph falls to 40.0 percent when they are discussing with either spouses or relatives and it drops lower still to even 20.0 percent when talking with neighbours and friends while it rises to 50.0 percent again, when discussing important family matters. On the other hand the graph on Yoruba usage is relatively on the high side throughout this domain with 80.0 percent when talking to siblings or spouse, 60.0 percent when talking with relatives, 80.0 percent when talking with neighbours and 80.0 percent again when talking with friends and finally 60.0 percent for family matters. English records 10.0 percent and below throughout in all situations in this domain.

To be able to assess fully the present situation, we now examine language use pattern at home among the youths to discover if the same pattern above exists in their language use with their interlocutors. The youths' language use at home is presented below as table 19, fig. 2

Table 19: Children's self-reports on language use at home (N=170)

Contexts	Erúshù %	Yoruba %	English %	Erúshù + Yoruba %	English + Yoruba %	English + Erúshù %
Talking to Parents	21.8	61.8	2.9	12.9	0.6	-
Talking to grand-parents	58.8	34.1	-	0.9	1.2	-
Talking to other siblings	21.8	55.3	8.3	9.4	4.7	0.6
Talking to other children in the neighbourhood	13.5	67.7	8.8	7.7	2.4	0.6

Fig 2. Language use in the home domain (children's self report)

In the graph, TP means language employed when talking to parents, TG represents when talking to grandparents, TS means language choice when talking to siblings in the family and Toc represents the language used when talking to other children in the community.

The pattern of language use among the youths in this community is not too different from that of their parents. A very high percentage of Erúshú youths claimed to use exclusively Erúshú in holding discussions with various interlocutors. However, when Yoruba is compared with Erúshú, it is discovered that the use of Yoruba is higher in percentage to that of Erúshú. This again, is a pointer to the fact that: (1) our respondents are truly bilingual in the two languages under study since the percentage of their use of the two languages is high, that is, when compared with the percentages recorded in the other rows; (2) Yoruba has dominance over Erúshú also among the youths.

For instance, the youths reported to use Erúshú mostly when talking with their grandparents which is not surprising since these old people are the custodians of culture.

Figure 2 also presents a clear picture of the foregoing. The two lines that are high up from all others in the graph belong to Erùshù only as well as Yoruba only. Erùshù has 40.0 percent when talking to parents but 97.0 percent when talking to grandparents and from that point onwards the graph line descends to even 20 percent. When talking to parents Yoruba has 100 percent but 60 percent when talking to grandparents. Again it has 85 percent when talking to other siblings and almost 120 percent when talking to their friends in the neighbourhood.

The influence of education is noticeable among this age group. It is noteworthy that few respondents communicate either in Yoruba and English (4.7%) or English (8.8%) exclusively with their interlocutors. Indeed, the Erùshù + English column that had nothing in the parents' table has a few percentages now, however minimal. This is a true reflection of the group we are analysing – students.

4.4.2 Language Choice at Work

This section presents the analysis of language use in the employment domain. Thus, the section takes care of workers only. In order to determine choice of code at place of work with different categories of people the respondents were asked to indicate the code(s) they use with their superiors, subordinates, equals when discussing different topics which could be private or official.

The responses of our subjects are shown in Table 20 below.

Table 20: Respondents' Language Choice at Work (N=150)

Context	Erúshú %	Yorúbá %	English %	Erúshú + Yorúbá %	Yorúbá + English %
Discussing officially with boss	6.0	56.7	18.7	14.0	4.7
Discussing officially with subordinates	15.3	53.3	12.0	14.0	5.3
Discussing officially with equals (colleagues)	4.7	59.3	14.0	17.3	4.7
Discussing unofficially with subordinates	6.0	66.7	10.0	12.0	5.3
When chatting during break	7.3	54.7	19.3	11.3	7.3

A comparison of the different choice of codes available reveals the fact that Yoruba can be regarded as the dominant language in the work domain in Erúshú community. Indeed, in all the different contexts Yoruba takes a comfortable lead over all the other code options. Next to Yoruba is English, especially in the context of discussing official matters with superiors. This is attributable to the fact that English is the nation's official language which must be reflected in a self-report investigation of this nature even though this is not the practice in reality. Moreover, English can only be used at work by the educated ones who are at the same time engaged in government offices.

A mixture of Erúshú + Yoruba is the next code in the order of frequency. This code mixture is noticeable at work among the artisan group. Generally, we observe that the two indigenous languages (Erúshú and Yoruba) here have high premium in oral communication in this community even when the official language

expected in this domain is English. English is however used invariably for all written communication. The high percentage of the use of indigenous languages in the data depicts the rural nature of this community which has very few government workers.

4.4.3 Language choice in schools

The school domain with respect to students in both primary and secondary schools in this domain bears correspondence to the work domain of the worker - civil servants, farmers, artisans and traders. Table 21 below presents the response of the students in respect of their choice of code when in school. The data in this section was got from their response to the question: what language would you normally use at school when talking formally to teachers, classmates, seniors, juniors and generally during break?

Table 21: Respondents language choice at school (N=172)

Context	Erúshú	Yoruba	English	Erúshú + Yoruba	Yoruba + English
Talking formally to teachers	1.2	26.7	65.1	2.3	4.7
Talking to classmates	1.7	59.3	33.7	0.6	4.7
Talking to seniors	1.2	59.3	36.0	–	3.5
Talking to junior	2.3	63.4	26.2	–	8.1
Talking during break	2.9	76.2	6.4	2.3	12.2

In formal situations, that is when talking formally to teachers, English, as expected is the code normally employed by the students with as high as 65.1 percent of the respondents indicating English. The reason for this is that English is the language of education in Nigeria. Next to this code is Yoruba with 26.7 percent which is still normally a code used in education at our primary schools in Nigeria. Indeed, Yoruba is allowed officially up to primary three in this domain.

Apart from the formal situation, majority of the respondents- 59.3% in row(2), 59.3% in row (3), 63.4% in row (4), and 76.2% in row (5) – use Yoruba to communicate with their interlocutors in this domain. And next to this code in terms of frequency is English with 33.7%, 36.0%, 26.2%, and 6.4% respondents in rows (2-5) respectively.

Generally speaking Erúshú as well as code-mixing has little or no place in the language use of the students when in school. This observation goes to confirm our earlier finding which shows that the school is not a place to learn Erúshú, after all, it is not a subject on the school curriculum. Moreover, the school is ethnically mixed to some extent in terms of staff and students, hence informal communication is much more expected in a general language like Yoruba or English than in Erúshú which is highly restricted to the home domain.

The next domain to be examined for language use is the domain of religion.

4.4.4. Language choice in Religion.

Although language use in churches or mosques is predictable, our respondents were still asked a few questions so as to elicit the dominant language for them in this domain. The result of our investigation is presented in table 22 below.

Table 22: Respondents' language choice in churches/mosques (N=300)

Context	No Response	Erúshú	Yoruba	English	Erúshú + Yoruba	Yoruba + English
When singing	3.0	1.0	91.0	2.3	0.7	2.0
Making announcement	1.3	1.3	92.7	1.7	0.3	5.0
When preaching	1.7	1.0	90.0	2.0	0.3	1.7
Praying during service	-	0.7	91.3	2.0	1.3	4.7
Praying individually	1.3	1.0	92.0	1.7	1.3	2.7
Talking to officials	0.7	0.7	96.3	0.3	0.7	1.3
Talking to congregation	1.0	0.7	92.3	1.3	1.7	3.0

As already stated, language choice in religion is always almost predictable. Thus, Yoruba as evident in the data has an overwhelming response as the language of the church and mosque for our respondents in all the contexts. But then, internal functions of language like praying personally or counting according to Mackey (1968) could be a function of the dominant language. It is for this reason that we bring up for discussion our respondents' responses to the question: what language would you normally use in the church /mosque when praying silently as an

individual? To this question, 92.0% respondents indicated Yoruba while only 1.0% picked Erúshù and another 1.3% picked Erúshù + Yoruba. Yoruba + English mixture has 2.7% and English only has 1.7%. Once again, Yoruba has come up as the dominant language for our respondents even in the context of praying personally.

The last domain of study here is the market domain.

4.4.5. Language choice in the Market

Our respondents were also required to state their choice of code in the market domain. For instance, whenever people buy and sell, haggling takes place in one language or the other. To elicit the dominant language in this domain for our respondents, they were asked to indicate their choice of code when buying or selling something to a customer who understands/speaks both Erúshù and Yoruba. Table 23 below summarizes the responses we got from the subjects in this regard.

Table 23: Language use in the Market when Buying or selling.

Language	Frequency	Percentage
Nil	9	3.0
Erúshù	6	2.0
Yoruba	240	80.0
English	5	1.7
Erúshù + Yorùbá	31	10.3
English + Yorùbá	9	3.0
Total	300	100.0

The table above shows that language use in the market domain is only in favour of Yoruba language despite the fact that these people are in a position to use either Erúshù or Yoruba with their interlocutors. For instance, while 80.0 percent claimed to use only Yorùbá, another 10.3 percent code-switch between Erúshù and Yorùbá in this domain. It is noteworthy that Yoruba+ English (3.0%) competes favorably well with English only (1.7%) in this domain. This is an indication of the fact that the market place is a mixed gathering which requires a general language to interact with the different ethnic groups usually present in a market situation.

Thus far, we have examined language use in various domains in the community under study. The next chapter will still focus on the results got from the data analysis. Suffice it to say for now that language use patterns here are in favour of Yoruba language. Yoruba from the analysis thus far serves in more domains in this community than Erúshú. We examine in a moment the general language use pattern in Erúshú community.

4.4.6 General Language use pattern in Erúshú

The indigenous language of this community is Erúshú language. And this language, no doubt, is still very much in use in this community by the young and the old. Hence, we tried to find out the popularity of the second language here which is Yoruba.

We sought to determine the popularity of this language, Yoruba, through some three or four questions of the following sort. First, we asked the respondents how frequently they do communicate in Erúshú as well as in Yoruba at home. To this question, 63.3 percent answered the always option for Erúshú, whereas we have 77.3 percent for those who communicate in Yoruba always at home. This is presented as Table 24 below.

Table 24: Respondents self-report on the use of Erúshú and Yoruba

Degree	Erúshú		Yorúbá	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Missing case	1	0.3	1	0.3
Never	3	1.0	1	0.3
Hardly	20	6.7	7	2.3
Sometimes	86	28.7	59	19.7
Always	190	63.3	232	77.3
Total	300	100.0	300	100.0

Furthermore, when we asked them to indicate in what language(s) they do communicate generally, the result is an overwhelming percentage of 75.3 for Yoruba as against 16.3 percent for Erúshú. This is also presented as table 25 and figure 3 below. Further still, we asked for the language they considered as their best language

of communication. The percentage for Yoruba is 84.0 percent while Erúshú has 11.3 percent. This is equally presented as in table 26.

Table 25: Respondents self-reports on the general language of communication

Language	Frequency	Percent
Missing cases	1	0.3
Erúshú	49	16.3
Yoruba	226	75.3
English	19	6.3
Others	5	1.7
Total	300	100.0

Fig 3: Bar chart showing the distribution of the general language use

Table 26: Respondents self-Reports on the best language

Languages	Frequency	Percent
Erúshú	34	11.3
Yoruba	252	84.0
English	10	3.3
Others	4	1.3
Total	300	100.0

The graph in figure 3 as well as tables 24-26 confirms clearly that Yoruba is more popular in Erúshú community than the native tongue. As evident in figure 3, the bar for Yoruba is more than triple in size the one for Erúshú, which is a clear indication of the fact that Yoruba is the more widely used language as regards the two languages under study.

The present situation is not surprising since Yoruba is of a higher status in the nation than English. Besides, the community is of the opinion that they are Yoruba by tribe; hence, they do not even feel they are losing anything by not using Erúshú to communicate in all contexts within the community. This observation has an implication for language shift. However, to be able to conclude on this beyond doubt, we need to examine the language attitude of our respondents and weigh this against the present discovery. Before then, we present code-switching as a bilingual language use option in Erúshú community.

4.5 Discussion of Important findings on code-switching/mixing

4.5.1 Patterns of Code-switching

The code-switching and code-mixing data in Erúshú community among bilinguals can take any of the following forms;

- a. Erúshú + Yoruba
- b. Erúshú + English
- c. Erúshú + Yoruba + English

In other words, it could be a mixture of the two major indigenous languages in this community or a mixture of Erushu and English or of even the three main languages here viz: Erúshú, Yoruba and English

Examples of type (a): (Erúshú + Yoruba)

4. Dèni keke *ilámwò* ní?

How do examination you

i.e. 'How did you do your exam?

5. *Á si yémi* *sí*
I not understand it
i.e. 'I didn't understand it'

6. *Wà ni ran* *ìwé gan*
They BE understand book very much
i.e. 'They are very brilliant'

7. *A mi ve ùwà eshú* *dandan*
I Future go farm tomorrow compulsorily
i.e. 'I will go to the farm compulsorily tomorrow.'

8. *Ówo po màáù*
We kill cow
i.e. 'We killed a cow'

The italicized words are the Yoruba words incorporated into Erúshù expressions.

Example of type (b) : (Erúshù + English)

9. *Óho wá set á* *ha*
What they give it difficult
i.e. 'what they gave (as questions) was difficult'

10. *Vá á da material*
They not buy material
i.e. 'They did not buy the material'

11. *Bòdá Accord á á* *gétí èje*
Brother accord he that got himself
i.e. 'Brother Accord is confused'

12. Wò gba *range* vá
 Go bring range come
 i.e. 'Go and fetch the range'
13. À ve *school*
 He go school
 i.e. 'He has gone to school'

Although, the English words in this section can be easily identified, we still consider it to be a consistent way of presentation if they are italicized in conformity with our pattern, rather than leave such items to the reader's imagination.
 Example of type (c): (Erúshù – Yoruba-English)

14. Omumu dè ni o ke *GBÌYÀNJÙ* dé á *gain anything*
 all as foc verb do try much we gain anything
 i.e. 'Hard as we tried, we did not gain anything'.

15. Ma *FE* ta ò da magí
 I want to go buy magí
 i.e. 'I want to go and buy magí.'

16. À *YE* tí omumu ò ve *school*
 It necessary that all us go school
 i.e. 'it is necessary for all of us to be educated'.

17. Àyàfí *graph* mà a ke *DAADAA*
 Except graph I not do well well
 i.e. 'Except the graph which I didn't do very well'

18. Age *YÀTÒ SÌ eje*
age different from one another'

i.e. Their ages are different from one another'

On the data in this section, English items are simply italicized while the Yoruba ones are capitalized and italicized.

People in Erúshú community generally are in the habit of code-mixing in informal conversations. Such conversations or discussions take place at home, at ethnic or village meetings, at parties, etc. In these situations, participants speak Erúshú cum Yoruba and some English, if need be. It is remarkable that the same people who code-mix on such informal occasions resist code-mixing on more serious or formal occasions. If they practice this at all on such occasions, they do it so minimally. Essien (1995) reported this same situation among the Ibibio of Nigeria with respect to Ibibio-English code-mixing.

The manifestation of code-mixing in our Erúshú data has once again established the fact that code-switching or code-mixing is a characteristic of language use in bilingual communities when all the participants in a speech situation share a bilingual background (cf. Savic 1995, Myers-Scotton 1993c, 1999, 2001, 2004, Nsawir 1999, Oyetade 2004).

The Erúshú community, no doubt, has remained consistently multilingual, while, the individual members have tended towards mono-or bi-lingualism. That is, the finding shows that the community is shifting to Yoruba and / or using a mixed code that consists of three languages. This same situation was discovered among Punjabi Sikh community in Malaysia by David et al. (2003). Their study reported the fact that the use of stand-alone Punjabi at home increases with age, the use of stand alone English at home increases as the age of respondents decreases, and that there is a language shift from Punjabi to either English or a mixture of three languages – Punjabi, English, and Malay. Fakuade et al.(2003) equally reported this same situation of language shift from mother tongues towards Fulfulde in Adamawa state of Nigeria. And that while economic, social ... factors are identified as some of the causes for the shift, language spread ... and *code-switching* are found to be some of the sociolinguistic implications of the shift.

4.5.2 Social Function

The question on the social functions of code-switching or code-mixing touches on the comparative ability of these languages in contact to express new concepts in a developing modern society such as Nigeria in general and Erúshú in particular. Sybil-James (1979) opines that one can hardly discuss language activity without taking into consideration the relationship between those who must communicate and the circumstances that give rise to the communication.

Using the functional model suggested by Appel and Muysken (1987) for why people switch between languages in the course of a single conversation, CS or code-mixing in Erúshú can be said to have the following functions:

1. A *referential* function, in that it often involves lack of knowledge of one language or lack of facility in that language on a certain subject.

19. *Maths set ni sì rí?*

Maths set your is where

i.e. 'where is your maths set?

20. *Má mi ké assignment ràn*

I not do assignment my

i.e. 'I have not done my assignment'

21. *Na wò da mattress*

You go buy mattress

i.e. 'you should go and buy mattress'

22. *Ma rí ve class*

I BE go class

i.e. 'I am going to the class'

23. À hen pé òna a o da rádiò
 He said that he BE go buy radio
 i.e. 'He said that he was going to buy radio'

This pattern reported above is found in discourse about technical subjects in many languages of the Third World (cf. Appel and Muysken, 1987). The list includes scotton (1979), Nsawir (1999), Myers-scotton and Bolonyai (2001), Lamidi (2003) among others.

For instance, Bentahila and Davies (1992: 453) cited in Myers-Scotton (1993c), studied two different groups of Moroccan Arabic / French bilinguals who differ demographically mainly in age and reported that the conversation of the older group is neither mainly in Arabic or French, while that of the younger group is basically Arabic. But the topics are fairly technical for the younger group (a biology lesson and a secretarial studies course) and the speakers use some French. We now consider the next function.

2. Another function is the *directive* function in that it involves the hearer directly. This participant-related switching can be seen as markers of some sort of familiarity as well as a kind of distancing device (i.e. a verbal strategy for purposes of solidarity or vice versa).

Examples:

24. Mistake wá ke IJÓSI á general
 Mistake they do that time BE general
 i.e. 'The mistake committed then was general'

25. Má si *dictate ine* íé take, problem wá kan beni
 You should dictate what want done problem you have this
 i.e. 'You should dictate what you want, this is your problem'.

26. Á ke ègírí dèni òbò
 He do head like monkey
 i.e. 'His head resembles that of the monkey'
27. À í rarà èmu
 He BE 'stupid' mouth
 i.e. 'He is joking /not serious or stupid'
28. Bòdá Accord á à gétì èje
 Brother accord he not get himself.
 i.e. 'Brother Accord is confused/ foolish'

The data above is directly related to the accommodation theory developed by Giles (1973). The process of adjustment between speakers to each other is called accommodation. This same pattern of code-switching was reported by Myers-Scotton (2004:5) with respect to Tamil/English code-switching (in Canagurajah 1995:204). In this example from Sri Lanka, a young job applicant uses code-switching to level inequalities between himself and a professor in an interview for a university position. English has no official status in Sri Lanka, but it is known by the highly educated. Thus, the professor opened the interview in English. The job candidate replied in code switching pattern of Tamil as the source of the morphosyntactic frame, with English content word insertions. It is noteworthy that after several turns in which the professor spoke only English, he switched to Tamil/English code-switching, as well. In effect, he accommodated to the job candidate.

3. Another reason worthy of note here given by respondents for code mixing bothers on *expressive* function of code mixing (Poplack 1980). That is, for fluent bilingual speakers, conversation full of code mixing is a mode of speech by itself, and individual switches no longer have a discourse function.

Moreover, speakers emphasize a mixed identity through the use of two languages in the same discourse.

Examples:

29. *Àwọn ará Àmò wón mi sí*
Plural people 'amọ' BE I BE
i.e. 'I am from Amọ quarters (in Erúshú).
30. *Ógá rán an gan berin*
'Boss my is particularly this
i.e. 'This is my real boss'.
31. *Sé àláfià mé sí?*
Hope peace you are
i.e. 'Hope it is well with you?'
32. *Vá á da material*
They not buy material
i.e. 'They did not buy the material'.
33. *But wá tiráí nà*
But you try even
i.e. 'Indeed, you have tried'.
34. *Wá rí mọ̀tọ̀ ve aja*
they see mọ̀tọ̀ go market
i.e. 'They couldn't get vehicle to the market'

The Erúshú bilinguals cannot really completely distinguish Yoruba vocabulary items from that of Erúshú. Thus, in such circumstances, code mixing serves to facilitate communication since people can easily and readily find a word or expression in Yoruba or even English to say whatever they mean to say. It follows

that instead of groping about for appropriate words or expressions to discuss an experience or concept in the mother tongue, bilinguals tend to substitute patterns from Yoruba or English as the case may be, since either of these are seemingly "richer" than Erushu in terms of vocabulary items. Both Ahukanna (1990) and Essien (1995) reported this same pattern among the Ibibio-English bilinguals and Igbo-English bilinguals respectively.

This pattern may however be used as a bid for solidarity with the other tongue or the tongues involved. For instance, Myers-Scotton (2004) cited the use of Fanakalo / Afrikaans (South African) by a white to bid for solidarity with the common people and also a lowering strategy. The language (Fanakalo) was used in colonial South Africa in asymmetrical master-servant relationships. However, when Fanakalo is used between peers, especially outside of the work setting, it can index shared group membership. The example (Myers-Scotton 2004:7-8):

Four middle-class white males are playing tennis double at a private club. Three of the players immigrated to South Africa earlier from Europe, and the fourth, a younger man, was born and brought up in South Africa. These are men whose unmarked language in this interaction would probably be English. One of the older residents (of British Origin) checks on the score by asking:

Ini lo telling?

'What's the score?'

(Adendorff 1993:21)

According to Myers-Scotton what makes this example especially interesting is that a white speaker uses Fanakalo to other whites in a tennis match at a private club outside the South African city of Durban. In this example, the speaker combines Fanakalo (*ini lo* 'what's the') with Afrikaans (*telling* 'score'). In doing this, he is using the two "indigenous" South African languages that all the participants would

be likely to know, at least in part. But note that he himself would be a native speaker of English. Adendorff (1993) comments that the speaker is indexing an assumed common South African identity among a group of status-equal white South Africans.

4.5.3 Morphosyntactic Patterning

This section examines the relationship between morphology and syntax as far as code-switching is concerned in Erushu community. For instance, a word can contain many morphemes just as a sentence is made up of many words. Thus, the code-switched items are classified according to their morphosyntactic features.

4.5.3.1 Lexical borrowing

We noticed that Erúshú-English CS is strongest in areas such as academic disciplines, the professions, politics, the economy, etc. Normally, such discussions would start off in Erúshú only to be switched into English and the two codes would be contending with each other for control.

No doubt, the English words that get slotted into Erúshú based expressions are foreign to the culture. Moreover, those English items must have been borrowed into Erushu via the Yoruba language, if we consider the fact that Yoruba is a medium of instruction at the primary school level in this community. To Myers-Scotton (1993a:165) these are cultural borrowed forms as opposed to core borrowed forms. Cultural forms are names of objects or concepts which are foreign to the culture of the host language. Such example in the data include: *set, maths, motor, chairman, etc.* Core forms, on the other hand, are items for which there are alternative items in the host language. Myer-Scotton contends that since core borrowed forms have alternatives in the host language, they occur less frequently than cultural borrowed items.

Based on the lexical typologies of loan-word found in the literature (see Ajolore 1982, Salami 1982, Appel and Muysken 1990, Myers-Scotton 1993a, Lamidi 2003) we conclude that the two types of loan –words evident in our data on Erúshú-English CS are:

1. Partially assimilated loan words:

Bòdà, sènjì, tirà, mòtò, ròbà

Sùkiù, pénsù, etc.

2. Unassimilated loan words:

maths, set, material, pure, range, accord, school, radio, etc.

Notice however that while the unassimilated loan items stand out completely as borrowed, the partially assimilated items resulted into forms which could still be spotted as borrowed words, hence, to be distinguished as foreign in Erúshú structures. Moreover, while the former type can be found in the speech of many uneducated speakers the latter type are used by educated speakers.

The Yoruba words slotted into Erúshú - Yoruba CS are of the same morphemic pattern with Erúshú words; hence they are unrecognizable as Yoruba words and undistinguishable from native words. Examples include:

Idámwò, iwé, àgbàdò, bàbá, ògá, etc.

In other words, to demarcate between borrowings which occur in Erúshú - Yorùbá CS and those which are generally regarded as part of Yoruba vocabulary is a little bit difficult. Thus, we conclude that borrowings within Erúshú - Yoruba CS is a case of fully assimilated loan- words.

It is however surprising to find in Erúshú - Yoruba CS, Yoruba words such as : *bàbá, màmá, tṣu, ògá, rùgbudùrugbudu*, etc. which are so basic in every language that it is not necessary for one language to borrow such from another. This negates Banjo's (1983:20) opinion that "...nouns like *head, hand*, etc. indicating parts of the body seldom occur" in Yorùbá - English CS simply because those items are so basic in every language and therefore need not be borrowed. Again, on Yorùbá - English CS Lamidi (2003:59) supplied words like *proud, grumble* and *lies* as counter examples to Banjo's explanation since these are also basic in every language yet they do get slotted into Yoruba - English CS.

All the same, since the degree of code -switching is indicative not only of the speaker's bilingualism, but also of his relative communicative incompetence in his

38. A i rara *ènu*
 (subject) (object)
 He Be joking mouth
 i.e. 'He is joking'
39. [*Akoko* inine] si [oso horo]
 (subject) (verb) (object)
 time everybody be home it
 i.e. 'It was a time everybody was at home'
40. Owo po *malu*
 (subject) (verb) (object)
 We kill cow
 i.e. 'We killed a cow'
41. Má á sẹ owon (*rara*) *Qlórun*
 (subject) (verb) (object) (adjunct)
 I not speak vernacular at all God
 i.e. 'I don't understand the language at all, to God I swear'
42. Mámá ran a ve uwa
 (subject) (verb) (object)
 Mother my she go farm
 i.e. 'My mother has gone to the farm'
43. [Tami so mi geni *orúkọ*] Verb Phrase
 (Negator) (verb) (object)
 don't call me that name
 i.e. 'Don't ever call me that name (again)'

44. A ke egeri deni obo
 (subject) (verb) (object) (adjunct)
 he do head like monkey
 i.e. 'His head resembles that of the monkey'

as an NP only once as follows:

45. [Awon ara Amo] won mi si
 (object) (verb) (subject) (verb)
 people (of) Amo quarters BE I Be
 i.e. 'I am from Amo quarters (in Erushu)'

as a verb only once as follows:

46. A si yemi si
 (subject) (negator) (verb) (object)
 I not understand it
 i.e. 'I didn't understand it'

as a VP in three sentences as follows

47. Se alafo me si?
 (question) (object) (subject) (verb)
 hope peace you are
 i.e. 'Hope it is well with you?'

48. Tini ba ri Dayo do ga (pe) owa [o ka] iwe
 (comp.)s (comp.)s (V) (O) (V) (O) (comp.) (S) (V) (O)
 if you see Dayo tell him that we BE read book
 i.e. 'if you see Dayo tell him that we are going to study'.

49. [Omumu udan (owọ)] a bọ sí asan
 (subject) (verb) (prep) (object)
 all work hand Asp. come to nothing

i.e. 'All his efforts have been wasted'

as *Adverbs* in many sentences as follows

50. Amí ve ùwà eshu dandan
 (subject) (verb) (object) (adjunct) (adjunct)
 I go farm tomorrow compulsorily

i.e. 'I must go to farm tomorrow'

51. Wa ke e tẹtẹ
 (subject) (verb) (object) (adjunct)
 they do it before

i.e. 'They have done it before'

52. [(Qga) ran an gan] be erin
 (subject) (verb) (object)
 boss my is particularly this

i.e. 'This is my real boss'

53. [(isu) ran an] şu daadaa
 (subject) (verb) (adjunct)
 yam my is develop well well

i.e. 'My yam tuber developed very well'

54. Má á se owọ rará (Qlorun)
 (S) (neg.) (verb) (object) (adjunct) (adjunct)
 I not speak vernacular at all God

i.e. 'I don't understand the language at all, to God I swear'.

55. Gè mi ba [(bàbá) ran] dandan
 (verb) (object) (verb) (object) (adjunct)
 Help me greet father my well well
 i.e. 'Help me greet my father very well!'

56. Ènàò árí rùgbùdùrùgbudu
 (S) (V) (C)
 ours appears very big very big
 i.e. 'Ours appears to be out of shape'

57. À ja [ìgbéjowó da] tagbáratagbára
 (S) (V) (O) (A)
 He held all hand that with force with force
 i.e. 'He held onto that with all power'

58. Á he òna nìmi bá mi tílíláé
 (S) (V) (S) (Neg.) (V) (O) (adjunct)
 he say he not greet me for ever
 i.e. 'He said that he would not greet me again'

59. [Omumu udan (owó)] á b' sí asín
 (S) (V) (prep) (object)
 all work hand ASPECT come to nothing
 i.e. 'All his efforts have been wasted'

N.B: S – Subject O – Object VP – Verb Phrase
 V – Verb A – Adjunct Neg. – Negator
 Comp. – Complementizer C – Complement Prep. – Preposition

Having determined the categories featured by the data, we may further ask: Is the probability of occurrence of these categories the same? The answer here is obviously No. The noun for instance, as evident in the data has the highest frequency, followed by the adverb.

Again, we may want to probe further by asking: what are the syntactic constraints which appear to operate on this process of code-switching? We observe that nouns appear inserted more frequently than any other parts of speech in Yoruba, thus signifying that the paradigmatic constraints on nouns appear to be less than that of other Yoruba word classes. Indeed, apart from verbs and adverbs, no other part of speech seems inserted. We are therefore of the opinion that only major parts of speech can be borrowed from Yoruba into Erùshù in matters of Erùshù- Yoruba CS.

A syntactic analysis (as presented in Poplack, 1980; Sankoff and Poplack, 1981; Bentahila and Davies, 1983; Woolford, 1983; Myers- Scotton, 1993, 1997; Savic, 1995; Myers-Scotton and Jake, 2000; Lamidi, 2003 among others) which will specify what properties bar these categories of words from CS structure is definitely beyond the scope of the present investigation that is sociological rather than syntactic in nature (cf. Banjo, 1983, 1996).

We conclude this section with a cursory analysis of the Erùshù- English CS in the data. We observe that nouns (partially assimilated or not) occur with little restraint in these CS structures whereas only one conjunction, *but*, and a few verbs occur. However, with the occurrence of a conjunction and no adverb at all, we conclude that although the noun takes the lead in frequency in the two types of CS, even then, the pattern of CS for the two mixtures still differs. Furthermore, the syntagmatic constraints (tense, aspect, plural morpheme) operating on Erùshù- English CS must be different from that of Erùshù- Yoruba CS. This is because Erùshù is very similar to Yoruba structurally. For instance, both have no affixes to overtly mark tense, aspect and number all the time whereas these are morphologically marked all the time in English.

4.6 Language Attitude

This section explores language attitude in Erùshù community. Language attitude is another major area of investigation in studies on societal bilingualism.

Baker (1992:3) is of the view that the relationship between two (or more) languages within a variety of contexts or domains can be explored in terms of individual attitudes. This is the approach adopted in this study. Moreover, since language attitudes can be ascertained through the use of indirect questions from respondents, we have tried to do exactly this here with the opinion questions posed to our respondents. This is to ensure that the information to be obtained is reliable.

In what follows, we present the responses we got to these attitudinal questions. In response to the question: which of the following languages (i.e. Erúshú, Yoruba, English and others) do you consider most prestigious? A prestigious language was explained to the subjects in terms of popularity and social status. Subjects responded as presented in figure 4.

Fig. 4: Pie Chart of the Language Attitude of the respondents

As evident from figure 4, Yoruba takes a comfortable lead again with 79.7 percent while English with 14.0 percent is even rated more prestigious (by the educated

people of course) than the mother tongue with 5.3 percent. We hasten, however, to say that this result is a typical another these people may not have taken cognizance of English as part of the languages in question which explains why Yoruba was rated higher than English here. Moreover, the background of the respondents who are predominantly illiterates affected the result.

Surprisingly, Erúshú has just 5.3 percent of the total responses. This no doubt is a negative disposition towards this mother tongue since the norm in studies of this nature is for respondents to see their mother tongue as more prestigious than the second language, at least for sentimental reasons if not for any other reason.

The highest percentage (70.0%) of our respondents says Yoruba is most prestigious because it is their forefather's language. Next to this reason in percentage (18.0%) is that there are many people who speak it apart from its native speakers. 9.7 percent are of the view that it is most useful to speak it than other languages. 1.0 percent says that Yoruba can be used for all purposes.

Finally, 0.7 percent picked the item which says that it is good, fluent and better than other languages.

Two important attitudinal questions on the questionnaire used to gather information from respondents are : (1) Yorùbá is a threat to Erushu and (2) If care is not taken Yoruba will completely replace Erushu in future The two questions were basically posed to the respondents so as to discover their attitude to their mother tongue, Erúshú, as well as their second language Yoruba, that is, when the question comes in a direct manner.

Respondents' answers to these two important questions are presented below as Tables (27a) and (27b).

Table 27a: Respondents Attitude Towards Erúshú Language.

Age	N	Positive %	Indifferent %	Negative %
10-20	107	95.3	-	4.7
21-30	32	96.9	-	3.1
31-40	47	91.5	2.1	16.4
41-50	42	100	-	-
51+	72	94.4	-	5.6

Table 27b: Respondents' Attitude towards Yorùbá Language

Age	N	Positive %	Indifferent %	Negative %
10-20	107	53.0	-	47.0
21-30	32	31.0	-	69.0
31-40	47	45.0	-	55.0
41-50	42	30.0	-	70.0
51+	72	44.0	-	56.0

Tables (27a) and (27b) show the attitude of the Erùshú towards their two languages. It is however not surprising to find on table (27a) an overwhelming support across the ages, indicative of a positive attitude, for the Erùshú language. Whereas as evident in table (27b) such a support is lacking for Yorùbá language.

The simple reason for this response is that the question bears directly on language attitude, thus making the informants to be conscious of their answers. And since most informants are aware of the fact that their mother-tongue is the principal carrier of their culture and identity; hence the tendency to answer such questions in the affirmative.

The overall inference from tables 27a and 27b is that Erùshú is in a healthy state. Based on the analysis on table 27, it appears that Erùshú and its values are exposed to danger more than the people are aware of. Yorùbá is accumulating more speakers at the expense of this community's heritage language.

This may however be a sign of a deeper problem. Notice that the youths are no longer clinging to their divine right i.e. culture (which includes language) but they let go of these privileges and glory in order to have enough room to imbibe other foreign cultures and languages such as English, French and Yorùbá. These youths mean well after all, hence the split commitment here between Erùshú and Yoruba. Indeed, they do not want the world to leave them behind at all cost. The cost this time is the forfeiture of a thorough mastery of the mother tongue since its socio-economic value in the global village is too minimal. Thus, their craze for civilization cum westernization has resulted into language shift and language endangerment. We therefore conclude that bilingualism in this community is subtractive.

The responses we got from the other attitudinal questions are however positive. For instance, in response to the question: Are you proud that you speak Erùshù? 87.7 percent ticked *Yes* as opposed to the small percentage of 11.3 percent who picked *No* and 1.0 percent is for *no response*. Again, we asked: if hitherto you don't speak Erùshù could you have learnt it? 83.0 percent of our subjects picked *Yes*, while 15.3 percent said *No*, and we are left with 1.7 percent as no response.

Responses to some other questions based on ethnic identity, language shift and maintenance are summarized and presented as table 28:

Table 28: Respondents' self-report on ethnic identity (N=300)

	No. Response	Strongly agree	Agree	Indifferent	Disagree	Strongly disagree
a) I need to speak Erùshù to express my ethnic identity	-	2.7	8.3	0.3	47.7	41.0
b) Yoruba is enough for me to express my ethnicity	-	16.7	44.7	1.7	31.0	6.0
c) I don't need to encourage my children to learn Erùshù	1.0	10.0	60.0	-	14.0	15.0
d) Yoruba is a threat to Erùshù	-	8.7	25.7	-	35.0	30.7
e) Erùshù speakers are socially inferior to Yoruba speakers	-	23.3	59.7	1.0	10.3	5.7
f) Erùshù speakers feel ashamed to speak it in mixed gatherings	-	18.7	58.7	1.3	11.7	9.7
g) if care is not taken Yoruba will completely replace Erùshù in future	1.0	21.0	13.7	0.3	24.3	39.7

From the responses in (a) and (b) respondents tend to consider themselves ethnically as Yoruba. This is because 88.7 percent did not see the need to speak Erúshú to express their ethnic identity. To corroborate this 61.4 percent (strongly) agreed that Yoruba is enough for them to express their ethnic identity. A natural corollary of their attitude which is evident in (a) and (b) above is that 70.0 percent did not see any need to encourage their children to learn Erúshú.

On whether the continued use of Yoruba in that locality constitutes a threat to Erúshú 65.7 percent disagreed as opposed to 34.3 percent who agreed. In addition, 77.3 percent agreed as opposed to 20.3 percent who disagreed to an opinion such as: some Erúshú speakers feel ashamed to speak it in mixed gatherings. Finally on this, an overwhelming 64.0 percent respondents as opposed to 34.7 percent disagreed vehemently with such a carefully worded statement such as: if care is not taken Yoruba will completely replace Erúshú language in future.

The foregoing is a clear indication that attitudes are latent, inferred from the direction and persistence of external behaviour. (Baker 1992). Thus, a distinction can be made with the present data between intention and actual behaviour. That is, while the respondents here outwardly manifest a positive attitude for their mother tongue, Erúshú, any time the question is more potent and direct, their underlying attitude is different. The consistent patterns in behaviour as evident in (a), (b), (c) and (e) variables in table 28 confirm a negative attitude. Indeed, rather than talk of language maintenance here, as things are, we should be talking right now of language shift and language endangerment.

In conclusion, Erúshú people can really be described as ethnocentric. That is, these are bilingual people who are attached to their ethnic group and its cultural heritage even though they speak the out-group language quite well. Incidentally, Erúshú people consider themselves attitudinally to be Yorùbá and this probably accounts for their hidden attitudes towards their real ethnic language which is Erúshú.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION OF MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE INVESTIGATION

5.0 Introduction

This chapter discusses the whole findings of this investigation. Important findings are highlighted here for detailed discussion. The different sub-headings already recognized in chapter four will still form the pattern of the present discourse.

The preceding chapter investigates the social aggregates that characterized the use by all of our respondents of two or more languages in the linguistic repertoire of Erùshù community. In this chapter, the key issues that will engage our attention begin with the demographic data.

5.1 Demographic Data

Of the different demographic variables explored in this investigation, the ones worthy of comment in the present context are age and education since they are the variables that present an appreciable influence on bilingualism in this community.

As evident in tables (9a) and (9b), bilingualism in the present study is widespread among the older respondents just as it is among the younger ones. However, we discovered a superior degree of Erùshù – Yorùbá bilingualism among the adults in this settlement as compared with their younger counterparts (10-20 age group) who were only fairly competent in Erùshù. This can only be explained in terms of the status of the second language (Yorùbá) vis-a-vis socio economic and educational upliftment.

The older people, however, have greater facility in using Erùshù than the younger ones so much so that the former's pattern of bilingualism can be described as Erùshù-Yoruba bilingualism while the latter group has a pattern of Yorùbá-English bilingualism. The Yorùbá-English pattern discovered among the youths can

only be explained in terms of the socio-economic advantages involved. This shift from endoglossic to semi-exoglossic type of bilingualism has to do with the socio-economic advantages which the knowledge of Yorùbà and English confers on the younger users. Moreover, this divergence in patterns of bilingualism between the young and the old may be due to the fact that the older people are not easily influenced by modernization. This finding has also been accounted for by earlier studies. For instance, Eckert (1997: 152) opines that community studies of variation frequently show that increasing age correlates with increasing conservations in speech. Thus, in this environment, English-Yoruba bilingualism depicts 'modernisation' or the 'new norm' whereas Erùshù-Yorùbá bilingualism represents the 'old norm'. The study therefore suggests the possibility that current age differences represent a continuation of an ongoing change process (cf. Eckert, 1980; Kemp and Yaeger-Dror, 1991; Fakuade, 2001).

The present analysis which reveals that age is a sociolinguistic variable, no doubt, has once again confirmed earlier studies (see Wardhaugh, 1992, Nsawir, 1999).

Now we present instances similar to the Erùshù case within and outside the country. Fakuade (1998) reported a similar situation in his work among the Ichen people in Wukari and Takum Local Government Areas of Taraba state. According to him, although the Ichen people are a different ethnic group from the Jukun, the Jukun language has spread among other ethnic groups in the North-Eastern Nigeria to include the Ichen group to the extent that only 17.1% of this population now speak their language, Ichen.

A similar study was (see Demos, 1988) conducted on the Greek-Americans. This study reveals that in spite of the fact that attitudes towards the retention of the Greek language are positive and Greek language proficiency is associated with Greek ethnic identification, maintenance of the Greek language is progressively weakened from generation to generation.

In the study of the Punjabi Sikh community in Malaysia, David *et al* (2003) reported a great difference in the language choices of younger and older community members. The younger community members just as in Erùshù, showed low

proficiency in the ethnic language. In other words, the respondents' abilities in Punjabi increase with age.

In the present study, education has also influenced second language acquisition. The ANOVA test together with its Post-Hoc analysis on table 15 revealed that the respondents with secondary or post-secondary education reported having greater facility in Yorùbá than the uneducated ones. That proficiency in Yorùbá is related to the level of education of subjects is quite normal in view of the fact that Yorùbá is a subject on the school curriculum in our schools. Thus, a subject in possession of a degree in Yorùbá for example is expected to display ability in all the four skills of Yorùbá unlike a subject with little or no formal education.

Our findings here have once again affirmed the general theoretical postulations on the role of education in bilingual language acquisition. In consonance with previous research work (Hoffman 1994, 2000; David et al 2003) in this area, the present study has revealed that education exerts an influence on the second language such that the educated (young or old) group exhibited a superior knowledge of Yorùbá in relation to the uneducated group just because Yorùbá is one of the languages used in education in Nigerian schools. Yoruba is used as a medium of instruction in early Primary Education at least in the Western part of the country. Yoruba is also a school subject at all levels of education in the country.

For instance, David and Naji (2000) showed in their study of Malaysian Tamil that Tamil is the dominant (i.e. most often used daily) language for most of the older-age respondents but more than a quarter respondents used a mix of English, Tamil and Malay. More importantly, according to them, half of the middle-age respondents had English as their dominant language. The difference was attributed to the fact that this middle age group had had English as the medium of instruction. They concluded that language shift is slowly but surely taking place in favour of either English or a mix of three languages, especially for the middle age group.

Similarly, David et al (2003) reported that among Punjabi Sikhs, the level of education is found to be an indicator of language shift. They discovered that there was an association between home language use and the level of education.

Indeed, Erúshù youths can boast of possessing more formal education than their parents (adults). This has resulted into Yorùbá-English bilingualism for the youths as opposed to the Erúshù-Yorùbá pattern available for the parents (adults). This, again, has implications for language shift in favour of Yorùbá or a mix of Yorùbá and English for the youths.

However, the present study indicates that Erúshù-Yorùbá bilingualism is still a prevalent feature in this community. In spite of this, however, the step towards language loss or death has already been taken by members of this community. More alarming, (that is, despite the fact that Erúshù -Yoruba bilingualism is still in force here), is the fact that the youths do not feel they are losing anything. This community erroneously believes, ethnically speaking, that the two languages belong to the same ethnic group which of course, is Yoruba. This simply signifies that this community is being culturally misplaced. In effect, loss of culture is equally leading now to loss of language.

Finally, that only a small number of Erúshù youths can now use their mother tongues perfectly well has implications for language shift and language maintenance. Based on the findings in our data, Erúshù community is already exposed to the risk of language shift and language loss with these youths gradually shifting away from the use of their mother tongue. A broader picture will finally emerge by the time we discuss language use in various domains.

5.2 Bilingualism and Bilinguality

Bilingualism has been variously defined in the literature leaving us with a polarity of typologies. It is noteworthy that whatever measure of bilingual proficiency is employed for our data, the respondents in Erúshù community are well qualified to be called true bilinguals.

However, our experience with this investigation having employed two methods of measuring bilingualism here, the questionnaire and participant observation methods make us to accept the fact that balanced bilinguals, (that is, ambilinguals), are the exceptions rather than the rule in bi/multilingual settings. Statistical results in this context reveal that our respondents, in spite of the fact that

that they learned the two languages at home, differ significantly in their first and second languages in terms of the age of the respondents (i.e youths). The results show that they are more proficient in their second language than their very first language or mother tongue.

Thus, this finding which corroborates past findings raises questions on the conception of bilingualism as native-like control of two languages (see Bloomfield, 1933).

The present analysis holds implications for all uninvestigated cases of endoglossic bilingualism. Indeed, ambilingualism or true bilingualism seems to be naturally unobtainable under exoglossic bilingualism because of phenomenon of language interference. But then, why is it not easily obtainable too even in an endoglossic situation. To assume, without considering the factor of motivation, that learning two indigenous languages in a natural setting like this will present no difficulty to the learner unlike when the learner is learning a foreign language, in addition to the mother tongue, may turn out to be a misguided opinion. Hence, this result has thrown more light on the concept of motivation in second language learning. What is more? It has also broadened our understanding of how best to define bilingualism.

Just as others have observed in their studies, we equally observe here that an insistence on ambilingual standard would have disallowed us to reckon with very many of our respondents as bilinguals. No wonder, Fishman (1971:560) asserts that sociolinguistically speaking "any society that produces functionally balanced bilinguals (that is, bilinguals who use both their languages equally and equally well in all contexts) must soon cease to be bilingual because no society needs two languages for one and the same set of functions". Our present findings prove this to be just very correct. For instance, it is clear in this study that Erùshù, the ethnic language is still dominant in the home, hence its survival thus far, but not outside the home.

Indeed, it is evident in the data that the two languages are not used by speakers in this community in all contexts. Erùshù is restricted solely to the home domain. Yoruba has become the general language which means it is the language

most widely used at all times and in most situations including the home. Thus, the two languages are only kept functionally distinct partially, a situation which has been described in the literature as bilingualism without diglossia (Fishman 1971). Bilingualism without diglossia is often considered to be less stable than bilingualism with diglossia.

In conclusion, language use has to vary in order to make research efforts on bilingualism worthwhile. For instance, Fakuade (1999:77) maintains that "there is a correlation between the nature of shift and type of bilingualism such that partial shift and stable bilingualism go together, while complete shift and transitional bilingualism show a marked correlation." He states further that the implication of this correlation is that after a period of stable bilingualism, the minority language group will become assimilated by the dominant language group. Moreover, the number of functional domains of minority language will decrease rapidly like the case being investigated here. Hence there will be transitional bilingualism which will eventually give way to monolingualism. In other words, the present language contact situation, which is a 'healthy' one, has resulted into partial shift from Erúshú to Yoruba. Eventually, based on the trend of events in this analysis, the weaker group (Erúshú) will drop its language and adopt the language of the stronger group-monolingualism via transitional bilingualism (cf. Fakuade 1999). Bilingualism in Erúshú community is presently at this stage of transitional bilingualism.

5.2.1 Bilingual Proficiency

As stated already in the preceding section here, a polarity already exists in the pattern of bilingual proficiency in this community between the young (those under 30 years in particular) and the older group (those who are 30 years and above). As evident in tables 14a and 14b, younger people have greater facility in using Yorùbá and English than older people. Just as the older people have greater facility in using Erúshú and Yorùbá than younger people.

Indeed, Yoruba seems to be spoken more by the youths than the adults. Most children (who are, of course, students in Nursery/Primary schools in the neighbouring towns) use Yorùbá and English actively, but Erúshú passively. It needs be stated here

that "Accord photos" one of my informants, tested this position openly by speaking Erúshú to a 10year old boy in my presence only for the boy to reply him unconsciously, of course, in Yoruba. Thus, while the youths tend towards Yoruba-English bilingualism, just because of their degree of proficiency in the two, the adults maintain Erúshú -Yoruba bilingualism. This situation is comparable with David et al's (2003) discovery when they investigated language choice and the dominant language of the Punjabi Sikh community in Petaling Jaya in the home and religious domains and with different interlocutors. The findings show that Malaysia is moving toward a mixed discourse of three languages – English, Malay and Punjabi. The ethnic language tends to take a minority role in this mixed discourse. And what is more? The younger members of the Punjabi Sikh community in petaling Jaya tend to gravitate toward English, and English has become the dominant language in this mixed discourse of code mixing, code switching, and code shifting. According to them, English has at times become a stand-alone language (while this is not so with Malay) for many younger community members, despite the fact that Malay is the national language.

The present polarity in bilingual proficiency in Erúshú community can however be accounted for in terms of disparity in the status of the three languages in contact in this community. English is an international language by all standards, while Yoruba is a national language, and Erúshú is a local one. The present result is consistent with the popular view (see Coulmas 2004) which is that the degree of bilingual proficiency is proportional to bilingual usage.

5.2.2 Gender and Bilingual Proficiency

The influence of sex on proficiency in the two languages was presented in tables 13a and 13b. In the case of Erúshú, the table value is greater than the t-calculated, hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 level of significance. This position is also true of Yoruba. This implies that there is no correlation between sex and bilingual proficiency in this community.

This result is at variance with some popular works in this field. For instance, David and Najl (2000) discovered in their study of the Malaysian Tamil community

that more men (66.7%) than women (33.3%) use Tamil in the home domain, and the women tend to use English or a mix of languages. In addition, more males (52%) than females (48%) tend to use Tamil with their spouse. Thus, the commonest view in this context in literature is for younger generation and females (cf, Naji and David, 2003) to have the tendency to shift from mother tongue to the second language; [see studies by Milroy in Belfast (1982) Gal in Oberwart (1979), Ohara in Japan (1997), Ide and Yoshida in Japan (1999)]. According to Coulmas (2004:8) in a number of Asian languages such as Japanese and Korean, these distinctions (i.e. sex-specific and sex-preferential speech forms) are so pronounced as to form women's and men's languages.

In spite of the foregoing, Wodak and Benke (1997:126) observe that "studies of gender-specific variation are often contradictory, depending on the author's implicit assumptions about sex and gender, the methodology, the sample used, etc." We therefore conclude, bearing all factors in mind, that the true situation in Erúshú from our participant observation perspective is that there is no disparity in Erúshú between male and female proficiency with respect to these two languages, Erúshú and Yoruba. This may have resulted from the fact that both of them have equal access to the two languages under study. After all, the community under study is not unique or special in any way when compared with other communities with gender variation in language use.

Since women are expected to be language bearers and language transmitters (cf. Mukherjee 2003) the present lukewarm attitude of women in this community towards mother tongue suppression by a second language holds implication for language shift and maintenance. The result shows that the precarious situation of this community heritage language is left completely unrescued by the young and the women. With these two key positions weakened the survival of this mother tongue in the nearest future is very doubtful.

5.2.3 Age and Bilingual Proficiency

Age is another variable which influences bilingual proficiency in Erúshú community. Our finding here presented as tables 14a and 14b shows that bilingual

proficiency in this community is evidently age-related. The result shows that although in the home domain the majority of the respondents across all age groups often use Erúshú, more of the younger respondents have shifted away from the use of their ethnic language. The younger generation who are under 30 years of age no longer have in their mother tongue that kind of proficiency found in their parents. In the light of this development whereby the respondents' use of Erúshú decreases with age language shift had thus commenced in this community. In other words, there is a language shift among the adolescents in favour of Yoruba or a mix of Yoruba and English.

Our finding here is in consonance with studies in societal bilingualism that purport that bilingualism in the second language is age-related and that the younger community members play the role of shift agent and are catalysts of community language use (see Gal, 1979; Lieberman, 1981; Fasold, 1984; Labov, 1984; Fowler, 1986; Trudgill, 1988; Demos 1988; Fakuade 1998; David and Naji 2000; David et al, 2003; Oyetade, 2004; Dada, 2004; Columas 2004 among others). However, the present result is at variance with Oyetade (1990). In this study of Saare/Tsaragi community in Nigeria, subjects did not vary significantly in their abilities in the second language in spite of the varying degrees of proficiency of different age groups.

We also discover that the older members in Erúshú community are increasingly using more Yoruba with the younger ones, that is, they are accommodating toward the younger members, a finding that parallels that of David's (1996) work on the Sindhi community. This result also corroborates, Trudgill's (1986:39) position which states that "in face-to-face interaction... speakers accommodate to each other linguistically by reducing the dissimilarities between their speech patterns and adopting features from each other's speech."

Notice however that the present situation under study is such in which the two languages under study are learnt at home informally by our respondents and that probably has made the younger generations to have a level of proficiency in the second language which is not radically different from that of the older generation.

Moreover, the partial mother tongue maintenance still found in this community stems from the kind of language loyalty found among the adults.

5.2.4 Education and Bilingual Proficiency

Our statistical result on the influence of education on bilingualism in this community reveals that the degree of our subjects' proficiency in Yoruba, their second language, often varies with education. That the educated group exhibited a superior degree of bilingualism over the other groups should not be a surprise since the target language here is also the language of education at least in the primary schools. Thus, anybody who has acquired any level of education in cases like this is usually more proficient in the language than those who have not (cf, Hoffmann 1994). Education gives competence especially in writing and reading skills, which in turn can be regarded as additions to the normal speaking, and listening skills common to every user of a language.

Our finding here seems to affirm general theoretical postulation on the role of education in bilingual acquisition. For instance, David et al (2003) reported on how education in the Punjabi Sikh community affects (negatively) ethnic language such that there is an association between home language use and the level of education. Invariably, according to them (cf Gal, 1979), the use of English (with spouse and children) is found to be associated with higher education, while the use of ethnic language (Punjabi) is associated with lower education.

Our data are in part supportive of the argument that educational attainment is a vehicle of social and geographical mobility and that good education is particularly likely to encourage the development of critical values incompatible with the maintenance of traditional forces such as ethnicity (Alba and Chamlin 1983). It needs be stated, however, that this is not a positive development especially in this rural community

5.2.5 Occupation and Bilingual Proficiency

Occupation, no doubt, is another factor that can influence bilingual proficiency. With respect to our data in Erùshù community occupation has no significant influence on the proficiency of our respondents in the second language. Indeed, the F table value which is 3.21 is greater than the F calculated which is 0.885. This implies that there is no significant difference in subjects' bilingual proficiency as a result of their occupation. This is true, even by participant observation method, since all the participants make good use of the second language, Yoruba, in their day to day activities without inhibition from any quarters.

Indeed, Yoruba is the out-group language in this community. This explains its equal mastery by every professional group in the community. To be deficient in Yoruba within Erùshù community is to be cut off from the larger group and the mainstream of socioeconomic import. Thus, to forestall this, every occupational group makes the required effort to have improved proficiency in Yorùbá. For instance, Harrison and Piete's (1980) cited in Cheng (2003) research on factors that determine language choice of bilinguals in Welsh-English mothers shows that children are linguistically what their mother intends them to be. However, a mother's decision of language choice depends on socio economic considerations. Similarly, Lewis (1982), Wardhaugh (1987), Fakuade (1998) among others have proved the place of economic factor in second language acquisition.

Since no professional group reports a higher proficiency in Yorùbá than the other groups, the popular view that language choice depends on socioeconomic considerations seems to hold sway here. Indeed, each profession in this community seems to be aware of the fact that their economic mobility is determined by their ability in Yorùbá language. Yorùbá as a trade language is a 'sine qua non' in Erùshù or in Akoko or even in the whole of Ondo state in general. It is therefore not surprising to discover that no group lacked a good knowledge of it just in their bid to be economically relevant.

5.2.6 Place of Acquisition and Bilingual Proficiency

The result of our statistical test reveals that respondents do not vary in their proficiency in the second language as far as place of acquisition is concerned. This is contrary to our working assumption that certain places of acquisition of these languages would necessarily facilitate their learning better than some other places.

By implication, language use at home in this community must be both Erúshú and Yoruba. We cannot, however, say this for now with full force until we have examined language use in the various domains.

5.2.7 Code-Switching and Bilingual Proficiency

In Erúshú community, language alternation is a common occurrence. This linguistic phenomenon re-affirms the claim that code-mixing and code-switching are inevitable phenomena in bilingual or multilingual society (Scotton 1979, Gambli 1983, Ahukanna 1990, Essien 1995, Banjo 1996, Lamidi 2003, David et al, 2003, Fakuade et al 2003, Oyetade 2004). However, this result is at variance with Fakuade (1997) where code -mixing between Mbula and Bachama, in Adamawa state, Nigeria was highly resisted. According to his report code-mixing was viewed also as a possible indicator of the social relationship between language, and hence, of language attitude. Moreover, only 13% of Mbula respondents do code-switch between Mbula and Bachama which was seen as indicative of a negative attitude towards Bachama.

Code-switching has implications for language use and language maintenance. The attendant effect of this is that the diglossic situation as advanced by Ferguson (1959, 1966) does not exist in Erúshú community in spite of the linguistic pluralism existing here. That is, as mentioned earlier on, the roles of Yoruba language and the Erúshú language have not been kept functionally apart. If in the home front where the mother tongue is expected to have an edge over any other language in the community, Yoruba is holding sway, it therefore, means that both the Erúshú language and Yoruba language did not have any distinctive or opposing role as both were used for similar roles. Again, code-switching and code-mixing as being practised in this community is an indication of the fact that our respondents are not

practised in this community is an indication of the fact that our respondents are not ambilinguals, hence, they find it difficult to keep apart their two languages in all situations.

5.3 Language Use

This section discusses our findings on language use in specific domains with a view to relating them to findings in other works.

5.3.1 Home

Tables (18) and (19), which present our analysis of language use in the home domain in the community, revealed that Yoruba is mostly used among the adults as well as the youths. Indeed, Erúshú or Erúshú + Yoruba, takes after Yoruba as far as language use at home is concerned in this community. However, it is interesting to note that Erúshú still maintains a lead (34.6 percent as opposed to 31.5 percent for Yorùbá) in the context of parents talking to their children at home. Again, among the youths, Erúshú also maintains a lead (58.8 percent as opposed to 34.1 percent for Yoruba) in the context of children talking to their grandparents. Thus, by and large, language shift at home is still fairly limited. Erúshú is a home language based on our data although this position is being keenly contested for by Yoruba.

This result resembles some earlier ones on societal bilingualism with reference to language use in important domains (cf. David and Naji 2000, Govindasamy 2003, Oyetade 2004). It re-affirms Dorian's (1981:105) assertion that the "home is the last bastion of a subordinate language in competition with a dominant language of wider currency." Again David, et al (2003:21) maintains that both the home and religious domains have often been cited to be the last bastion of ethnic language use.

5.3.2 Official Work

It is surprising to note that among the adults, Yoruba is still the main language of communication even during official hours at work. Although for the students, English has a comfortable lead (65.1 percent as opposed to 26.7 percent for Yorùbá) here over Yoruba. However, we perceive that the youths have only

responded in the direction of social acceptability. By participant observation, it is obvious that Yorùbá is still the major code for holding discussions in the schools.

The kind of patterning we have here with regard to language use in the community simply reveals the kind of rural location within which the study is pitched. The locality has given Yoruba ascendancy over the official language, English, even in official domain. This again, is an assertion of Yoruba over other languages in this community. By implication, Yoruba has successfully made incursions into the most sacrosanct domain (home) for the mother tongue. Similarly, David et al (2003) reported on how English (a second language) has successfully displaced Malay in Malaysia, the national language either at home or outside home among respondents across all age groups.

The present analysis reveals the fact that societal bilingualism in Erúshú community is gradually being drawn into a monolingual one. The analysis foretells in no uncertain terms mother tongue's approaching doom in Erúshú community. We now know beyond any doubts that within this century the Erúshú community heritage language would be gone completely.

5.3.3 General Observation on Language Use in the Community

The type of bilingualism we are reporting on here is transitional bilingualism. In contrast to the language maintenance at home, Erúshú is rarely used outside the home (cf. Naji and David, 2003). The majority of the respondents across all ages and genders reported that they use either Yoruba or English or a mixture of these two when not at home. Thus it is clear that there is a real shift outside the home from the ethnic language in favour of either Yoruba or a mix of Yoruba and English.

Indeed, the pattern of language use in Erúshú community can only be captured by the term "triglossia". A typical triglossic situation (cf. Abdulazizi-Mkilifi, 1972) would be found where there exists side by side:

- a. A local language with the basic role of intra-group communication;
- b. A standardized regional *lingua franca* which is used extensively in the educational system, mass media and in government administration but

which is not developed enough to cover all settings of a modern urban technological culture, and

c. A world language.

The implication of a triglossia in the case of Erúshù is that for those who speak Erúshù, Yoruba and English, each of these languages has its domains of use. For instance, Erúshù language serves only for communication within ethnic group and it is rarely or never learned by speakers of other languages. Since this is a multilingual context its function may even be reduced to the family. This native tongue, Erúshù, is usually the language of intimacy, (i.e. of the home and close friends in informal situations). When people do not speak the same language, then Yoruba takes over the functions of the mother tongue.

Thus, Yoruba, another ethnic language in this community serves two functions: the in group function, but it is also used as lingua franca to communicate with members of other 'ethnic' groups in that these people only understand Yoruba. Indeed, for this group, Yoruba is the language of regional public life: political rallies, post office, transport, banking, schools, church, etc. And the language of specialized communication is English language (cf. Nida and Wonderly, 1971).

By specialized communication, we mean domains such as higher education, Parliament, High court, and the court of Appeal, diplomacy, foreign trade and any other public functions in multilingual situations where neither Erúshù, the local mother tongue nor Yoruba, a regional language, is considered to be adequate or appropriate.

Accordingly, for full participation in social interaction at all levels to be possible within and outside Erúshù community the three languages discussed must be learned and used based on their functions

This pattern, however, is changing. The trend is that many domains where Erúshù was once used exclusively are now being taken over by Yorùbá. For instance, in the past in this community, language interaction between siblings, parents, relatives and friends (the informal domain) used to be Erúshù, the native language. It is pertinent to note that the information gathered with the questionnaire

reflected that this is true in the speech of the adults who are slightly above 30 years. However for the youths who are under twenty years, the language of informal domain is now Yoruba. While adults agree that they communicate always at home in either Erùshù or Erùshù and Yoruba, the youths communicate at home always in Yoruba.

Indeed, this behavior is an unconscious one in the life of the youths. I reiterate again that at a particular point in the course of my gathering this data, my research assistant, popularly known as Accord photos had to demonstrate to me that the teenagers no longer use actively their mother tongue. He demonstrated this by calling a kid of about 10 years old and said to him "Baba ni siri?", which when translated means "where is your father?" The kid unconsciously replied him in Yorùbá. Thus proving the point that youths no longer speak Erùshù at home even when communicated to in the language. This phenomenon called reciprocal and non-reciprocal code-switching by Elthereda (1999) was noted by her among the Cameroonians. She reported that language shift by one of the interlocutors did not always call for a corresponding shift by the other interlocutor. And that effective communication could take place between bi/multilinguals without distorting the piece of discourse with each maintaining his language. The implication this has for the ethnic language is now very clear.

It follows that while the pattern of the informal language use in this community for adults is Erùshù and Yoruba, that of the youths is Yoruba.

5.4 Language and Inter-Ethnic Relations.

Language is a special mark of distinction which spells out the uniqueness of a community and thereby gives it a sense of pride. Indeed, language is an integral part of culture, a reflection of many features of a given culture. Thus, like culture itself, it is a learned behaviour, which can be enhanced through direct or indirect contact.

For instance, Fakuade's (1996) examination of a reported case of language conflict involving the Bachama and the Mbulla in Numan and Demsa Local Government Area of Adamawa State in Nigeria revealed that the language situation between these two contiguous communities is a case of language maintenance rather

than that of language conflict. This is simply because the Mbula people are of the view that their mother-tongue is the principal carrier of their culture and identity: they rely on it as the main defence mechanism against assimilation. The Polish, the Baltic and the Greek peoples can be regarded as other examples of such groups in Europe, as can the French in Quebec (McRae 1989:9). According to McRae, the survival of such language-centred cultures in a viable form is deemed by the group members to depend on the preservation of their mother tongue. He explains further that in these instances, the language is more than the medium of communication and self-expression.

Another study that confirms language as an aspect of ethnic and cultural distinctiveness is that of Naji and David (2003). Their study of markers of ethnic identity in Malaysian Tamil community revealed that once members of a community feel that their ethnic language is threatened they would resort to other markers of ethnic identity like clothing, food, celebration of religious and cultural festivals, etc.

Thus, our probe into language and inter-ethnic attitudes among our respondents reveals that our respondents are positively disposed towards ability in their two languages. It is however surprising to see this community recognizing both language as the language of their progenitors, although they know that Erùshù is their exclusive possession through which the community can be uniquely identified (cf. Awobuluyi 1991, Fakuade 1995, 1997). This kind of 'double identity' with respect to their languages was reported by Hesbacher and Fishman (1965) among Polish and Yiddish speaking immigrants in Pennsylvania. Oyetade's (2005) report on incipient language shift in Auga, Akoko in Nigeria is another good example.

The Polish and Yiddish expressed this positive attitude according to Hesbacher and Fishman for affective reasons whereas in our own case, the Erùshù people tend to be guided by instrumental motivation such as "Erùshù is indispensable to our existence here" or "it enables me to interact freely with the Erùshù speaker", etc.

For instance, respondents' self-report on ethnic identity shows that they are in favour of Yorùba as their ethnic language. When asked: 'I need to speak Erùshù to express my ethnic identity, 11.0 percent picked (strongly) agree while 88.7 picked

(strongly) disagree. To a statement such as "Yoruba is enough for me to express my ethnic identity, 61.4 percent picked (strongly) agree while 37.0 percent picked (strongly) disagree.

Thus, in line with the opinions of Hesbacher and Fishman (1965) and Oyetade (2005) we assert that the subjects display a "split commitment" to the two languages in their repertoire. Indeed, they see the Yoruba as a positive-reference group (cf. Akere 1982) and this is why Yoruba has gained ascendancy over the mother tongues among the youths. Hence, people have a pull between the mother tongue and the second language. Really, they know that the mother tongue symbolizes their ethnic identity, whereas the second language, Yoruba, is the only language that is useful for inter-ethnic interactions. This kind of split commitment according to Grosjean (1982) is usually the case in bilingual communities.

As evident in their responses to the questions on language attitude and ethnic identity, the Erúshú people are only superficially committed to the survival of their language. Indeed, the pride, loyalty and commitment being demanded in a situation like this are no longer evident. Incidentally, Erúshú people consider themselves attitudinally to be Yoruba and this probably accounts for the type of inner attitude they have towards their ethnic language Erúshú.

Furthermore, the dichotomy normally made between integrative and instrumental reasons (Gardner and Lambert, 1972; Akeredolu-Ale 2000; Nercissians, 2001) for learning the second language seems to be irrelevant here because these people are oblivious of their past. They are not conscious of being part of any other ethnic group (now or in the past) apart from the Yoruba race. Hence, the responses got in this data cannot depict the actual figure expected in a real bilingual-bicultural situation (cf. Oyetade 1990, 1995, 1996) since they do not really feel any different from the Yorubas.¹ If the present analysis is taken alongside those ones on language use and bilingual proficiency, then our analysis shows that bilingualism in Erúshú community is anything but stable.²

Notes

1. This assertion is true of every town/village in Akoko community in spite of the fact that they all use different languages in addition to Yoruba.
2. Stable bilingualism is an established bilingualism where the second language is already adopted in addition to the first language. Moreover, in stable bilingualism, the two languages are kept functionally apart.

CHAPTER SIX

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.0 Introduction

This chapter attempts an overview of the present study by presenting a summary of the major findings of the investigation and subsequently presenting a conclusion on them. The final part provides a number of recommendations based on the theoretical and pragmatic import of our findings.

6.1 Summary of Findings

6.1.1 Bilingualism in Erúshú community

The analysis of our data on the demography of subjects reveals a fairly uniformed pattern with the exception of two variables. For instance, there was no significant difference in the levels of bilingualism of male and female subjects. Indeed, of all the relevant demographic factors examined in this study such as sex, age, educational attainment, occupation and place of acquisition of the second language, only age and education have influence on the degree of bilingualism and language use among our respondents. The influence of age and education on language use of our respondents becomes obvious as we discuss presently, the language use pattern in Erúshú community.

6.1.2 Domains of Language Use in Erúshú

In chapter four of this study the general direction of language shift in the study area (i.e. towards Yoruba), was very evident. More alarming, however, is the dominance of Yorùbá in virtually all the different domains to the extent that its use is a *sine qua non* to the survival of individuals in the community, thus revealing the position of endoglossic bilingualism in the community of study.

A description of the distribution of languages over specific domains of social behaviour can be discussed along two clusters of domains viz primary and

secondary domains. The primary domain cluster has to do with everyday activities involving the family, kinship, friendship, local markets, work, traditional social institutions (village council, age groups, etc). Thus, the primary domain represents all the basic social functions of language in society. The secondary domain (which refers to advanced areas of social life which are the result of the development of statehood in the modern sense) includes the following: administration, political institutions, education, modern mass media, the legal apparatus, and so on (cf. Mansour 1980, Dirvin 1991, Elthereda 1999).

In this analysis, it is discovered that even in the primary domain where language use evolves naturally in response to the needs of the community, Erúshú has recorded a loss. The only area left for Erúshú of these clusters within the primary domain is that of the family or home domain. In fact, Yorùbá has almost taken over this area too and it is, ironically speaking, the only domain left for the Erushu language. This 'restricted usage' of Erúshú is an indicator of the present plight of the community's heritage language, a fate common to all small-population languages in Nigeria and in many other parts of Africa and the world at large. Thus, Erúshú, a language without an orthography has again been confined in its oral use to a particular social domain, the home.

Directly related to the loss of domains for the Erúshú language is that children have insufficient exposure to the language to achieve good proficiency in it. The adolescents' rejection of the use of Erúshú may be due to the fact that they perceive no significant contexts in which the language is necessary and appropriate.

On the other hand, Yorùbá features in virtually all the domains (primary and secondary) listed above no matter how minimal. The foregoing probably explains why the population of those speaking Erúshú is declining in favour of Yorùbá, the big fish swallowing up all the smaller fish in its environs.

Our investigation reveals that language use in this community, which in turn affects proficiency in each of these languages, is dependent on the respondents' age and education. On proficiency in Erúshú, the older the better; whereas Yorùbá proficiency is slightly influenced by education such that the literate group speaks (and even write) Yorùbá fluently more than the illiterate group. In addition, language use

in Nigeria in general, and Erúshú community in particular, is also dependent on such variables as the mode of discourse, audience, context and the topic. Written communication-letter writing, literature, journalism, etc- for instance is done in either English or Yoruba. Again, the issue of technical vocabulary requires that English be used in health centres, the law court, and in the schools. We notice however, that English is rarely used in the contexts of family domain and traditional religious practices. The three major languages in use in Erúshú, as stated already are: Erúshú, Yorùbá and English. Our findings reveal the fact that our respondents speak both Erúshú and Yoruba. In addition to these two languages, the educated ones can speak English. Thus, while people with little or no education in this community are bilingual with a knowledge of Erúshú and Yorùbá, an educated indigene, however, is trilingual with a knowledge of Erúshú, Yorùbá and English.

In chapter four, we presented how the variables: age, sex, education, occupation and place of acquisition, are related to proficiency, language choice and dominant language in the lives of members of this community.

The attendant effect of languages in contact within this community manifests as follows:

1. The more literate a person is, the more likely he is to be a fluent speaker of English or Yoruba at the expense of his mother tongue.
2. As evident in the data, younger people have greater facility in using Yoruba than older people.
3. Older people, however, have greater facility in using Erúshú than younger people.
4. Yoruba tends to be spoken more in educated homes than in illiterate homes. Indeed, most children born in well educated homes use Yoruba and English actively, but Erúshú passively. Incidentally, Yorùbá and English are languages of education as well as languages of upward mobility.

5. The use of pidgin, a linguistic product of multilingualism, within the Erúshú community is not widespread because the Erúshú community is ethnically homogenous. Many Erúshú people use either Erúshú or Yoruba.

In conclusion, the choice of language in the different domains in Erúshú community has revealed very interesting facts about the linguistic situation in this community in particular and in Nigeria in general.

Our findings support the general consensus among sociolinguists:

1. That language choice is determined by the domains of social behaviour (family, neighbourhood, work, etc.) and that we can distinguish between three major functions of communication: In-group communication, out-group communication and specialized communication. Yorubá, is however, used along with Erúshú for in-group communication. For out-group communication, Yorubá is in use and English is the language used for specialized communication.
2. That the dominant language for the youths in the community varies from that of the adult. While the youths have Yoruba as their dominant language, the adults still retain their mother tongue which is Erúshú.
3. That a natural corollary from (2) is that the youths are gradually shifting away from Erúshú to Yoruba. An attitude that has serious implications for the survival of Erúshú, the mother tongue of these youths.
4. That the importance of English language to different races and its official status in Nigeria has again been revealed by this study. This in fact, partly explains why the youths abandoned their mother tongue but have embraced the English language consequently resulting in the triglossic pattern of language use in this community.

- 5 That the probable trend of events in the nearest future should be our greatest concern. It would be interesting to see how the picture presented here will have changed say, in fifty years from now. That is, by the time the community is blessed with a number of nursery/ primary schools.

Based on the data in this study, to predict the trend of language use in Erushu in the nearest future may not be too difficult. There is a possibility that Yoruba will gradually acquire more official functions with the Federal Government's active support of the major languages of the country cum the rate of development in Yorubá. At the same time, Erúshú is also likely to give way completely to Yoruba as the latter becomes more entrenched into the socio-cultural fabric of this community, taking into cognizance the national status of Yoruba and the attitudes of the female and the younger generation to their mother tongue.

For more illumination, we present now summary of our findings on language attitude in this community.

6.1.3 Language Attitude in Erushu Community

The survival of a language in a multilingual community like ours depends on the true inward attitude of the owners towards the language (cf. Fakuade, 2001).

The main thrust of the present work is that language use in Erúshú community involves a choice between Erúshú, Yoruba and English. As far as the attitudes of our subjects on the two indigenous languages under investigation are concerned we conclude that the respondents exhibit a kind of split commitment to their two languages. We observe that the mother tongue, Erúshú, was positively regarded on emotional or sentimental grounds and the second language was mostly preferred for instrumental reasons.

The importance of attitudes in bilingualism as individual or society phenomenon must not be underestimated. It is for this reason that the unwholesome attitude (revealed in language use) of the Erúshú people towards their community heritage language leaves much to be desired. The foregoing is a clear indication that

attitudes are latent inferred from the direction and persistence of external behaviour. Thus, while the respondents here outwardly manifest a positive attitude for their mother tongue, Erúshú, any time the question posed to them is very potent and direct as in questions (d) (i.e. Yorúbá is a threat to Erúshú) and (g) (i.e. if care is not taken Yorúbá will completely replace Erúshú in future) of table 28. Their underlying attitude as manifested in language use is however different. Attitude is an inner resource, which translates into a potent force in matters of language survival and language maintenance. Indeed, the present language attitude of Erúshú people is not propitious for the survival of their language. The consistent patterns of behaviour as evident in (a, b, c, and e) variables of table 28 confirm a negative attitude.

In matters of attitude, the Erúshú community has displayed a kind of language loyalty towards their mother tongue when the result on table (27a) is compared with that of (27b). Although, they use the second language, Yoruba, more than their mother tongue. Thus, the supposedly positive attitude expressed by the Erúshú is external only. They have substituted the outward act for the correct inner attitudes which is however of a higher force. Moreover, since language attitude does not proceed from a mere external act only but from an all-embracing language attitude which is lacking here, we are bound to conclude from language use evidence that the language attitude toward the mother tongue in this community is negative. The split commitment evident in this self-report is not evident in language usage which is of paramount importance. In Conclusion, rather than talk of language maintenance here with the present analysis, we should rather be talking of language shift and language endangerment. From the pattern of language use and language attitude in Erúshú, as evident in the foregoing, we make the following observations:

1. There is a gradual demise of this community's heritage language, Erúshú, due to cultural assimilation and inferiority complex on the part of these bilingual speakers.

2. This disappearance is attributable to the 'gobbling' effect of Yorubá over the minority languages in the Western Region of Nigeria.
3. Most parents (especially mothers and elite) do not encourage the use of their mother-tongue any longer. Rather, they prefer to use the language of wider communication.
4. In addition, in this community, ethnolinguistic identity has been lost long ago, thus, they identify with a major ethnic group for several reasons.
5. Indeed, the transitional type of bilingualism exists in this community as a result of the factors listed above.

Jubril (1990) observes that the Yankan people, a small ethno-linguistic group in Plateau State of Nigeria, are negatively positioned against their mother-tongue in that those who are below 30 years of age could not speak the Yankan language. He states further that the inability of the younger ones to speak the Yankan language is due to the preference given to the Hausa language which is the lingua franca of the area.

Thus, the Erúshú people in comparison with the Yankan people have also shown evidence of language shift in individuals as well as in the community as a whole. Indeed, the only area of maintenance left for Erúshú language is that the elders are still careful to use this language at home.

The Erúshú experience in this context is similar in part to the Krenak's in South Eastern Brazil where only a handful of elders among the 70 or 80 tribesmen still speak their mother tongue. Originally a tribe of hunter-gatherers, the Krenak were expelled from their land and herded into reserves by government agents intent on making more space for farming. Up until the 1950s, Catholic Missionaries forbade them to perform rituals or speak their own language. The linguistic ban, combined with the tribe's expulsion from its traditional lands, devastated the oral transmission of tribal culture (Geary 1997:40). Yoruba too vis-a-vis Erúshú, has enjoyed institutional support (Giles et al. 1977) during the Regional Government in Nigeria and this has in part assisted its spread throughout the former Western

Region. Suffice it to say that the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1979,1999) which states that the business of the National Assembly shall be conducted in English and in Hausa, Ibo and Yorùbá and the National policy of Education (1981) that says the medium of instruction in pre-primary and early Primary Education will be the mother-tongue or the language of the immediate community actively encourage the use of Yoruba in various institutions in the country.

The present language use and language attitude in Erúshú might have resulted from the fact that it is a frontier zone where there is cross-current of contact between the Ekiti, Yagba, Ebira, and other Akoko sub-groups, who of course, speak different languages. Therefore, to get across linguistic barrier in this settlement, Yorùbá, a ready lingua franca, has been adopted. Hence, Yorùbá is not only necessary here for educational or economic advancement but also for spatial and social mobility.

Based on the foregoing and given that speakers of a weak language usually shift to a stronger language which is more influential, then, the stage is already set for language shift and language displacement in Erúshú community.

We conclude this section with Tandefelt's (1992) formula on the process of language endangerment¹ since it aptly captures the Erúshú language situation. The formula:

$$A > Ab > AB > aB > B$$

Language A, in the formula represents the minority language (i.e. the language dominated socially, politically, or numerically) and language B represents the majority language (the dominating language) in a multilingual society. Notice that the intervening variables Ab, AB, and aB between language A and B point to the processes involved in language shift. The process of initial second language learning

is Ab, which is followed by a period of bilingualism AB, then followed by almost total language shift aB. At point aB the minority language is endangered.

We observe that Erúshú is at present at the penultimate stage of this formula. Again, observe that all the factors already noted in literature (see Demons, 1988; Dimmendaal 1989; Garzon 1992, Fakuade, 1999, Fakuade *et al* 2003) as being responsible for language shift are very evident in Erúshú data already analysed here. Causes of language extinction include the following: see (Garzon 1992 (61-64) Fakuade 2004:12-22 for details) .

1. **An extended period of limited language contact culminating in a period of language shift:** Communities experience a substantial period of contact between speakers of the subordinate language and speakers of the dominant language. During this period the majority of the population is monolingual although some individuals may acquire proficiency in the dominant language. During the extended period there may be substantial borrowing from the dominant language by the subordinate one. This period of contact lasted over 300 years for some Indian languages (Garzon 1992-62), from the time of the Spanish conquest to the late nineteenth century. Dimmendaal (1989:22) cites the shift of the Elmolo-speaking people of Kenya to Sambure language use, over an eighty year period, as a case of rapid language change. Similarly the death of Mennonite German in Kansas took over one hundred years (Bucheit, 1988). In the case of Erúshú, lack of documented evidence on this community makes such an accurate record unavailable here. Even then, it is evident from oral sources that Erúshú and Yorúbá have been in contact now for over one hundred years. Thus, language death is usually seen as a long-term process.
2. **A Shrinkage of domains for the subordinate language:** The second step in the process of language loss takes place at the same time that an increasing number of people learn the dominant language as well as, or in place of, the subordinate one . The subordinate language experiences a

shrinkage of domains, usually withdrawing first from the public domain and finally disappearing from the home as well (Garzon 1992:63). While Erúshú was formerly used in a variety of public and private contexts within Erúshú, its use is now largely confined to private conversations at home among older Erúshú speakers.

3. **Use of Dominant language by parents with their children:** The third step in the language death process occurs when parents begin to speak the dominant language with their children to the exclusion of their own native language. Parents, shift along with their children since they are concerned about their children's ability to get along in the outside world. Therefore, they are afraid that the use of the Erúshú language will hinder the children's ability to learn Yoruba correctly and to do well in school (cf. Oyetade 2004).

In Erúshú those children who did not learn Erúshú from their parents were unlikely to ever learn the language. Although, this is not always the case in situations of language shift. In the early stages of language shift or in a situation of stable bilingualism, children may learn a subordinate language even if their parents choose not to speak it to them when they are small (Garzon 1992:63). Farber (1978:177) cited in Garzon (1992) describes how children in Comalapa, a Mayan community in Guatemala, continue to learn Kaqchikel even though their parents address them exclusively in Spanish at least until the time they enter school.

4. **The Language Policy of a State:** According to Fakuade (2004: 12) state policies, severally and combined in globalisation are behind the punishment of a child for speaking their language, state policies create the framework within which parents and children can choose from the choices that school language policies have offered to indigenous children and parents. He states further that educational language rights are not merely vital but the most important linguistic human rights for the maintenance of linguistic and

cultural diversity on our planet and the development of languages. And that, if children are not granted the opportunity to learn their parents' idiom fully and properly so that they become proficient as the parents, the language is not going to survive.

Cobarrubias (1983) on his part presents a taxonomy of policies which a state can adopt towards minority languages as presented in table 29 below:

Table 29: Taxonomy of State Policies Towards Minority Languages

i.	Attempting to kill a language
ii.	Letting a language die
iii.	Unsupported co-existence
iv.	Partial support of specific language functions
v.	Adoption as an official language

Source: Cobarrubias (1983: 71)

While commenting on the classification in table 29, Fakuade says that the first three policies, with few exceptions seem to lead to languages dying/being killed. And that when all children participate in formal education, only the last two policies seem to make a language potentially safe.

In the light of this background information above, the official language policy in Nigeria as contained in section 55 and 97 of the 1999 constitution as well as in the National Policy on Education (NPE) 1981 seems to be one in support of policy number (iii) in table 29. The policy simply translates into an unsupported co-existence for the minority languages since only Hausa, Igbo, Yorùbá and English have been accorded the status of national official languages. To Fakuade 2004:15 'whereas the policy clearly spells out functional roles for the three national languages in law-making and education, it appears somewhat reticent on the roles for the remaining 387 or so indigenous languages. Moreover, the policy puts all the indigenous languages at par in terms of their functional role in primary education when

the government in actual fact is not ready to develop these languages. What is more? Many of them are unwritten let alone be a useful medium of instruction in the primary schools.

Oyetade (2002:54) describes these policies as policies for policy's sake, in that they are not committal about implementation, which will make it possible for Hausa, Igbo and Yorùbá on the one hand, and the major languages of respective states on the other, to assume the role accorded them by the constitution. Suffice it to say that 'escape clauses' (cf. Bamgboṣe 1990) were deliberately built into them. Egbohare (2004) has simply described the national language policy as a mockery of planning.

This policy as evident in the foregoing has turned most Nigerian languages including Erúshù into what Fakuade (1989) calls bedroom languages. These minor languages are restricted completely to the family domain by the claims in the policy. We conclude this factor in line with Fakuade's (2004:16) submission that the provision of policy framework without official support, legal support or financial support amounts to folding of arms and letting the languages die off. Indeed, the rhetorical multilingualism (cf. Fakuade 2004) of the language policy has only resulted into the increasing domination of English with respect to the nation's indigenous languages either major or minor. Again, in agreement with Adegbija (1997:3) the present policy does not encourage the development of minority languages, resulting in gradual shifts to (regional) lingua francas, especially in areas that lack deliberate community effort to ensure survival and development of their languages.

5. **Failure by young people to gain proficiency in the subordinate language:**
The final step in the language-death process takes place when young people fail to learn the subordinate language. Directly related to the loss of domains for the language is that children will have insufficient exposure to the language to achieve fluency in it. The child may reject its use if he perceives no significant contexts in which the language is necessary and appropriate.

Moreover, a young person may also reject the ethnic identity the language represents. At this point (or even later), according to Garzon (1992:61), the language may still be revived if the language serves as a marker of ethnic identity. However, these conditions do not seem to apply to the Erúshú community and all such towns/villages in the Akoko region of Ondo State.

To this extent Erúshú is very much endangered. The Erúshú linguistic experience as presented here is a classic example of African languages under the threat of extinction. The Erúshú data presented here is just one of the several instances of endangered languages in Akoko, Ondo State (cf Awobuluyi, 1991; Fakuade, 1997; Oyetade, 2004). This is however a universal phenomenon. Instances of endangered languages either in Nigeria or the world at large abound in literature (see Dorian 1989; Buchheit 1988; Sridhar 1988 1990; Oyetade, 1995, 1996, 2002, 2004; Fakuade, 1995, 1999, 2001, 2003, 2004; Brenzinger, 1998; Emenanjo and Bleambo 1999; Yuka 2002; David et al. 2003; Cheng 2003 among others).

6.1 Implications of the Findings and Recommendations

6.2.1 Language Use

The present study sheds light on the linguistic situation in Nigeria in that the result of our data in Erúshú –Yoruba bilingualism is not limited either to Erúshú only or to Akokoland or to even Nigeria as a whole. From all indications, based on the present discovery in Erúshú, these minor indigenous languages are gradually fading out of existence giving way completely to the major indigenous languages in each of the regions in Nigeria.

Ironically, the very factor that led to the shrinkage in the domains of use of Erúshú also led to the spread of Yorúbá in the Western Nigeria. Factors that assisted the spread of Yorúbá in the Western Region include: colonization, urbanization, christianity and education. We observe as follows: "according to Fakuade (2004: 14) the official language policy in Nigeria tends to complement what was started during the colonial period". Lagos and Ibadan are major Yorúbá cities that accommodate thousands of other people of other tribes who get to speak and spread the language.

The Bible was translated into Yorùbá and became widely used in this part of the country. Educational factor has been discussed already in this work.

It is significant to note that in spite of Nigeria's linguistic pluralism, many Nigerians are actually bilingual in their native tongue plus the regional language in their domain. The implications of this is that thus far the three regional languages are still restricted to their regions. This has implication for the effectiveness of the national language policy which has been formulated for about three decades. Another implication of this result is that once the native tongue gets wiped off by the regional language, endoglossic bilingualism in such societies and within individuals turns to monolingualism. Once again, this has implications for the National Policy on Education (1972, 1981, 1998) (cf. Harris *et al.*, 2002) which stipulates that every child should learn one of the three major languages in addition to his/her own language. That is, if minority groups refuse to learn any major indigenous language outside its region, definitely the major language groups are obviously not learning any indigenous language in addition to theirs.

It is therefore our hope that language planners in Nigeria will take a cue from the linguistic situation in Erúshú community as exposed in this work so as to be able to evolve a workable national language for Nigeria. The nation's National language policy expressed in the 1979/1999 constitution is in support of Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba as co-official languages with English. The assumption is that one of them may emerge as the official language of the nation in future.

Based on the present picture of linguistic realities in Erúshú community, this assumption is not completely misplaced. Since Yorùbá has gradually displaced the indigenous languages of the western part of the country like Erúshú, then, it may not be unreasonable to expect Yoruba to still spread beyond its regional borders (cf. Fakuade 1998). After all, English language started somewhere before it conquered the whole world. Trade, education or even war, depending on the ambition of the Yorùbá may be used to effect this. Time will bear this out. What is more? This natural phenomenon which is already at work in the country, if left unchecked may give birth to an 'unopposed' national language (*lingua franca*).

On the other hand, the current scholarship on endangered languages embarked upon by linguists offers an example of the positive attitude that all Nigerian-linguists, relevant government agencies and language owners themselves should have as efforts are on to determine the extent and probable solutions to language endangerment in Nigeria. The current trend has to stop if only for the sake of Africa and its values. The zeal with which present day Nigerian linguists is espousing the cause of the endangered languages in Nigeria despite the fact that these are privately funded research programmes behoves the government of the day to rise up to the challenge of stabilizing this community heritage languages.

6.2.1 Code-Switching

In Erúshú community, CS as evident in our data is a common occurrence. This language use situation in Erúshú seems to corroborate the claim that code-mixing and code-switching are inevitable phenomena in a bilingual and multilingual society (see Gambhir (1983), Ahukanna (1990) Banjo (1983,1996) Myers-Scotton (1993a, 1999, 2004) Essien (1995) Myers-Scotton and Bolonyai (2001) Fakuade, et al (2003) and Lamidi (2003) just to mention a few.

However, this is not always the case in all bilingual communities. Fakuade (1997:45) in his study of the linguistic situation, between the Bachama and the Mbula in Numan and Demsa Local Government Area of Adamawa State of Nigeria describes how code-mixing and borrowing from Bachama are not frequent among the Mbula which is indicative of a negative attitude toward Bachama. Only 13% of Mbula respondents do code-switch between Mbula and Bachama. This situation is however an exception rather than the rule. Thus, that code-switching is 'unrestrained' between Erúshú and Yoruba is indicative of a positive attitude of the respondents towards Yoruba,

For now, we turn to a discussion of the implications of our findings on CS for the two languages. The question to be discussed presently is: what is the relationship between the influence which a first language has on a second language and that which a second language has on the first language in Erúshú community.

The present study holds linguistic as well as non-linguistic implications for the two languages under study since CS normally starts as interference (cf. Fakuade 1999). It therefore means by implication that the phonological, grammatical and lexical systems of both languages are gradually being weakened. The borrowed words which have now been integrated into the host language will carry the phonological, grammatical and lexical patterns of this host language. Moreover, Weinreich (1953) cited in Dittmar (1976:187) says "...loan words are mainly integrated into the system of a language at the point where the structure of the vocabulary is at its weakest". Thus, this phenomenon of CS will only continue to weaken the vocabulary of Erúshù and also result into a poor mastery of the two languages in contact because CS is an alternative way of communicating. After all, a code-switched variety of course is just as much language use (i.e. a code) as is the 'undiluted/ unmixed' variety.

From a non-linguistic angle, the culture as well as the language of this community is gradually being eroded. The study of code-switching in its socio-cultural context however reveals one major way in which the language and culture of a speech community can enrich and enhance the development of another, that is, if the borrowed items are viewed positively. This view is however very difficult to develop because once CS is left unchecked it may escalate to pidginization.

6.2.2 Interference and Contact Linguistics

The many products of languages coming into contact include bilingualism, language shift, loss and death, borrowing, pidgins and creoles, code-switching, linguistic interference, etc. Some of these phenomena have been discussed already in this study.

Andre Martinet in Weinreich (1953) cited in Lamidi (2003:1) states that "... a linguistic community is never homogenous and hardly ever self-contained" (p.viii). According to Lamidi "members of a speech community interact within the micro-community and also with members of the macro-community of their speech communities." Thus, apart from the regional variety of Yorùbá otherwise known as Standard Yoruba, there are also ethnic dialects of Yoruba used in Nigeria. This

approach (cf. Odumuh, 1987) can be regarded as ethno-linguistic influences in the study of variation in any language. These influences, according to Odumuh, affect all levels of linguistic analysis- phonological, lexical, semantic and syntactic.

Based on this premise, the type of Yorùbá spoken in Erúshú community differs at these four linguistic levels from the standard Yorùbá. In other words, it is no exaggeration to say that there are as many Yorùbá dialects in Western Nigeria as there are many ethnic languages and dialects in this area. This is because there are noticeable differences in Standard Yoruba usage in Western Nigeria resulting from influences of ethnic languages. Thus, what we have are Ekiti Standard, Igbomina Standard, Erúshú or even Akoko² Standard, Egba Standard, Ijebu Standard, Ijesa Standard, etc.

This research work observes ethnic language influence on Standard Yoruba, in that the numerous ethnic languages and dialects still continue to superimpose their phonology, lexis, and structure on the standard Yoruba to produce the various ethnic varieties of Yoruba. Indeed, the type of Yoruba spoken in Erúshú community or throughout Akokoland is noticeably different from the type(s) spoken in other parts of Yorubaland. This is the influence of Erúshú language on the Standard Yoruba. It follows, therefore, that we can identify several, dialects of Standard Yoruba such as Yorùbá- Èkiti, Yorùbá- Erúshú / Àkókó, Yorùbá- Ègbá, etc.

Yorùbá- Erúshú emanates from the influence of Erúshú language on Yorùbá. This influence results into accentual patterns which characterize the spoken Yorùbá of the Erúshú people. This influence may not affect the written Yoruba of Erúshú writers anyway. This linguistic interference essentially characterizes spoken Yoruba. We also observe that nobody will pick on the form of spoken Yoruba at Erúshú as the type to be used on the radio or TV or for a national programme on Yoruba as it is being done with the English 'RP'. Of special concern to us in this work is the influence of Yoruba and English on the Erúshú language which we had already discussed as code - switching. The dominance of Yoruba in the indigenous linguistic repertoire of Erúshú community made Yoruba to be borrowed into Erúshú language

as code-switched materials. Whereas in national and international discussions involving a mixed code, English takes over as the language of dominance.

The foregoing is an attestation to the fact that when two languages co-exist, they tend to influence each other in a number of noticeable ways. The Yoruba, just like the English language in Nigeria, has influenced Erúshú language and various ethnic languages, including Erúshú, which has also influenced its (Yoruba) use. The Erúshú influence on Standard Yoruba has been more prominently felt at the phonological level. This influence has resulted into a variety of Standard Yoruba, which we have identified here as Yorúbá- Erúshú, that is an Akoko-accented Yoruba. In fact, many Yoruba can identify an Akoko man based on the peculiarities of his speech.

6.3 Summary

The present study details the dynamics of language use and language alternation in a Nigerian community- Erúshú, Akoko, Ondo State. Our findings here positively attest to four sociolinguistic universals: (1) not all people in the same community speak the same linguistic varieties; (2) the linguistic varieties in use in any community are generally allocated to different situational uses; (3) all varieties are either positively or negatively evaluated by community members, according to their use in a specific type of interaction. (4) code-switching is the norm rather than the exception in bilingual communities. We conclude the study with our recommendations as presented in the next section while the last section is on areas for further research.

6.4 Recommendations

1. The present study brings to the fore the fact that the present National language policy does not encourage the development of minority languages such as Erúshú. It has only resulted into gradual shifts to regional lingua francas in Nigeria. Thus, we suggest a review of the national language policy with a view to officially institutionalize multilingualism in Nigeria. Indeed, where there is the will, a way can be found. According to Adegbiya (1997) in Papua New Guinea,

with its population of 3.5 million and about 869 languages, a basic and solid ideology already exists to develop all languages, the number of their speakers notwithstanding. Thus, Nigeria should have language policy which promotes the principle of linguistic human rights. The Nigerian government should set up agencies for minority language development and maintenance. Moreover, the campaign mounted up by the governments on bush burning and tree felling should by now include that of language disappearance.

2. Since use is the bedrock of language growth, efforts should be made to use Erúshú in the media, Ondo Radio and Television, public notices on streets in the community, etc. Akoko languages including Erúshú hitherto feature very little, if at all, in media coverage. Hence, the present situation should be improved upon for the survival of these languages and the cultures they represent.

Again, parents, especially mothers should take up with all seriousness the fundamental responsibility of teaching and using Erúshú with their children. Nature has made mothers experts in language teaching and language learning activities. Thus, the issue of language survival can never be tackled without mothers being deeply involved in view of the influence they have on their children most especially during the formative years. Willingness has within itself the power to master all other powers and the ability to influence others flows from inside. It is rooted in what we are. Thus, these Erushu mothers should use their positions and influence to create a lingering and compelling influence for the learning of Erushu language at home by their kids. Erushu should be given the same aura of greatness that surrounds Yoruba in this bilingual speech community if this mother tongue is to survive.

3. A natural corollary to point number 2 is the issue of documentation. Thus, considering its embattled situation now Erushu language should be documented with urgency. Linguistic preservation after all is the easiest kind of preservation. Thus, an orthography, grammar(s), dictionary, oral and folk materials should be devised for Erúshú language. With such documentation, to maintain or even establish a limited role for the language within the society will always be possible.

4. Erushu speakers should set-up language committees like Native California Network (NCN) or Rivers Readers Project (RRP) discussed in section 2.4.5.4 of the study, in order to initiate measures for developing their languages in all ramifications. This committee should impress it on the youths that the natural (i.e. mother tongue) is greater than the artificial (second language). Thus their mother tongue must not at all costs be killed by Yoruba. Erushu language maintenance must first begin in the community itself through voluntary efforts and through community resources in this early stages. This is the bottom-up strategies for preserving language and diversity.
5. The present analysis plus similar ones should be made available to the relevant government agencies such as the National Institute for Nigerian Languages for them to update their analyses of Nigerian languages and thus be better equipped to stem this wave of disappearing languages of Nigeria.
6. State and local governments of the multilingual states on their part should set-up adequate machinery for a more purposeful bilingual education in the macrosense and this must be entrenched in the Nigerian educational system.
7. Although the study has painted a gloomy picture of Erushu language, yet the situation can be saved by also adopting top-down strategies as suggested by Fakuade (2004: 24):

The first one is to make the preservation of languages part of general activism on behalf of the environment. Arguments in favour of supporting linguistic diversity are the same as those used by scientists in favour of protecting biodiversity. This means that linguists and others will have to become activists and convince other international groups such as Cultural Survival, Green Peace, Amnesty

International, the Sierra Club and various local civic groups that language preservation is an important task falling within their remit (Kangas 2000).

The second strategy in Fakuade (2004: 24 – 25) is to establish language policies on a local, regional and national level is part of overall political planning and resource management. That is, establishing an institution for Nigerian languages is not enough. Thus, Nigeria should set up more agencies for language maintenance and development.

6.5 Further Research

In the first place observe that of the three major languages in Erúshú community, the present study has only compared two, Erúshú and Yoruba. Thus, further research can be done on Erúshú-English bilingualism and alternation. Results from such investigation can then be compared with the present one.

Secondly, the competence of the Erúshú people as far as Standard spoken Yoruba is concerned is an area that deserves special investigation. The phonological features that gave the Erúshú man or the Akoko man for that matter his typical accent when speaking Yoruba can then be isolated. Indeed, the different aspects of Erúshú interference with Yoruba language can only be examined in a subsequent work since the whole grammar of the two languages needs to be systematically compared to be able to do this. A fuller comparative study of Erúshú and Yoruba at all linguistic levels to ascertain similarities and differences may throw more light, for instance, on why the Erúshú pronounce Yoruba words the way they do. Moreover, it may shed more light (other than attitude of the youths) on why the Erúshú language is giving way to Yoruba language in this community.

Thirdly, a more comprehensive study on language use and language attitudes among the various communities in Akokoland using a greater number of samples may be necessary for future research. Although, such a research work will take a longer time than this, the need for it is obvious since there are many languages in this area (Akokoland) that compete or co-exist with the Yoruba language. It may thus be

worthwhile to find out what this co-existence pattern will look like in all these areas in the near future.

Moreover, that Erúshú, the native tongue of this community, is giving in to Yoruba in its home front is an indication that Erúshú was never a dialect of Yoruba (personal communication with Oye Taiwo). We conclude this way, since other dialects of Yoruba like Ekiti, Ijesa, Egba are co-existing healthily with the Yorùbá language without any threat of extinction. This assertion however does not imply that Yorùbá dialects are not influenced in any way by the standard Yorùbá. Again, there is the need to document Erúshú now that many speakers are still available. This can only be done with a greater amount of resources expended on the present study.

In conclusion, sociolinguistic variation has become a great field of serious concern to linguists all over the world. Thus, whatever inadequacies the present study might record, it represents another modest contribution to sociolinguistic investigation in Nigeria in particular and in the world in general.

The study makes no pretensions to have exhausted all relevant topics in a language contact situation. Indeed, this is just a humble contribution to studies related to language contact situations. Nevertheless, it is our belief that the work has thrown enough light on the issue of defining bilingualism, language use and language attitude in an African setting as well as language alternation involving two indigenous languages. It is our hope that the work would stimulate a desire for further research in the reader on topic discussed there in and even some other topics left untouched such as the influence of English on these two indigenous languages in Erúshú community.

Notes

- 1 The concept of language endangerment has been severally defined in the literature. The most obvious definition is by number of speakers. Obviously, a language with fewer speakers is more likely to be endangered in comparison with a larger language. Speakers of such languages tend to learn another (more widely spoken) language for purposes of interaction outside their immediate community. Where language loyalty is not strong, it is a short step to language shift and eventual language death (Bamgbose, 1993). Bamgbose opines however that the best definition is the one based on use. Thus, endangered languages belong to a point in a cline of language types ranging from deprived to dying. It follows that, an endangered language, is not used in formal education, and its communicative role is limited to in-group communication such as traditional purposes: rituals, festivals village meetings, etc.

- 2 Akokoland is a race in the Northern part of Ondo State with a multiplicity of languages. Indeed, virtually every town, village and hamlet here speaks a native language in addition to the Yoruba language making the area to be known for its plethora of tongues.

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APPENDIX I

(This was used for the Pilot Study)

QUESTIONNAIRE

Introduction

I am currently carrying out investigation on Erúshú language vis-à-vis Yoruba and English. What is required here is your frank opinion as regards the information required below by me. The information here will be treated in strict confidence and is purely for academic purpose.

Thanks for your anticipated cooperation.

Part I: Personal Data

1. Name.....
2. Sex: Male..... Female.....
3. How old are you?
 - (a) Below 15.....
 - (b) 15 - 20
 - (c) 21 - 30
 - (d) 31 - 40
 - (e) 41 and above
4. Where were you born?
 - (a) Erúshú town?
 - (b) Elsewhere in Akoko community?
 - (c) Elsewhere in the Yoruba - speaking area?
 - (d) Elsewhere in the non-Yoruba -speaking area?

5. (i) Any qualification at all?
 a) Yes
 b) No
 (ii) If yes, state it.....
6. What is your parents' language (s)?
 a) Erúshú
 b) Yoruba
 c) Others (specify)
7. What is/was your occupation?.....
8. Where do you live?
 (a) Lagos
 (b) Erúshú
 (c) Small town/village near Erúshú
 (d) Elsewhere in the Old Akoko-North community.
9. Which of the following languages, do you speak?
 (a) Erúshú
 (b) Yoruba
 (c) English
 (d) Others (specify)
10. Where did you learn Erúshú/Yoruba
 (a) At home.....
 (b) At school.....
 (c) In the neighbourhood.....
 (d) Elsewhere
11. How frequently do you communicate in Erúshú at home?
 (a) Never
 (b) Hardly
 (c) Sometimes
 (d) Always

12. How frequently do you communicate in Yoruba at home?
- (a) Never
 - (b) Hardly
 - (c) Sometimes
 - (d) Always
13. How frequently do you communicate in Erúshú and Yoruba at home?
- (a) Never
 - (b) Hardly
 - (c) Sometimes
 - (d) Always
14. How frequently do you communicate in English at home?
- (a) Never
 - (b) Hardly
 - (c) Sometimes
 - (d) Always
15. In what language (s) do you communicate generally?
- (a) Erúshú
 - (b) Yoruba
 - (c) English
 - (d) Others (specify)

PART II

Language use in different domains in Erùshù

Domain

	Erùshù	Yor	English	Er/Yor	Yor/Eng	Er/Eng
1. Informal - home - with neighbours - work place						
2. Cultural/Social - place of worship - literature - cinema/entertainment						
3. Commercial - big business - small - tourism						
4. Educational - Medium: pry Schl - Sec. Schl - Tertiary - level - medium: Adult - education books, - journals, etc						
5. Political - Parliament - Public rallies						
6. Administration - Village - District/regional - National						
7. Judiciary - Primary court - District court - Magistrate court - High/appeal court						
8. Mass Media - Radio - Daily papers						

APPENDIX II

QUESTIONNAIRE

Introduction

I am currently carrying out investigation on Erushu language vis-à-vis Yoruba and English. What is required here is your frank option as regards the information required below. The information here will be treated in strict confidence and is purely for academic purpose.

Section A

1. Age
2. Sex: Male Female
3. Occupation:
4. Level of Formal Education: Nil

Primary.....

Secondary.....

Post secondary.....

5. Where were you born?
 - a. Erushu town ()
 - b. Elsewhere in Akoko community ()
 - c. Elsewhere in the Yoruba community ()
 - d. Elsewhere in the non-Yoruba-speaking community ()
6. What is your parents' language(s)?
 - a. Erushu ()
 - b. Yoruba()
 - c. Others (specify)

7. Which of the following languages do you speak?
- a. Erushu () b. Yoruba () c. English ()
- d. Others (specify)
8. Where did you learn to speak Erushu/Yoruba?
- a. At home () b. At school ()
- c. In the neighbourhood () d. elsewhere ()
9. How frequently do you communicate in Erushu at home?
- a. Never () b. Hardly ()
- c. Always () d. Sometimes ()
10. How frequently do you communicate in Yoruba at home?
- a. Never () b. Hardly ()
- c. Always () d. Sometimes ()
11. How frequently do you communicate in Erushu and Yoruba at home?
- a. Never () b. Hardly ()
- c. Always () d. Sometimes ()
12. How frequently do you communicate in English at home?
- a. Never () b. Hardly ()
- c. Always () d. Sometimes ()
13. In what language(s) do you communicate generally?
- a. Erushu () b. Yoruba ()
- c. English () d. Others (specify)
14. Which language of the following do you consider to be your best last several years?

15. What changes have you noticed in your language (Erushu) during the last several years?

- a. Less spoken, especially among the youths ()
- b. Renewed interest in it by scholars from Akokoland ()
- c. People are ^{MC} on more comfortable speaking it ()
- d. No essential change/don't know ()

SECTION B

16. Indicate how well you can speak as well as understand Erushu, Yoruba and other languages available to you by putting a tick under any of these.

A Speaking	Poorly	Fairly well	Very well	Excellently
Erushu				
Yoruba				
English				
Others				
b. Understanding	Poorly	Fairly well	Very well	Excellently
Erushu				
Yoruba				
English				
Others				

SECTION C

17. What language would you normally use at home when:

I	(For parents only)	Erushu	Yoruba	English	Mixture of Yoruba and Erushu	Mixture of Yoruba and English	Erushu and English
A.	When talking to my children						
b.	When talking to my wife/husband						
c.	When talking to my relations						
d.	When talking to my neighbour						
e.	When talking to friends who speak the language.						
f.	When discussing important family matters						
II.	(for children only)						
a.	When talking to my parents						
b.	When talking to my grandparents						
c.	When talking to brothers and sisters						
d.	When talking to other children in neighbourhood.						
III	At work for Workers only						
A.	When discussing official matters with superior						
b.	When discussing official matters with subordinate						
c.	When discussing private matters with our superior						
d.	When discussing official matters with your equals						
e.	When discussing private matters with one's subordinate						
f.	When merely chatting with others during break						

IV	At school (for those schooling)						
a.	When talking formally						
b.	When talking to classmates						
c.	When talking to seniors						
d.	When talking to juniors						
f.	When talking generally during break						
V.	In the Church/Mosque						
a.	When singing						
b.	When making announcements						
c.	When preaching						
d.	When praying generally during the service						
f.	When talking to the church/mosque officials						
g.	When talking to other members of the congregation						
VI	In the market						
a.	When buying or selling to a customer						
.	who understands/speaks both Erushu						

SECTION D

18. In which of the following languages do you prefer to listen to news broadcast

a. Erushu () b. Yoruba ()

c. English d. Others (specify)

a. Why do you prefer to listen to news broadcast in that language?

b. I have better proficiency in it

c. It is the language usually used for broadcast

d. It is good, fluent and better than other language

e. It is more important to me than any other language

f It enables me to identify with people from my town

g I want to improve my proficiency in it

20 Which of the following languages do you consider most prestigious?

a. Erushu b. Yoruba

c. English d. Others (specify)

21. Why do you consider it most prestigious?

a. It is most useful to speak it than other languages

b. It is the language of my forefathers, therefore I should be proud of it

c. There are many people who speak it apart from its native

d. It is good, fluent and better than other language

e. It can be used for all purpose

22. Why did you learn Erushu?

a. I consider Erushu an important for my trade

b. I consider Erushu an important language worthy to know in Nigeria

c. So that I can interact freely with Erushu speakers

d. I can easily know when I am being insulated

e. The language is pleasant to ears

f. I like Erushu speakers

g. I wish to be identified with Erushu speakers

h. So that people may know my true identity

23. If hitherto you don't speak Erushu, could you have learnt it

a. Yes No

26. Why would you have loved to learn it?
- a. I love the language
 - b. It is indispensable
 - c. I cherish ability to use many languages
 - d. I like to be identified with the Erushu
 - e. I consider Erushu an important language worthy to know in Nigeria
27. If hitherto you don't speak Yoruba, would you have learnt it.
28. Why would you have loved to learn it?
- a. I love the language
 - b. It is indispensable
 - c. I cherish ability to use many languages
 - d. I like to be identified with the Erushu
 - e. I consider Erushu an important language worthy to know in Nigeria